

Swiss Institute
for Global Affairs
www.globalaffairs.ch

SIGA

Das Swiss Institute for Global Affairs SIGA betreibt, unterstützt und fördert interdisziplinäre Forschung zu geo- und sicherheitspolitischen Themen. Ziel ist es, die Sichtbarkeit für diese Themengebiete zu schaffen sowie neue Ansätze in der Analyse und Methodik zu erarbeiten. Dabei steht im Vordergrund, die breite Öffentlichkeit für diese Themen zu sensibilisieren sowie Übersetzungs- und Vermittlungsarbeit zwischen Wissenschaft, Politik und Wirtschaft zu leisten. Das Institut versteht sich als unabhängiger Think Tank und Brückenbauer zwischen den unterschiedlichen Disziplinen und Sphären.

KONTAKT

Swiss Institute for Global Affairs
Effingerstrasse 10
3011 Bern
team@globalaffairs.ch
+41 (0)31 552 01 20

SIGA Study

INDIA, THE MISUNDERSTOOD SUPERPOWER?

COLLECTED INSIGHTS AND STRATEGIC OUTLOOK

Edited by Remo Reginold

A study by the Swiss Institute for Global Affairs (SIGA),
December 2025

India, the Misunderstood Superpower?

Collected Insights and Strategic Outlook

Edited by Dr. Remo Reginold

A study by the Swiss Institute for Global Affairs (SIGA),

December 2025

Foreword

The Swiss Institute for Global Affairs (SIGA) has been monitoring strategic developments in the Indo-Pacific, or rather the Asia-Pacific region, for some time. The rise and positioning of China is the central factor in this area. The future of world politics appears increasingly dependent on developments in Beijing. Yet it seems that Beijing is not the only actor shaping the dynamics of the region. The 21st century is often referred to as the *Asian Century*, a term that creates a set of projections and expectations for a vast region that is politically, culturally, and economically highly diverse and difficult to grasp. In addition to China, India is also considered a significant player in the context of the Asian Century. However, there is less certainty regarding the actual resources and options available to India. It is often said – perhaps for far too long – that India is on the rise and about to establish new standards in diplomacy, the economy, and culture. So far, however, this has not materialised, at least according to the prevailing sentiment in the West.

In line with the title of this publication, this collection of essays seeks to explore the extent to which India has the potential to play a leading role internationally, whether it is under- or overestimated, and what strategic agenda the Modi government is pursuing. Through the various contributions in this volume, a common thread is intended to emerge: identifying and connecting the elements and building blocks of New Delhi's strategic culture. Put differently, the core aim of this publication is to distil India's geopolitical self-understanding and to uncover what its deeply rooted patterns of thought, values, historical context, and security strategies signify.

The collection does not follow a neatly defined structure, yet three clusters can be identified: politics, security dynamics, as well as technology and research. We have deliberately refrained from imposing a perfectly balanced thematic architecture. It should leave space for contingent relationships and interpretive linkages. Economic analysis, as well as domestic political and demographic dimensions, are entirely absent. The publication draws primarily on contributions from the SIGA Fellows of the South Asia Desk, and the topics therefore reflect their areas of expertise.

With these contributions, SIGA hopes to strengthen awareness of a world region that is economically and politically highly interconnected, yet culturally and politically not always easy to interpret.

Dr. Remo Reginold, President SIGA

Tables

1. Hindu Nationalism's Impact on India's Foreign Policy	5
2. India Through the Chinese Lens: Perceptual Shifts in the Context of US-China Geopolitical Rivalry	11
3. From Autonomy to Alignment: India's Strategic Turn to the United States in the China Era	19
4. India, South Asia, and Their Regional Organisations	28
The Kashmir Issue	34
5. Hardships of the People of Azad Jammu & Kashmir: From the Beginning to Today	34
6. Kashmir: Between Fear, Hope and The Politics of Supression	47
7. Strategic Outlook on Indian Defence and Security Establishment.....	52
8. Indian Intelligence Culture: A Strategic Outlook.....	61
9. International Solar Alliance (ISA), India and the Geopolitics of Solar Power	68
10. Geopolitics of Outer Space: Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) and Its Strategy	75
11. India's Arctic Ambitions: A Multifaceted Engagement in a Transforming Region	82

1. Hindu Nationalism's Impact on India's Foreign Policy

Dr. Anugrah Kumar (pseud)*

New Delhi's «New» Assertive Diplomacy Aligns with Western Interests but Undermines Rights at Home and Stability in South Asia

The ascendance of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) to power in India in 2014, under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi, has ushered in a transformative era in Indian foreign policy. The shift is deeply rooted in the ideology of Hindu nationalism, locally known as *Hindutva*, which forms the core of the BJP's political philosophy. The ideology is reshaping India's relations with its neighbours, its positions on global issues and its projection of soft power, while also having damaging effects at home.

Hindu nationalism, as propagated by the BJP and its ideological parent organisation, the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS), envisions India as a Hindu nation, focused on the cultural and religious heritage of the majority Hindu population. This worldview has translated into a more assertive and culturally driven foreign policy, marking a significant departure from the Nehruvian principles of secularism and non-alignment that guided India's international relations for decades after the 1947 independence from British rule.

Rooted in Jawaharlal Nehru's vision, secularism meant that India would not let religion dictate its foreign policy, maintaining equal distance from all religious blocs and ideologies. At the same time, the policy of non-alignment allowed India to resist joining either the Western or Soviet blocs during the Cold War, asserting its strategic autonomy while advocating for peaceful coexistence, anti-colonial solidarity and global disarmament. These principles positioned India as a moral voice in international

forums and helped build ties with newly decolonised nations across Asia, Africa and Latin America.

The manifestation of Hindu nationalism in India's foreign policy is evident in several key areas. One of the most notable shifts has been in the realm of diplomatic language and cultural projection.

Promotion of Hindi Language

The Modi government has actively promoted the use of Hindi, which is primarily spoken in northern India – where the national capital is located – in international forums, moving away from the traditional reliance on English. This linguistic assertion is not merely a matter of communication preference but a deliberate strategy, viewed through the lens of Hindu nationalists, to project India's cultural identity on the global stage.

India has no “national” language, a fact clearly established by the Indian Constitution. [Article 343\(1\)](#)¹ designates Hindi in Devanagari script as the official language of the “Union,” alongside English, but no provision grants it the status of a national language. The [Eighth Schedule](#)² of the Constitution recognises 22 languages. However, Hindu nationalists have [pushed to position Hindi](#)³ as the singular national language, promoting its use in government, education and cultural narratives. This has sparked opposition within India, especially from non-Hindi-speaking states, especially Tamil Nadu and Kerala in the south, where linguistic identity is tied to regional autonomy and constitutional rights.

According to a report by the Indian Ministry of External Affairs, since 2014, there has been a concerted effort to increase the use of Hindi in United Nations forums. This initiative culminated in a significant milestone in 2018 when India [signed](#)⁴ a Voluntary Financial Contribution Agreement with the UN to promote Hindi within the UN system. This agreement, which was extended for another five

* Pseudonym des Autors; echter Name der Redaktion SIGA bekannt.

¹ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/379861/> (November 26, 2025)

² <https://www.mea.gov.in/Images/pdf1/S8.pdf> (November 26, 2025)

³ <https://thediomat.com/2025/02/modi-governments-language-policy-reignites-old-conflict-in-southern-india/> (November 26, 2025)

⁴

<https://sansad.in/getFile/loksabhaquestions/annex/178/AU4098.pdf?source=pqals> (November 26, 2025)

years in 2019 and remained in force until March 2025, has led to tangible changes in the UN's linguistic landscape.

Modi has consistently chosen to [deliver speeches in Hindi](#)⁵ at various international platforms, including the United Nations General Assembly sessions. This choice of language represents a departure from the practice of previous Indian leaders who typically addressed such forums in English.

Further, India co-sponsored the UN General Assembly [Resolution A/RES/76/268](#)⁶ on "Multilingualism," which was unanimously adopted on June 10, 2022. The resolution, for the first time, explicitly mentioned Hindi, encouraging the UN Department of Global Communications to disseminate important communications in Hindi.

The UN has launched Hindi social media accounts on platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. Furthermore, the UN now maintains a [Hindi website](#)⁷ for UN News and broadcasts programs in Hindi, including a weekly Hindi news bulletin.

Promotion of Culture

Apart from promoting Hindi, there is an emphasis on exporting aspects of Indian culture closely tied to Hinduism, creating the impression that India is not just Hindu-majority but a Hindu country.

As per the 2011 Census, about 79.8% of India's population is Hindu, 14.2% is Muslim, 2.3% is Christian and 1.7% belongs to other religions including Sikhism, Buddhism, Jainism and tribal faiths. The Constitution of India guarantees freedom of religion under Article 25, allowing every individual the right to profess, practise and propagate their faith. It declares India a secular state, meaning the state does not favour or discriminate against any

religion. Articles 26 to 28 further protect religious denominations in managing their affairs, grant freedom to establish and maintain religious institutions, and bar religious instruction in state-funded educational institutions. The Constitution also prohibits discrimination on religious grounds and affirms the right of all communities to preserve their distinct language, script and culture.

Indian embassies worldwide have increased their engagement in celebrating Hindu festivals for cultural diplomacy. For example, Diwali, the Hindu festival of lights, is now celebrated at [various embassies](#)⁸.

Indian embassies around the world have increasingly embraced Hindu festivals as part of their cultural diplomacy efforts. Diwali, the festival of lights, has become a prominent event in many diplomatic missions. For instance, the Indian Embassy in Guatemala [organised](#)⁹ a grand Diwali celebration in November 2024, attracting over 500 guests from both Indian and Guatemalan communities. The event featured Bollywood dance performances and traditional Indian attire, fostering cultural exchange between the two nations.

Similarly, in Bangkok, the "Amazing Thailand Diwali Festival 2024" was [held](#) in the city's Little India district¹⁰.

These celebrations are not limited to Diwali. The Indian Embassy in Iceland organised a Holi Utsav in March 2024, featuring music and dance performances by the Indian diaspora and local participants.

Further, India has signed Cultural Exchange Programmes (CEPs) with [78 countries](#)¹¹, which include the exchange of artistic talents and the promotion of mutual understanding through cultural dialogue. The Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR), which implements many of these programmes, regularly sends classical and folk

⁵ <https://www.indiatvnews.com/news/india/world-hindi-day-2024-india-pm-narendra-modi-push-for-promoting-hindi-internationally-globally-in-the-world-unga-uns-India-latest-updates-2024-01-10-910988> (November 26, 2025)

⁶ <https://docs.un.org/en/A/RES/76/268> (November 26, 2025)

⁷ <https://news.un.org/hi/> (November 26, 2025)

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0Pnlwy4cp4s> (November 26, 2025)

⁹ <https://www.theindianpanorama.news/unitedstates/indian-embassy-in-guatemala-organizes-a-fabulous-diwali-festival/> (November 26, 2025)

¹⁰ <https://www.indianewsnetwork.com/en/20241101/india-and-thailand-celebrate-cultural-bond-through-the-amazing-thailand-diwali-festival> (November 26, 2025)

¹¹ <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2043021> (November 26, 2025)

dance troupes abroad – performing forms like Bharatanatyam, Kathak and Odissi, many of which have roots in Hindu mythology, as reflected in the [ICCR's Annual Report 2023–24](#)¹².

While not all events under these CEPs focus solely on Hindu traditions, many performances draw on religious epics or temple art forms, shaping how Indian culture is represented internationally.

While India is a multi-religious country with no state religion, events promoted through cultural diplomacy often focus on Hindu traditions, with occasional inclusion of Buddhist themes – particularly in the context of India's Act East Policy. For example, cultural festivals in Southeast Asian countries frequently feature performances based on the Ramayana or classical Hindu dance forms. Similarly, India has supported Buddhist exhibitions and conferences in countries like Thailand, Vietnam and Japan, highlighting shared religious heritage.

However, representation of other Indian religious traditions—such as Islam, Christianity or Sikhism—in state-led cultural initiatives remains limited, despite Christianity's early presence in India through St. Thomas the Apostle and the country being home to the world's third-largest Muslim population.

Furthermore, the establishment of [International Yoga Day](#)¹³ in 2014 by the United Nations is seen as a strategic move to project India's cultural influence globally. The initiative, spearheaded by the Ministry of External Affairs, is considered one of Modi's significant foreign policies. The International Day of Yoga is now celebrated by Indian embassies worldwide.

Yoga, though widely practiced as a secular discipline, has [deep roots in Hinduism](#)¹⁴. Its origins trace back to ancient Hindu texts, including the Vedas and the Upanishads, where it was described as a spiritual practice for self-realisation and union with the divine. While modern adaptations focus on its health

benefits, yoga remains deeply intertwined with Hindu philosophy and traditions.

Now, let's examine India's assertive diplomacy.

Regional Assertion

It's important to note here that Hindu nationalist ideology envisions *Akhand Bharat* (Undivided India), a reunification of territories that were once part of what is often loosely referred to as “pre-Partition India,” including present-day Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Sri Lanka and parts of Afghanistan and Myanmar. However, this notion rests on a mythologised idea of a unified Indian nation.

Historically, India as a single political entity did not exist before 1947. The subcontinent was a mosaic of over 500 princely states, colonial provinces under British rule, and regions with varying degrees of autonomy. Even under British rule, there was no cohesive national structure encompassing the entire region; administrative control was fragmented between directly ruled territories and semi-sovereign princely states.

The political construct known as “India” came into being only at the time of Independence and Partition in 1947, when the modern nation-state was formed. The *Akhand Bharat* vision, therefore, imagines a unity that never historically existed as a political reality.

While largely symbolic, ruling party leaders and [BJP's ideological affiliates](#)¹⁵ have referred to *Akhand Bharat*, sometimes stirring diplomatic tensions with neighbouring countries.

While the Indian government officially maintains a commitment to sovereign borders, this vision appears to align with India's emphasis on cultural diplomacy, outreach to Hindu communities beyond

¹² <https://iccr.gov.in/sites/default/files/sites/default/files/2024-02/Annual%20Report%202023-24%20%28English%29.pdf> (November 26, 2025)

¹³ <https://pminewyork.gov.in/pdf/Yoga.pdf> (November 26, 2025)

¹⁴ <https://www.hinduamerican.org/projects/hindu-roots-of-yoga> (November 26, 2025)

¹⁵ <https://network.aljazeera.net/en/pressroom/bjp-leader-ram-madhav-believes-india-pakistan-and-bangladesh-will-reunite-form-undivided> (November 26, 2025)

its borders and a stronger push for regional leadership or hegemony.

To assert such leadership or national pride, the BJP government has shown a readiness to use military force in response to perceived threats, signalling a shift from India's traditional policy of strategic restraint. This was most evident during the four-day conflict with Pakistan in May 2025.

The clashes began after a deadly attack on civilians in Indian-administered Kashmir, which India attributed to Pakistan-based militants. In retaliation, India launched "Operation Sindoor," targeting alleged militant infrastructure in Pakistan and Pakistan-administered Kashmir. India named it "Operation Sindoor" as a symbolic gesture referring to the red vermilion worn by married Hindu women, framing the attack on Hindu pilgrims as an assault on religious sanctity.

In 2016, New Delhi carried out "[surgical strikes](#)"¹⁶ across the Line of Control in Pakistan-administered Kashmir, and [airstrikes in Balakot](#)¹⁷, Pakistan, in 2019.

The surgical strikes were a response to a terrorist attack on an Indian Army base in Uri, Kashmir. While Pakistan denied that any such operation had taken place, the Indian government presented these strikes as a demonstration of its resolve to combat cross-border terrorism.

The Balakot airstrikes of 2019 represented an even more significant escalation. Following a [terrorist attack in Pulwama, Kashmir](#)¹⁸, that killed 40 Indian security personnel, India conducted airstrikes on what it claimed was a terrorist training camp in Balakot, deep inside Pakistani territory. This marked the first time since the 1971 war that India had used air power against Pakistan in undisputed Pakistani territory. The strikes were widely publicised by the

Indian government and media, further fuelling nationalist sentiment and projecting an image of a more militarily assertive India.

These three military actions, since 2014, not only projected India's military capabilities but also served to stoke nationalist sentiment within the country.

The government's rhetoric surrounding these operations often invoked themes of national pride and Hindu cultural resilience. Prime Minister Modi, in his [public addresses](#)¹⁹ following the first two operations, frequently used phrases that resonated with Hindu nationalist sentiments, such as referring to the "surgical strikes" as a response befitting a "New India."

The Modi government has taken a firm stance also during border standoffs with China, notably in [Doklam in 2017](#)²⁰ and [Ladakh in 2020-2021](#)²¹. The government instructed the Indian Army to stand its ground during these clashes.

Furthermore, the implementation of policies like the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) of 2019, which offers fast-track citizenship to non-Muslim refugees from neighbouring countries, has strained relations with Bangladesh. This act is perceived as discriminatory against Muslims and has [raised concerns in Bangladesh](#)²² about the treatment of its citizens and potential migration.

India's perceived interference in Nepal's internal affairs, often attributed to the BJP's ideological leanings, has led to diplomatic friction. The [unofficial blockade](#)²³ of Nepal in 2015, following the promulgation of Nepal's new secular constitution, was seen by many as an attempt to influence Nepal's political landscape in favour of Hindu interests.

In 2015, after Nepal adopted a new secular constitution, India's alleged blockade coincided with protests by Nepal's Madhesi community – an ethnic

¹⁶ <https://www.nytimes.com/2016/09/30/world/asia/kashmir-india-pakistan.html> (November 26, 2025)

¹⁷ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-47366718> (November 26, 2025)

¹⁸ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-47302467> (November 26, 2025)

¹⁹ <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/pm-modi-remembers-uri-surgical-strike-when-bjp-govt-responded-to-bullets-101727509881982.html> (November 26, 2025)

²⁰ <https://warontherocks.com/2018/06/doklam-one-year-later-chinas-long-game-in-the-himalayas/> (November 26, 2025)

²¹ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-53062484> (November 26, 2025)

²² <https://www.internationalaffairs.org.au/australianoutlook/citizenship-amendment-act-implications-for-bangladesh-and-other-south-asian-countries/> (November 26, 2025)

²³ <https://thediplomat.com/2015/11/r-i-p-indias-influence-in-nepal/> (November 26, 2025)

group with close ties to India – who opposed aspects of the new constitution. Many in Nepal viewed the blockade as a pressure tactic by India to influence constitutional changes and promote a political environment more aligned with Hindu interests, particularly because Hindu nationalist groups in India had openly criticised Nepal's move away from its earlier Hindu state identity.

Furthermore, India has pursued strategic partnerships that align with its nationalist agenda and assertive foreign policy.

India's active participation in the [Quadrilateral Security Dialogue](#)²⁴ with the U.S., Japan and Australia reflects its assertive stance in the Indo-Pacific region, particularly in countering China's influence. India has also worked to enhance its military capabilities and strategic autonomy by strengthening defence ties with countries such as the U.S., France and Israel, securing major defence procurement deals.

Western Interests

The influence of Hindu nationalism on India's foreign policy has found resonance with Western interests, particularly those of the United States, in the context of growing competition with China, particularly in the Indo-Pacific region. This alignment is evident in the deepening of strategic partnerships, increased defence cooperation and growing economic ties between India and Western nations.

The United States, in particular, designated India as a Major Defense Partner in 2016, facilitating India's access to advanced military technologies and leading to substantial defence trade between the two countries. According to the U.S. Department of State, U.S.-India defence trade grew from virtually nothing in 2008 to [over \\$20 billion](#)²⁵ in 2020.

Furthermore, the U.S.-India initiative on Critical and Emerging Technology ([iCET](#)), launched in 2023, is a framework designed to deepen technological and economic cooperation. The iCET has facilitated collaborations in areas such as semiconductor chip design and production.

This strategic convergence has led to a situation where Western nations, particularly the United States, have often focused more on geopolitical interests than concerns about civil and political [rights violations](#)²⁶ within India. The Modi government's controversial domestic policies, including the suppression of dissent, restrictions on media freedom and the marginalisation of minority groups, have faced relatively muted responses from Western allies.

Concerns Over Rights in India

While India's ties with Western nations have strengthened under the BJP administration, this period has also seen a decline in civil and political rights.

Human rights organisations and NGOs have documented significant concerns about the erosion of civil and political rights in India since 2014. According to the 2023 [Country Reports on Human Rights Practices](#)²⁷, there have been credible reports of arbitrary or unlawful killings, including extrajudicial killings by government forces. Between 2016 and 2022, India registered 813 cases of extrajudicial killings, with the most reported in Chhattisgarh and Uttar Pradesh.

Freedom of expression and media freedom have also faced significant challenges. India was ranked 151 out of 176 countries in the [2025 Press Freedom Index](#)²⁸ by Reporters Without Borders. The government has been accused of using defamation, sedition and national security laws to silence critical

²⁴ <https://gija.georgetown.edu/2023/05/01/engagement-not-entanglement-indias-relationship-with-the-quad/> (November 26, 2025)

²⁵ <https://www.state.gov/u-s-security-cooperation-with-india/> (November 26, 2025)

²⁶ <https://www.businesstoday.in/india/story/india-didnt-meet-threshold-for-designation-as-country-of-particular-concern-us-on-uscirf-report-on-religious-freedom-449288-2024-10-09> (November 26, 2025)

²⁷ <https://www.state.gov/reports/2023-country-reports-on-human-rights-practices/india/> (November 26, 2025)

²⁸ <https://rsf.org/en/country/india> (November 26, 2025)

voices. Moreover, India has been identified as the “[world’s largest offender](#)”²⁹ for internet shutdowns.

Religious freedom and minority rights have also been areas of concern.

The U.S. Commission on International Religious Freedom ([USCIRF](#)³⁰) has recommended designating India as a “Country of Particular Concern” due to systematic violations of religious freedom. These concerns include incidents of cow vigilantism, attacks on Muslim and Christian minorities, and the enactment of laws in several states that restrict religious conversions. However, the U.S. Department of State has so far declined to adopt this recommendation.

Further, despite these documented human rights concerns, Western nations have largely maintained their strategic partnerships with India, potentially emboldening the Indian government to continue its controversial policies.

Beyond India’s borders, this ideologically driven foreign policy has significantly affected South Asian stability. Relations with neighbouring countries, particularly Pakistan and China, have grown increasingly tense.

The [revocation](#)³¹ of Article 370 of the Constitution, which granted special status to Jammu and Kashmir, was a move aligned with the BJP’s Hindu nationalist agenda and has intensified historical tensions with Pakistan, which claims parts of the region as disputed territory. The unilateral decision, made in August 2019, restructured Jammu and Kashmir into two Union territories, stripping it of its autonomy. This move triggered widespread protests, a security crackdown and international concern over its implications for regional stability and human rights.

Similarly, India’s more confrontational stance towards China, as seen in border standoffs and economic measures, reflects a departure from the cautious engagement of previous administrations. The [Galwan Valley clash](#)³² in June 2020, which resulted in the deaths of 20 Indian soldiers and an undisclosed number of Chinese troops, marked the most serious military confrontation between the two countries in decades. The incident led to a series of economic measures by India against Chinese interests, including [bans on Chinese apps](#)³³ and restrictions on Chinese investments.

Conclusion

India’s foreign policy under the BJP has undergone a clear ideological shift, driven by Hindu nationalism. This transformation has produced a more assertive global posture, aligning India more closely with Western strategic interests, particularly in the Indo-Pacific. Yet, this assertiveness abroad is matched by increasing repression at home and growing instability in South Asia. The blending of religious nationalism with foreign policy has marginalised India’s secular democratic foundations, strained regional relationships and weakened its moral authority on the global stage.

While India’s rise as a strategic partner may serve Western geopolitical goals, the costs – in terms of internal democratic decline and regional volatility – are becoming impossible to ignore. The West must recognise that their short-term geopolitical gains may come at the cost of long-term democratic erosion in India and regional instability in South Asia.

** The author is known to the editorial team*

²⁹ <https://www.tbsnews.net/world/south-asia/india-country-most-internet-shutdowns-4th-time-85-ik-alone-report-411126> (November 26, 2025)

³⁰ <https://www.uscifr.gov/news-room/releases-statements/uscifr-releases-report-indias-collapsing-religious-freedom-conditions> (November 26, 2025)

³¹ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-67634689> (November 26, 2025)

³² <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-53076781> (November 26, 2025)

³³ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-53232486> (November 26, 2025)

2. India Through the Chinese Lens: Perceptual Shifts in the Context of US-China Geopolitical Rivalry

*Ayesha Khalid Chaudhry**

This study investigates the changing character of China's strategic perception of India within the context of the US-China competition. Traditionally regarded by Beijing as a peripheral strategic actor, constrained in capability and influence, and thus manageable within its broader regional security calculus, India is now increasingly seen as a pivotal player aligned with U.S.-led containment efforts. Using qualitative analysis of open-source Chinese discourse, the study notes that India's growing involvement in the QUAD, acceptance of the Indo-Pacific concept, and rising defense cooperation with Washington are all components that clearly influence China's threat assessments. The results point toward a major change in Sino-Indian ties, which has ramifications for increased strategic competition and regional instability across the Indo-Pacific.

The shifting dynamics of big power competition have significantly altered the strategic geography of the Indo-Pacific. The increasing geopolitical rivalry between the United States and China is at the heart of this transformation. New security alignments, elevated threat perceptions, and reimagined strategic priorities of regional states have all been sparked from this competition. One of the most significant changes is China's changing strategic view of India (Verma, 2025). The India-China feud has typically been seen in terms of territorial disagreements, power imbalances, and mutual suspicion. However, China's strategic thinking has undergone a shift as a result of its expanding strategic ties with the United States and its active

participation in multilateral security initiatives (Yao and Li, 2025). Despite the expanding number of studies examining India's growing impact in the Indo-Pacific strategy (Li and Jiang, 2023) (Singh and Marwah, 2024) and the closer strategic partnership between the United States and India (Nisar, 2023), there hasn't been much theoretical work done on how China views India's role in U.S.-led containment measures. This essay fills that hole by claiming that India is perceived by Beijing as a major strategic competitor allied with the United States rather than as a peripheral regional actor. This perceptual transformation reflects a structural response to the shifting balance of power in the Indo-Pacific rather than just a bilateral adjustment.

This study argues that systemic pressures and strategic balancing shape China's recalibrated threat perception. Its foundation is the neorealist theoretical framework, which highlights the anarchic character of the global system and the significance of material resources and alignments in affecting state conduct (Waltz, 1990). In this view, Beijing sees India's expanding military prowess, deeper defence cooperation with Washington, and participation in alliances like the QUAD as components of a larger countervailing coalition aimed at containing China's rise (Lindgren, 2025). Consequently, Chinese discourse now portrays India more and more as a regional competitor as well as an active participant in a containment strategy led by the United States. To explore this shifting perspective, the article qualitatively examines Chinese strategic narratives from 2017 to 2025 using English-language sources such as official statements, state-affiliated media (such as Global Times), academic journals, and think tank analysis. This approach facilitates the discovery of discursive continuities and changes in how India is portrayed in Chinese strategic thought. The article is divided into three parts. The first looks at China's historical perspective of India as a second-tier nation. The second examines the increasing idea that India is crucial to the US-led containment plan. The effects of this transformation on the dynamics of Indo-Pacific

security are discussed in the conclusion.

China's Traditional Perception of India: A Regional Rival

China's conventional view of India is shaped by a delicate combination of structural power disparities, strategic compartmentalization, and deliberate diplomatic engagement. Under a neorealist lens, Chinese strategic thinking has long seen India as a geographically close but hierarchically lower power in the Asian order. Beijing has usually regarded India as devoid of the economic vitality, technical sophistication, and international clout needed to mount a credible threat to China's rise. Based on relative power computations, this assessment has resulted in the view of India as a second-tier regional player whose strategic alliances are important to watch but not inherently alarming (Garver, 2002). China's main strategic need against India throughout the Cold War was to stop it from becoming part of any unfriendly bloc – especially one headed by the United States. China's dependence on diplomatic pragmatism and India's own strategic culture of non-alignment mostly achieved this goal (Wang, 2011). Early Indian support for China's peaceful rise, including Prime Minister Nehru's declaration in 1954 that China had no hostile designs and its defense of China in international fora such as the 1956 Commonwealth Heads of Government Meeting, bolstered Chinese confidence in India's opposition to alignment with Western security designs (Indian Defense Research Wing, 2025).

Crystallized in the 1962 conflict, the unresolved border conflict did not fundamentally change this strategic view. China's attitude toward the Line of Actual Control (LAC) has traditionally been steered by the conviction that boundary tensions might be kept separate and controlled without spilling over into more general geopolitical hostility. Zhou Enlai's statements in the post-war era stressed a will to rebuild friendly relations (Dobell, 1964), and later events like the Depsang (2013) and Chumar (2014)

standoffs were understood in Beijing as tactical disturbances rather than signals of systematic competition (Mehta, 2023). Though Beijing was not unaware of India's ability to interfere with Chinese maritime routes of communication, compete in international supply chains, and oppose China in multilateral forums (Hailin, 2014). But it considered New Delhi a rather manageable peripheral actor (Fernando, 2012). Consequently, China's policy included strengthening its strategic relationship with Pakistan in addition to engaging India diplomatically and economically (Wang, 2011). By using this dual-track strategy, China was able to concurrently limit India's regional goals. India was seen here as a regional player whose trajectory could be influenced by diplomatic incentives, measured balancing, and strategic signaling rather than as an existential challenge.

Even Beijing responded with remarkable composure to the nuclear tests conducted by India in 1998, as well as the simultaneous naming of China as the threat and primary cause of this event. China chose to restart diplomatic relations and border discussions within months, rather than make the situation worse, even if it was critical of the exams (Shirk, 2002). This moderate reaction was fuelled by a long-held belief in the manageability of the Indian challenge and an understanding that an overreaction would bring India closer to the United States. Beijing continued to engage India economically and diplomatically, even as Chinese academics, like Hongyi Nie, saw India's nuclearization as a component of its push for superpower status (Verma, 2025), as it remained confident in its own dominant position in the regional order. Strategic stories started to tentatively converge in the early 2000s with both nations stressing the need of peaceful coexistence as rising Asian powers, the return of the slogan "Hindi-Chini Bhai Bhai" (cf. Indians and Chinese are brothers) captured a rhetorical optimism anchored in shared interests including multipolarity, South-South cooperation, and reform of world institutions (Madan, 2024). This era saw the institutionalization of bilateral mechanisms aimed to convert geopolitical restraint

into practical collaboration: Strategic and Economic Dialogues, Confidence Building Measures, and increased economic ties (Wang, 2011).

As the Modi government emerged in 2014, this cooperative phase started to fall apart. Though Chinese rhetoric during this time focused on regional coordination and economic complementarity (Jingjie, 2014; Zhendong, 2014), Beijing was quickly put on alert by Modi's aggressive foreign policy and closer relationship with the U.S. China opposed the 2015 U.S.-India Joint Strategic Vision and was concerned about Japan's role in naval operations between India and the United States. India started opposing the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), a flagship Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) project (Madan, 2020). The relationship between India and China deteriorated further when China denied India's application to the Nuclear Supplier Group (NSG) in 2016 and opposed UN sanctions against Masood Azhar, reinforcing India's perception of China's strategic support for Pakistan. In response, India adopted a more aggressive stance, such as allowing the Dalai Lama to visit Tawang in 2017, a region that China claims (Cohen, 2024). Even in the face of Chinese overtures such as Ambassador Luo Zhaohui's suggestion to rename CPEC, India remained cautious, viewing the BRI as a means for Chinese neo-colonialism (Park, 2017).

India's border security plan also shifted towards aggressive command and ambitious infrastructure construction, which ultimately led to the Doklam conflict in 2017. India's impediment in Bhutanese home to prevent Chinese road construction near the India-China-Bhutan tri-junction was seen by Beijing as a symbolic demonstration of geopolitical opposition as well as a logical barrier (Cohen, 2024). Chinese accounts following Doklam highlighted India's "hegemonic gesture" and "strategic overreach," implying a perceptual shift from India as manageable to one of decreasingly revisionist and inspired by foreign collaboration (Singh, 2022b). Still, a group of Chinese strategists believed that the chances for improving Sino-Indian ties were promising. They advocated greater positive

interaction with India to prevent it from straying further into the U.S.-led strategic orbit. Some even advocated providing benefits – including supporting India's attempt for NSG membership – in exchange for India's endorsement or at least a neutral stance on China's BRI (Shisheng, 2018). President Xi Jinping's words also reflected this conciliatory approach: "We cannot only dwell on differences and disregard friendship and cooperation" (Minwang, 2018). Overall, China perception of India as a threat started to emerge by this point. India's closeness with the U.S., and assertiveness on Tibet, NSG, and CPEC were seen as elements of a larger containment policy. This signalled a major change in Chinese threat perception: India was viewed as a competitor with the will and ability to limit China's rise, rather than as a controllable regional player.

Shifting Perceptions: India in the US-Led Strategic Framework

Since the growing Sino-American rivalry and the emergence of the Indo-Pacific notion, India's position within the changing strategic framework led by the United States has undergone a major shift, especially in Chinese strategic thinking. As Beijing has increasingly seen New Delhi as a key hub in a larger containment strategy led by Washington, its initial cautious and sometimes dismissive evaluation of India's strategic intent has gradually shifted into a more worried and hostile perspective (Xinkai, 2012; Hailin, 2019; Guihong, 2019). Zhang Weiwei, a well-known Chinese academic, and Wu Shicun, president of the National Institute for South China Sea Studies, both highlighted that Washington depends on India more than any other nation to counter China's rise (Shicun and Colombage, 2019). This change in perspective is more influenced by India's adaptive alignment to changing regional dynamics and systemic changes than by ideological divides or bilateral disputes. As the United States strengthens its strategic presence in the Indo-Pacific through revived alliances and new security agreements, India's active participation in these initiatives has

raised its significance in Chinese threat assessments (Liping, 2015; Global Times, 2020). Beijing now sees India's growing strategic confidence and presence in the area as real threats to China's maritime interests, such as the security of its sea lines of communication (SLOCs) and the long-term execution of the BRI. Ambassador Yuan Nansheng, the former Chinese Consul General in Mumbai, emphasized the strategic value of India's naval capabilities, aircraft carriers and their capacity to extend power across vital maritime chokepoints like the Strait of Malacca (Singh, 2022a). Similarly, Mao Yue, a Chinese specialist, believes that India's opposition to the BRI is indicative of its broader objective of establishing itself as a dominant player in the world (Cohen, 2024). Rong Ying, Vice President of the China Institute of International Studies (CIIS), a well-known think tank under the Chinese Foreign Ministry, has suggested that India's regional strategy is centred on developing India-centric multilateral frameworks to increase its influence throughout the Indian Ocean, thus strengthening its position as a regional security provider (Times of India, 2018).

Notably, the 2020 Galwan episode was both a tactical military battle and a strategic turning point that prompted a large reorientation in China's opinion of India. According to Ye Hailin (2020), Chinese experts saw the confrontation as evidence that Beijing's former diplomatic and deterrence-focused strategy had fallen short and that more resolute actions were necessary to reconfirm Beijing's strategic upper hand. Ironically, this more aggressive posture triggered a more dramatic strategic shift in India's orientation, which Beijing has seen more and more alarming. India speeded its matching with other like-minded countries and the United States (Global Times, 2020; Xing, 2022; Feng, 2024). Deeper defense collaboration, improved interoperability, and increasingly convergent threat assessments have underpinned this shift from strategic hedging to more purposeful alignment (Wenxin, 2021; Deb and Jiayue, 2024). The signing of basic agreements, such as the Logistics Exchange Memorandum of Agreement (LEMOA), the Communications

Compatibility and Security Agreement (COMCASA), and the Basic Exchange and Cooperation Agreement (BECA), has significantly improved India's military collaboration with American forces (Kathju, 2024). The Malabar exercise, which began as a bilateral naval drill between India and the United States, has grown in scale and strategic significance, increasing China's worry of being surrounded (Junuguru, 2025). Such exercises, according to Qian Jiayin (2023), not only militarise the Indo-Pacific region but also convey a desire to establish a de facto military alliance led by the United States.

Concurrently, India's participation in mini-lateral forums like the QUAD has expanded in terms of scope and depth. Although China first saw the QUAD as a "hollow" project (Xingchun, 2019), India's energetic involvement in joint naval manoeuvres, high-level discussions, and crucial technology partnerships has led Beijing to see the forum as a major instrument of a Western-led containment plan (Xuanzun, 2021). With India placed as the western pillar of a projected semicircular containment plan aimed at China, the QUAD is increasingly understood in Chinese discourse as an "Asian NATO" (Xingchun, 2018; Feng, 2024). According to Qian Feng, India's aggressive efforts to institutionalize the QUAD align with its overall policy of strengthening ties with the United States to counter China and increase its negotiating power in ongoing bilateral disputes (Global Times, 2020). India's symbolic backing for AUKUS, even though it is not an official member, fits with its strategic goals of naval modernization and power projection, strengthening its place in the larger anti-China alliance and portraying AUKUS as a stabilizing force in the Indo-Pacific (Samanta, 2021; Kaura, 2021; The Economic Times, 2021). This endorsement further validates China's threat perception. According to Chinese analysts, AUKUS may develop into a more all-encompassing alliance framework, perhaps dubbed "AUKUS Plus," with Japan and India as possible partners (Xue, 2023). A researcher from the renowned Beijing think tank Pangoal Institute points out that AUKUS "fills a gap" in military

cooperation programmes in the US Indo-Pacific Strategy, making up for a significant weakness of the Quad (Zhang, 2022). India's naval modernisation effort had strengthened this impression. Scholars and strategic analysts draw a direct correlation between India's renewed focus on SSNs and the precedent set by AUKUS, wherein Australia is acquiring nuclear submarine technology from the United Kingdom (Acton, 2021; Brewster, 2022). With two nuclear-powered ballistic missile submarines (SSBNs), "INS Arihant" and "INS Arighat", already in operation (Ramkumar and Panneerselvam, 2023), India is currently making a concerted effort to build nuclear-powered attack submarines (SSNs) with enhanced domestic capabilities (Honrada, 2024). Lu Xiang (2021) notes that the U.S. may extend nuclear-submarine aid to countries already in line with its strategic aims, including India.

This convergence is further evident in India's defense technology cooperation with the United States, which is exemplified by the "U.S.-India Initiative on Critical and Emerging Technology (iCET)" and the "TRUST roadmap" started in 2025. These systems expand Indo-U.S. strategic convergence into fields like Artificial Intelligence (AI), cybersecurity, semiconductors, and space—areas covered under AUKUS Pillar II agreements and central to the wider U.S.-China strategic competition. Chinese scholars such as Lin Minwang (2018) see iCET as a U.S. technique to "lock in" India over the long term by including it into Western technological ecosystems. Jiamei (2023) argue that these alignments support the same strategic encirclement logic that underpins China's perceptions of regional threats. Overall, there has been a shift in how China views India's strategic realignment, which is based on deeper relations with the United States. China sees India's aggressiveness in the maritime sector, its growing defense and technological convergence with Washington, and its active cooperation with the U.S. and allies as components of a broader containment strategy rather than as isolated incidents or swing powers.

Conclusion

This research examines how China frames India's role in the Indo-Pacific, claiming that China's strategic perspective of India has undergone a significant shift in its discourse. India, formerly regarded as a peripheral country with little interaction with significant blocs, is now increasingly portrayed as a key player in the U.S.-led containment strategy against China. Emphasizing the central of systemic pressures, power distribution, and alliance patterns in influencing state behaviour and threat perceptions, the structural logic of neorealism underlies this perceptual transformation not by accident but rather deeply rooted. The effects of this change are particularly important. First, it helps to exacerbate the regional security challenge by strengthening reciprocal threat perceptions and driving parallel military modernization and alliance-building, especially among India, China, and the United States. Second, Beijing's opinion of India as a strategic opponent could speed China's strengthening strategic collaboration with Pakistan and other nations against U.S. influence, therefore exacerbating already-existing tensions in South Asia. Third, China's diplomatic conduct in multilateral and regional forums, where it may try to subvert India's influence and strategic agility, will likely be informed by this reframing. Furthermore, the discursive shift in China's perception of India reveals how strategic narratives shape geopolitical realities. Viewing India as a major participant in U.S.-led containment, Chinese strategic thinking justifies aggressive countermeasures—from deterrent to hybrid competition spanning marine, technological, and diplomatic domains. The reshaping of India reflects a broader redefinition of the Indo-Pacific order in response to growing geopolitical rivalry. As India deepens its ties with the United States and China reacts to perceived encirclement, regional dynamics are likely to become more polarized. This emphasizes the need of more thorough research of

how strategic discourses create and institutionalize threat perceptions. This essay emphasizes the importance of conceptual and perceptual changes in propelling regional instability by concentrating on China's internal conversation rather than just material developments – an area that calls for more scholarly involvement as the Indo-Pacific enters an age of increasing strategic flux.

* Ayesha Khalid Chaudhry is a Senior Fellow with the SIGA South Asia Desk and a PhD candidate in Strategic Affairs at Deakin University, Australia

References

- Acton JM (2021) Carnegie Endowment For International Peace.
- Brewster D (2022) The Interpreter.
- Cohen DFS (2024) China's Strategic Thinking toward India, 2017-2020. *The Asan Forum*.
- Deb S and Jiayue L (2024) The Changing Dynamics of China's Threat Perception toward India
A Shift from Asymmetry to Symmetry? *Asia Policy* 19(4).
- Dobell WM (1964) Ramifications of the China-Pakistan Border Treaty. *Pacific Affairs* 37(3): 283-295.
- Feng Q (2024) Small gangs like Quad will never make a big wave. *Global Times*, 17 October 2024.
- Fernando S (2012) China's relations with the Indian Ocean region: Combining realist and constructivist perspectives. *Institute of Chinese Studies* 1-40.
- Garver J (2002) Asymmetrical Indian and Chinese threat perceptions. *Journal of Strategic Studies* 25(4): 109-134.
- Global Times (2020) India plays with fire spicing up G7 expansion. *Global Times*, 5 June 2020.
- Guihong Z (2019) 'Yi dai yi lu' chang yi yu yin tai zhan lue gou xiang de bi jiao fen xi" [Belt and Road Initiative vs. Indo-Pacific Strategy]. *Contemporary International Relations* 2: 33.
- Hailin Y (2014) "Bu duichen xuqiu dui zhong yin guanxi de yingxiang" [The Influence on Asymmetric Needs toward Sino- Indian Relations]. *World Economics and Politics* 1: 6-15.
- Hailin Y (2019) Strategic Thoughts on China's Addressing of the US's New Version of the "Indo-Pacific" Concept. *Indian Ocean Economic and Political Review* 5: 1-14.
- Hailin Y (2020) *China hopes to establish normal state relations with India, No need to worry about Indo-Pacific strategy*. Available at: https://fangtan.china.com.cn/2020-07/14/content_76270833.htm. (accessed 18 May).
- Honrada G (2024) *Project 75: India's new nuke subs aspire to outmatch China*. Available at: <https://asiatimes.com/2024/10/project-75-indias-new-nuke-subs-aspire-to-outmatch-china/#> (accessed 5 April).
- Indian Defense Research Wing (2025) *Declassified Insights: How Nehru's Policies Shaped India-China Relations in the 1950s*. Available at: <https://idrw.org/declassified-insights-how-nehru-policies-shaped-india-china-relations-in-the-1950s/> (accessed 18 May).
- Jiamei W (2023) US' attempt to pit India against China undermines global recovery. *Global Times*, 01 February 2023.
- Jiayin Q (2023) Quad collective maritime defense an illusion in the 21st century. *Global Times*, 10 August 2023.
- Jingjie Y (2014) Modi likely to be pragmatic toward China. *Global Times*, 14 May 2014.
- Junuguru S (2025) Review of the QUAD Role in India–China Relations. *East Asia*.
- Kathju J (2024) Despite new nuclear submarine, India still lags China in naval strength. *South China Morning Post*, 3 September 2024.
- Kaura V (2021) View: AUKUS is no Counter to Quad, both have common vision of Indo-Pacific region. *The Economic Times*, 25 September 2021.

- Li L and Jiang T (2023) From Conceptual Idea to Strategic Reality: 'Indo-Pacific Strategy' from the Perspective of Chinese Scholars. *Asian Perspective* 47(1): 101-119.
- Lindgren WY (2025) Assessing Alternative Alignments: China's Reception of the Quad, AUKUS, and IPEF. In: Elena Atanassova-Cornelis ea (ed) *Security Order and Strategic Alignment in Europe and the Asia-Pacific: Times of Global Power Shifts*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, pp.205-228.
- Liping X (2015) "Di yuan zheng zhi yu di yuan jing ji shuang zhong shi jiao xia de mei guo 'yin tai zhan lue'" [U.S. Indo-Pacific Strategy: Geopolitical and Geoeconomic Perspectives]. *Chinese Journal of American Studies* 29(2): 37.
- Madan T (2020) MANAGING CHINA: COMPETITIVE ENGAGEMENT, WITH INDIAN CHARACTERISTICS. *Global China*.
- Madan T (2024) US views of India-China ties and their impact on the US-India partnership. *GLOBAL INDIA PODCAST*. Washington D.C.: The Brookings Institution.
- Mehta S (2023) Impasse at the LAC: An Examination of the 2013, 2014, and 2015 Standoffs.
- Minwang L (2018) We can't just focus on the differences between China and India.
- Nisar RD (2023) Assessing India - United States Security Agreements: A Critical Analysis. *Vestnik RUDN International Relations* 23(3): 536-546.
- Park S (2017) Why India boycotted the Belt and Road Forum.
- Ramkumar KG and Panneerselvam P (2023) Indian Navy's Submarine Development Programme: A Critical Assessment. *Journal of Asian Security and International Affairs* 10(3): 395-416.
- Samanta PD (2021) ET Analysis: Aukus Powers up Five eyes' anti-China plan, boosts Quad. *The Economic Times*, 23 September 2021.
- Shicun W and Colombage J (2019) Indo-Pacific Strategy and China's Response. *National Institute for South China Sea Studies*. 1-13.
- Shirk S (2002) CHAPTER 6 CHINESE PERCEPTIONS OF INDIA: BRIEF COMMENTS. Reportno. Report Number], Date. Place Published]: Institution].
- Shisheng H (2018) "Te lang pu "yin tai zhanlue" gouxiang yu zhong yin hudong qianjing"[Trump's Indo-Pacific Strategy and prospect for India-China expectation]. Available at: https://www.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_2014796. (accessed 18 May).
- Singh A (2022a) Securing Sea Lines of Communications in Asia. Reportno. Report Number], Date. Place Published]: Institution].
- Singh AG (2022b) China's Evolving Strategic Discourse on India: From Doklam to Galwan and Beyond. Reportno. Report Number], Date. Place Published]: Institution].
- Singh S and Marwah R (2024) *India and ASEAN in the Indo Pacific: Pathways and Perils*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- The Economic Times (2021) After AUKUS, Russia sees a potential threat - and an opportunity to market its own submarines. *The Economic Times*, 25 September 2021.
- Times of India (2018) India's Foreign Policy has become vibrant, assertive: Chinese Think tank. *Times of India*, 31 January 2018.
- Verma R (2025) India's democratic political system, economic growth and domestic security challenges, and China's dismissiveness of India's great power ambitions. *Contemporary South Asia*. DOI: 10.1080/09584935.2025.2458278.
- Waltz KN (1990) REALIST THOUGHT AND NEOREALIST THEORY. *Journal of International Affairs* 44(1): 21-37.
- Wang VW-c (2011) "Chindia" or Rivalry? Rising China, Rising India, and Contending Perspectives on

India-China Relations. *Asian Perspective* 35: 437-469.

Wenxin X (2021) India's strategy is left in limbo as China-US tensions somewhat ease. *Global Times*, 26 October 2021.

Xiang L (2021) West would sacrifice rest of world for its own interests, AUKUS sets precedent. *Global Times*, 21 October 2021.

Xing B (2022) India a vulnerable member on fringe of Quad. *Global Times*, 23 May 2022.

Xingchun L (2018) Be wary of Quad threat to ASEAN unity. *Global Times*, 20 November 2018.

Xingchun L (2019) US-Japan-India-Australia alliance stillborn. *Global Times*, 18 March 2019.

Xinkai Z (2012) China's Indian Ocean Dilemma. *South Asian Studies*. 2.

Xuanzun L (2021) PLA holds far sea exercises amid multinational drills targeting China, 'shows capability, determination against provocation. *Global Times*, 26 August 2021.

Xue F (2023) AUKUS represents outdated political ideology, won't have extensive appeal. *Global Times*, 31 January 2023.

Yao B and Li M (2025) International Alliances: Chinese Views and Responses. In: Routledge (ed) *Security Order and Strategic Alignment in Europe and the Asia-Pacific: Times of Global Power Shifts*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, pp.175-204.

Zhang J (2022) China and AUKUS: Growing Tensions Ahead. (accessed 17 november 2022).

Zhendong P (2014) Beijing, New Delhi poised for closer ties. *China Daily*, 4 June 2014.

3. From Autonomy to Alignment: India's Strategic Turn to the United States in the China Era

*Ayesha Khalid Chaudhry**

This article analyses India's developing grand strategy and contends that New Delhi is experiencing a significant behavioural transition from conventional doctrines of non-alignment and strategic autonomy to a de facto strategic alignment with the United States. This move is primarily motivated by India's re-evaluation of China as its most significant security concern and the realization that Russia, now increasingly reliant on China, cannot safeguard India's security. Based on recent developments in defence, technology, and the Indo-Pacific region, particularly the 2025 Ten-Year Major Defence Partnership, the research indicates that India now considers ongoing integration with U.S. power crucial for addressing the challenge posed by China. India maintains hedging strategies and avoids formal alliances, while its trajectory indicates a systematic, asymmetric alignment with Washington.

India's foreign policy heritage has always been characterised by a reluctance to engage in formal alliances. Since the Cold War ideology of non-alignment and the post-1990s concept of strategic autonomy, New Delhi has endeavoured to optimise its capacity for independent action while evading enforceable obligations (Mishra 2023). That self-perception persists rhetorically. However, the institutional conditions that formerly facilitated it have undergone profound changes. This essay contends that India is experiencing a behavioural transition from strategic autonomy to de facto strategic alignment with the U.S., primarily influenced by a re-evaluation of China as the most significant challenge India has encountered since independence. The

2025 India–US Ten-Year Major Defence Partnership (2025), established amid American criticism about India's relations with Russia and tariffs on Indian exports, represents a crucial turning point. It indicates that India's leadership now perceives enduring security and technology collaboration with Washington as essential for addressing the challenge posed by China, even at the expense of traditional non-alignment ideologies. The study is grounded in known literature that examines India's transition from non-alignment to strategic autonomy and multi-alignment (Pant and Super 2015; Raghavan 2017; Pant 2017; Jaishankar 2020; Smith 2020; Tellis 2021; Majumdar 2024). This analysis posits that India's conduct since about 2020 can no longer be sufficiently characterised as equidistant hedging among big powers. Although India maintains the rhetoric of autonomy, its decisions regarding defence, intelligence, technology, and Indo-Pacific security demonstrate a structural alignment with the U.S. that is unparalleled by any other partnership. This signifies the most significant transformation in Indian grand strategy since the 1971 alignment with the Soviet Union.

India's shifting policy trajectory

Throughout the majority of its post-colonial history, India's grand strategy has been structured around autonomy in a world initially dominated by two superpowers and subsequently by a singular hegemon. Throughout the Cold War, non-alignment served as both an identity and a strategy. Under Jawaharlal Nehru's leadership, India played a pivotal role in establishing and guiding the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), positioning itself as a representative of the decolonizing Global South (Harshe 1990). This position allowed India to obtain development aid, diplomatic flexibility, and restricted security assurances from both Washington and Moscow without formal obligations (Smith 2012; Pant and Super 2015). This stance was not unchangeable. The 1971 Indo-Soviet Treaty, established as India faced a Pakistan supported by

the US and China, signified a pragmatic shift. Despite being officially termed cooperation, it constituted a restricted security alignment in return for armaments, United Nations support, and geopolitical protection (Rajan 1972).

The dissolution of the Soviet Union necessitated a reassessment. India lost its primary great-power ally at the moment it faced a domestic economic crisis and a US-led unipolar world. Since the 1990s, Indian politicians have embraced the term 'strategic autonomy', acknowledging that the doctrinal inflexibility of non-alignment no longer aligns with global reality (Dolbaia, Banerjee, and Southfield 2025). Strategic autonomy emphasises the prevention of external limitations on India's nuclear, defence, and foreign policy rather than maintaining equidistance (Smith 2020). This revised strategy coincided with strengthened relations with Washington, culminating in the 2005 defence framework and the 2005–08 civil nuclear agreement (Nautiyal 2008). Simultaneously, India maintained its historical connections with Russia and engaged in organizations such as BRICS to enhance its position among non-Western nations (Oak 2025).

Under Prime Minister Narendra Modi, autonomy was redefined as multi-alignment. Jaishankar (2020) delineated India's objective as concurrently engaging the U.S., controlling China, fostering relations with Europe, comforting Russia, and collaborating with Japan. The objective was to expand India's strategic alternatives rather than completely eschew partnerships. This strategy resulted in a multifaceted profile: India established itself as a leader of the Global South via BRICS, while simultaneously emerging as a key member of the QUAD perceived as an Indo-Pacific framework to counterbalance China. This multi-alignment technique seemed durable for around two decades. It enabled India to mitigate shocks and gain time to strengthen its economic and military strengths. The intensifying US–China rivalry, Russia's growing reliance on Beijing, and China's more aggressive stance towards India have constrained the scope for hedging (Tellis 2021; Kaura 2025; Lal 2025).

China's rise and the reconfiguration of India's threat perception

The primary catalyst for India's strategic shift has been a fundamental shift in its threat perception. For decades, Pakistan has played a vital role in India's security considerations. China was identified as a possible foe, particularly following 1962. Although for the majority of the post-Cold War era, it remained a relatively remote apprehension. This hierarchy has now inverted (Raghavan 2017). A survey conducted in late 2022 revealed that 43 percent of Indians regarded China as India's 'greatest military threat,' whereas only 13 percent recognised Pakistan as such (Kugelman 2023). Recent U.S. intelligence evaluations indicate that Indian policymakers currently perceive China as the 'primary security threat,' but Pakistan is viewed as a 'secondary' challenge. This signifies a pivotal change in long-term strategy (Peri 2025).

A multitude of developments underpins this rearrangement. Firstly, the Line of Actual Control (LAC) has experienced unparalleled militarization. The Doklam standoff in 2017 and the fatal confrontations in 2020–21 indicated a collapse of border management protocols. Recent talks indicate both the resilience and the constraints of border control as a stabilising framework. The June 2024 WMCC meeting reiterated its commitment to collaboration but did not achieve any breakthroughs. These approaches mitigate tactical hazards but fail to confront the strategic mistrust that underlies the rivalry. As border negotiations address the symptom, not the underlying issue (Sharma 2025). Secondly, China's influence in the Indian Ocean Region has increased. The access arrangements and infrastructure under BRI have enabled increased PLA Navy deployments, hence raising India's fear of encirclement (Scott 2025). Thirdly, China's technology supremacy has generated novel types of leverage. Its significance in telecommunications, electronics, rare earths, and other vital industries compelled India to diversify suppliers, limit Chinese investment, and prohibit some applications post-

2020 (Pandey 2025). Fourth and the most significant is China's increasing alignment with Pakistan, which has resulted in a collaborative two-front challenge (Singh 2021). China's enduring backing for Pakistan's defense modernization, with the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and substantial arms sales, has enhanced Pakistan's capabilities. From 2019 to 2023, China accounted for around 81 percent of Pakistan's total arms imports, integrating Islamabad significantly into Beijing's defence framework (Ians 2025). The increasing presence of the PLA Navy in the Arabian Sea and the Pakistan buying Chinese submarines have expanded this dynamic into the maritime sphere (Pandita 2023; Naqvi 2024). The May 2025 India-Pakistan conflict significantly revealed the operational capabilities of the China-Pakistan alliance and exacerbated Delhi's enduring concerns of a two-front threat. The US Economic and Security Review Commission's report to Congress (2025) characterised the conflict as a 'real-world field experiment' for Chinese weaponry, highlighting Pakistan's significant dependence on Chinese platforms and sensors, as well as its 'reported utilisation of Chinese intelligence,' which includes real-time data on Indian troop locations. Pakistan asserted that it had destroyed five Indian aircraft, then increasing the count to seven; US President Donald Trump publicly declared that 'essentially eight' had been shot down, including the West's most advanced aircrafts, Rafale (Dawn 2025). For experts, these losses were not merely tactical setbacks it adds a layer of geopolitical messaging. It indicates the increasing technological superiority of a China-backed Pakistan and revealed the constraints of India's capacity to independently address a coordinated two-front threat. Thus, these tendencies collectively represent the most constricted and perilous strategic landscape India has faced since 1947. The conventional paradigm of balancing Pakistan, controlling China, and leveraging great-power rivalry while remaining outside alliances has grown progressively unviable.

This modified threat environment has necessitated a reassessment of strategic autonomy.

Historically, autonomy was frequently associated with a detachment from the U.S., motivated by apprehensions regarding influence or limitations on India's nuclear and Kashmir policies. That perspective has diminished. There is a widespread elite agreement that classical non-alignment has beyond its usefulness (Smith 2020). Whereas, in the face of significant external threats, selective alignment can bolster rather than undermine autonomy by enhancing a state's ability to dissuade more powerful rivals (Tellis 2021; Dolbaia, Banerjee, and Southfield 2025; Kaura 2025). Autonomy is now characterised as the capacity to operate freely within a network of alliances, including those essential for counterbalancing China (Jaishankar 2020). This reconceptualization reinforces India's readiness to engage in long-term, institutionalised security agreements with the U.S., notwithstanding divergences about trade, sanctions, and Russia.

The India-US partnership: from cooperation to embedded alignment

Over the past two decades, India-US relations have expanded across military, intelligence, technological, and industrial sectors. Since the mid-2010s, the partnership has experienced a qualitative transition. The 2005 New Framework for U.S-India Defence Relationship and the civil nuclear agreement alleviated Cold War animosities. In 2016, the U.S. classified India as a 'Major Defence Partner,' indicating a commitment to provide India with access to advanced defence technologies (Garge 2025). From 2016 to 2020, the two parties finalised essential agreements such as LEMOA, COMCASA, and BECA that facilitated reciprocal logistics, secure communications, and geospatial intelligence exchange. These agreements provide the foundational framework for collaborative operations and interoperability (Pant 2017; Nisar 2023). Subsequent operational collaboration intensifies. The Malabar exercises now incorporate intricate anti-submarine warfare, carrier operations, and maritime surveillance (Garge 2025). In the 2020 LAC crisis, Washington allegedly supplied India with real-time

satellite intelligence regarding Chinese troop movements. This demonstrates an unparalleled degree of tangible assistance (Smith 2020).

The defence trade has experienced a significant increase. India has procured P-8I maritime patrol aircraft, C-17 and C-130J transport aircraft, Apache and Chinook helicopters, M777 howitzers, and sophisticated drones. The 2023 accord for the co-production of GE F414 jet engines represented a notable transfer of technology (Krishnan 2023). A 2024 agreement for 31 MQ-9B drones enhanced collaboration. The cooperation is increasingly grounded in high-technology collaboration, in addition to arms sales. The Initiative on Critical and Emerging Technologies (iCET) connects endeavours in semiconductors, quantum computing, artificial intelligence, space, and telecommunications. Joint comments underscore the establishment of 'trusted and resilient' supply chains to diminish reliance on China (Chaudhuri and Bhandari 2024). INDUS-X, inaugurated in 2023, links Indian and American defence start-ups and industrial ecosystems. By connecting India's iDEX with the US Defence Innovation Unit, INDUS-X transforms the partnership into one of co-development and co-production (Bhatia and Bhandari 2023).

The relationship is integrated into a wider Indo-Pacific alignment. Both nations express analogous aspirations for a free and open Indo-Pacific; collaborate on maritime domain awareness; and synchronise their stances within the Quad regarding infrastructure, supply networks, and regional security. U.S. strategic documents characterise India as a 'linchpin' of the Indo-Pacific strategy (Jaiem 2023; Seth 2024). The 2025 Framework for the US-India Major Defence Partnership signed on 31 October 2025, consolidates these transformations. Extending until 2035, it enhances collaboration across all domains (land, sea, air, cyber, and space). The deal accelerates India's defence modernisation and fortifies its industrial foundation in sectors such as aircraft engines, drones, maritime systems, and secure communications through co-development, technology transfer, and enhanced intelligence

sharing (U.S. Department of War 2025). This effectively integrates India into the Indo-Pacific security framework. It complicates China's ability to launch attacks against New Delhi, facilitates collaboration between U.S. and Indian troops, and enhances India's position as a regional security supplier, reducing its dependence on outdated Russian capabilities (Dutta 2025).

However, the timing of this agreement is very significant. It was agreed following a period of considerable mutual tension. The Trump administration enacted taxes on Indian exports, publicly encouraged New Delhi to diminish its defence and energy relations with Russia, and proposed very punishing penalties on purchasers of Russian oil (Croucher 2025; Kugelman 2025). This pressure indicated a bigger signal: the period of equal-distance hedging by India was no longer viable. However, in spite of this pressure, India decided against diminishing or weakening defence cooperation with the U.S., rather, it chose to enhance and formalise it. This choice is challenging to align with the interpretation of strategic autonomy as chiefly focused on countering U.S. influence. It reflects a pragmatic acknowledgement in Delhi that Russia, now increasingly reliant on China, cannot safeguard India's security. In contrast, Washington is essential for addressing the China challenge and counterbalancing the China-Pakistan alliance.

Russia as legacy partner in managed decline

Russia remains deeply embedded in India's defence and energy architecture, yet its strategic utility is steadily contracting. The majority of India's primary military equipment, including Su-30MKI jets, T-72 and T-90 tanks, Kilo-class submarines, and various artillery systems, is sourced from Russia. Collaborative initiatives like BrahMos continue to hold significance (Raghavan 2017; Dolbaia, Banerjee, and Southfield 2025). India's transition to rupee-rouble transactions and third-party payment mechanisms post-2022 was a calculated strategy to maintain this connection in the face of Western

financial penalties (Financial Express 2024). However, these modifications can no longer obscure the more significant issue: Russia is increasingly perceived as an unreliable security partner.

Three developments elucidate this point. The initial aspect is political. The increasing alignment of Moscow with Beijing following the 2022 'no-limits' proclamation raises significant concerns regarding Russia's potential actions in a future India-China dispute. For India, a Russia aligned with China can no longer fulfil its previous stabilising role. The second issue is to capability. The Ukraine conflict has severely strained Russia's defence sector. Delivery delays, a paucity of spare parts, and the inability to provide the third nuclear-powered submarine that India anticipated leasing indicate a significant reduction in Russia's offerings. Western vendors and India's local industries are currently addressing these gaps (Dawn 2025). The third pressure originates from the increased Western pressure. Subsequent to 2022, cheap Russian crude positioned Russia as India's primary supplier, with 35–40 percent of total imports. This pattern promptly elicited pressure from the U.S. On 27 August 2025, Washington put a 25 percent tariff on India's acquisitions of Russian oil, and President Trump explicitly pledged to eliminate these imports entirely. By late 2025, escalating sanctions from the US, EU, and UK, increased bank surveillance, and the risk of secondary measures compelled Indian refiners to retract. State-owned enterprises ceased new acquisitions from Russia, while US crude oil constituted 10.7 percent of India's imports, its largest proportion since 2021 (Verma 2025; Sahai 2025). The result is unmistakable. Dependence on defence, vulnerability to energy fluctuations, and geopolitical instability have combined to position Russia as a legacy partner rather than a prospective cornerstone. These factors collectively propel India towards increased alignment with Washington.

Beyond dual alignment: hierarchy and structural tilt

Contemporary scholarship often characterises India's external conduct as a measured type of dual alignment; nonetheless, the data increasingly suggests a hierarchical structure rather than a symmetrical one. New Delhi intentionally maintains a balance between the U.S. and Russia to safeguard its strategic autonomy in a progressively polarised international landscape (Kaura 2025). The decline of U.S. credibility during the Trump administration prompted India to more overtly hedge by engaging in China-affiliated organisations like as BRICS and the SCO (Oak 2025). However, India's involvement with the SCO indicated uneasiness: India was overly cautious to face China directly and too ambiguous to completely meet U.S. expectations. Consequently, it became economically restricted by Washington, strategically confronted by Beijing, and politically entwined with Moscow, a situation that made India prominent although not definitive inside the evolving U.S.-China strategic framework (Chaudhry 2025). Recent developments suggest a transition from ambiguity to quiet definitive alignment choices. As established above, India's commitment to the 2025 Ten-Year Defence Partnership, despite tariffs, political tensions, and scrutiny regarding its ties to Russia, indicates that New Delhi now perceives enduring security collaboration with Washington as essential for addressing China's ascendance, rather than an optional enhancement. This nascent hierarchy is bolstered by empirical evidence. No other relationship parallels the U.S. in the profundity of defence planning, technological integration, real-time intelligence cooperation, or maritime alignment in the Indo-Pacific region. It seems that India has now realized that its dedication to multi-alignment may disguise the tangible advantages of a closer strategic cooperation with Washington. The defence framework confirms that understanding. India opted to enhance collaboration with the U.S. at a time of maximal political cost, signifying a developing consensus that, in the context of the China age, a

more profound albeit non-treaty alignment with Washington is strategically essential.

Conclusion

India's foreign policy is frequently described as one of continuity: non-alignment evolves into strategic autonomy, which then transforms into multi-alignment. However, China's ascendance has shown the constraints of this narrative. Survey data and official evaluations align: China has supplanted Pakistan as India's foremost danger. The collusion between China and Pakistan, tensions at LAC, and China's expanding influence in the Indian Ocean have led Indian policymakers to conclude that unilateral balancing is impractical. India has significantly enhanced its security, defence industrial, and technical integration with the U.S. to an unparalleled extent. Foundational military agreements, significant arms acquisitions, iCET, INDUS-X, and the 2025 ten-year framework collectively signify a qualitative alignment that cannot be entirely elucidated by autonomy, hedging, or multi-alignment.

Simultaneously, India has preserved some of its traditional methodology. It persistently evades treaty obligations, rejects the designation of 'ally', sustains significant defence and energy relations with Russia, and engages in non-Western forums in conjunction with China. In this context, alignment is taking place according to Indian parameters. Nevertheless, it constitutes alignment. The U.S. currently has a uniquely significant role in India's strategic planning, especially with the management of China, and no other relationship demonstrates similar depth or institutionalisation. The implication is that strategic autonomy is being practically redefined. Instead of indicating a separation from power centres, it now signifies the preservation of national autonomy within an asymmetric yet essential security alliance with the U.S. India aligns with Washington chiefly on matters concerning China, while maintaining flexibility in other areas. The extent to which this alignment intensifies or faces new limitations will be contingent

upon China's actions, Washington's dedication to the Indo-Pacific, and India's internal developments. The period during which India could convincingly maintain a neutral stance between major nations has concluded. In a global framework increasingly defined by US-China competition, India has transitioned carefully yet resolutely from autonomy to alignment.

** Ayesha Khalid Chaudhry is a Senior Fellow with the SIGA South Asia Desk and a PhD candidate in Strategic Affairs at Deakin University, Australia*

References

- Bhatia, Rahul, and Konark Bhandari. 2023. "INDUS-X: Charting the Way Ahead for India-U.S. Defense Industrial Cooperation." [Think Tank]. Carnegie Endowment For International Peace. Last Modified 25 Aug 2023. Accessed 22 Nov. <https://carnegieendowment.org/posts/2023/08/indus-x-charting-the-way-ahead-for-india-us-defense-industrial-cooperation?lang=en>.
- Chaudhry, Ayesha Khalid. 2025. "India at the SCO Summit: Trapped in the Strategic Triangle." [Think Tank]. Swiss Institute for Global Affairs (SIGA). Last Modified 8 Sep 2025. Accessed 22 Nov. <https://www.globalaffairs.ch/2025/09/08/india-at-the-sco-summit-trapped-in-the-strategic-triangle/>.
- Chaudhuri, Rudra, and Konark Bhandari. 2024. "The U.S.–India Initiative on Critical and Emerging Technology (iCET) from 2022 to 2025: Assessment, Learnings, and the Way Forward." Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. Last Modified 23 Oct 2024. Accessed 22 Nov. <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/10/the-us-india-initiative-on-critical-and-emerging-technology-icet-from-2022->

- to-2025-assessment-learnings-and-the-way-forward?lang=en.
- Croucher, Shane. 2025. "Trump Issues Fresh Warning to India After Modi, Xi, Putin Meeting." *News Week*. Last Modified 1 September 2025. Accessed 4 September. <https://www.newsweek.com/trump-india-tariffs-trade-russia-oil-2122670>.
- Dawn. 2025. "US report credits Chinese weapons for Pakistan's success in May war." *Dawn* 20 Nov 2025, 2025, Report. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1956177>.
- Dolbaia, Tina, Vasabjit Banerjee, and Amanda Southfield. 22 Aug 2025 2025. *Guns and Oil: Continuity and Change in Russia-India Relations*. Center For Strategic & International Studies (CSIS) (Washington, D.C.: Center For Strategic & International Studies). <https://www.csis.org/analysis/guns-and-oil-continuity-and-change-russia-india-relations>.
- Dutta, Amrita Nayak. 2025. "India, US seal 10-yr defence partnership framework, signal strategic convergence." *The Indian Express*, 1 Nov 2025, 2025. <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/india-us-sign-new-10-year-defence-partnership-framework-amid-tariff-tensions-10338454/>.
- Financial Express. 2024. "India and Russia Seek to Bypass Dollar with Rupee-Ruble Trade, Tackle Financial Barriers." *Financial Express*, 29 Oct 2024, 2024. <https://www.financialexpress.com/policy/economy/india-and-russia-seek-to-bypass-dollar-with-rupee-ruble-trade-tackle-financial-barriers/3651755/>.
- Garge, Ramanand. 2025. "India as the anchor (stabilising force) of the Indo-Pacific in the era of roaring forties." *Australian Journal of Maritime & Ocean Affairs*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18366503.2025.2480950>.
- Harshe, Rajen. 1990. "India's Non-Alignment: An Attempt at Conceptual Reconstruction." *Economic and Political Weekly* 25 (7/8): 399–405. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4395968>.
- Jaishankar, S. 2020. *The India Way: Strategies for an Uncertain World*. India: Harper Collins Publishers India.
- Jiamei, Wang. 2023. "US' attempt to pit India against China undermines global recovery." *Global Times*, 01 February 2023, 2023. https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202302/1284642.shtml?utm_source=chatgpt.com.
- Kaura, Vinay. 2025. "India's Diplomacy of Dual Alignments: Russia and the US." [Guest Commentary]. Royal United Services Institute (RUSI). Last Modified 21 Jul 2025. Accessed 16 Nov. <https://www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/indias-diplomacy-dual-alignments-russia-and-us>.
- Krishnan, Kavya R. 2023. "Legal Aspects of General Electric and Hindustan Aeronautics Limited F414 Engines Deal." [Think Tank]. Vivekananda International Foundation. Last Modified 11 Dec 2023. Accessed 22 Nov <https://www.vifindia.org/article/2023/december/12/Legal-Aspects-of-General-Electric-and-Hindustan-Aeronautics>.
- Kugelman, Michael. 2023. "China Has Become India's Greatest Threat." *Foreign Policy*, 19 Jan 2023.
- . 2025. "The U.S.-India Trade Spat Boils Over." *Foreign Policy*, 6 Aug 2025, 2025. <https://foreignpolicy.com/2025/08/06/india->

trump-russia-oil-modi-united-states-tariff-trade/.

alignment-in-multipolar-competition-india-and-russias-strategic-pull-toward-china/.

- Lal, Anil Kumar. 2025. "India's strategic autonomy in a G2 era: The urgent need for a national security strategy." *Times of India*, 12 Nov 2025, 2025, Opinion. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/akshakindia/indias-strategic-autonomy-in-a-g2-era-the-urgent-need-for-a-national-security-strategy/>.
- Majumdar, Anindya Jyoti. 2024. "The Evolving Trajectory of India's Foreign Policy: Non-alignment to Multi-Engagement and Beyond." In *75 Years of India's Foreign Policy: Bilateral, Conventional and Emerging Trends*, edited by Partha Pratim Basu and Tanwir Arshed, 63–81. Singapore: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Mishra, Rahul. 2023. "From non-alignment to multi-alignment: assessing India's foreign policy shift." *The Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs and Policy Studies* 112 (1): 43–56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00358533.2023.2165367>.
- Nautiyal, Annpurna. 2008. The Indo-US nuclear deal: what is there?
- Nisar, Rana Danish. 2023. "Assessing India - United States Security Agreements: A Critical Analysis." *Vestnik RUDN International Relations* 23 (3): 536–546. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.22363/2313-0660-2023-23-3-536-546>. <https://journals.rudn.ru/international-relations/article/view/36156>.
- Oak, Mandar. 2025. "Rational Alignment in Multipolar Competition: India and Russia's Strategic Pull Toward China." *The Diplomat*, 9 Sep 2–025, 2025. <https://thediplomat.com/2025/09/rational->
- Pandey, Rahul. 2025. "China's Rare Earth Leverage Is the Frontline of 21st Century Geopolitics." *The Diplomat*, 10 Oct 2025, 2025. <https://thediplomat.com/2025/10/chinas-rare-earth-leverage-is-the-frontline-of-21st-century-geopolitics/>.
- Pant, Harsh V. 2017. "The End of Non-Alignment?" *Orbis FPRI's Journal of World Affairs* 61 (4): 527–540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orbis.2017.08.004>.
- Pant, Harsh V., and Julie M. Super. 2015. "India's 'non-alignment' conundrum: a twentieth-century policy in a changing world." *International Affairs* 91 (4): 747–764. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.12336>.
- Peri, Dinakar. 2025. "India views China as the 'primary adversary', Pakistan more an 'ancillary' security problem, says U.S. report." *The Hindu*, 26 May 2025, 2025. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/india-views-china-as-primary-adversary-pakistan-more-ancillary-security-problem-us-report/article69618056.ece>.
- Raghavan, P.S. 2017. "The Making of India's Foreign Policy: From Non-Alignment to Multi Alignment." *Indian Foreign Affairs Journal* 12 (4): 326–341. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/45342011>.
- Rajan, M.S. 1972. "The Indo-Soviet Treaty and India's non-alignment policy." *Australian Outlook* 26 (2): 204–215. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/10357717208444440>.

- Sahai, Vrinda. 2025. "The Impact of U.S. Sanctions and Tariffs on India's Russian Oil Imports." Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. Last Modified 20 Nov 2025. Accessed 26 Nov. <https://carnegieendowment.org/posts/2025/11/the-impact-of-us-sanctions-and-tariffs-on-indias-russian-oil-imports?lang=en>.
- Scott, David. 2025. "China-India Competition in the Indian Ocean." China-India Brief #256. Centre on Asia and Globalisation
- Lee Kuan Yew School of Public Policy. Last Modified 30 Jun 2025. Accessed 18 Sep. <https://lkyspp.nus.edu.sg/cag/publications/center-publications/publication-article/detail/china-india-competition-in-the-indian-ocean>.
- Seth, Nayan. 2024. "The Quad's Growing Role in the Indian Ocean: One Step at a Time." Asia Matters for America. Last Modified 7 October 2024. Accessed 20 August <https://asiamattersforamerica.org/articles/the-quads-growing-role-in-the-indian-ocean-one-step-at-a-time>.
- Sharma, Vidushi. 2025. "From Standoff to Structured Stability: The 34th WMCC and the Quiet Diplomacy of Border Management." NICE. Last Modified 26 Jul 2025. Accessed 21 Nov. <https://niice.org.np/archives/11503>.
- Smith, Jeff M. 2012. "A Forgotten War in the Himalayas." Yale Global. Last Modified 14 Sep 2012. <https://archive-yaleglobal.yale.edu/content/forgotten-war-himalayas>.
- . 2020. "Strategic Autonomy and U.S.-Indian Relations." War on the Rocks. Last Modified 6 Nov 2020. Accessed 16 Nov <https://warontherocks.com/2020/11/strategic-autonomy-and-u-s-indian-relations/>.
- Tellis, Ashley J. 2021. Non-Allied Forever: India's Grand Strategy According to Subrahmanyam Jaishankar. 1–8.
- U.S.-China Economic and Security Review Commission. Nov 2025 2025. *2025 Report to Congress* U.S. Congress (Washington, D.C.). https://www.uscc.gov/sites/default/files/2025-11/2025_Annual_Report_to_Congress.pdf.
- U.S. Department of War. 2025. FACT SHEET: Framework for the U.S. India Major Defense Partnership. edited by U.S. Department of War. Washington, D.C.
- Verma, Nidhi. 2025. "India's Russian oil binge to end in December as sanctions bite, sources say." *Reuters*, 25 Nov 2025, 2025. <https://www.reuters.com/business/energy/indias-russian-oil-binge-end-december-sanctions-bite-sources-say-2025-11-25/>.

4. India, South Asia, and Their Regional Organisations

*Dr. Remo Reginold**

South Asia is difficult to define as a coherent geographic, political, ethno-cultural, or historical unit. There are no universally accepted criteria for inclusion or exclusion, nor are there shared identity markers that command broad consensus or claim general validity. For some analysts, South Asia is geographically delineated by the Himalayan arc in the north, the Hindukush to the west, the Chin Hills to the east, and the vast expanse of the Indian Ocean to the south. Others emphasise the civilisational dimension of a Hindu-driven *Akhand Bharat*, while yet others see the legacy of the *British East India Company* and the shared colonial experience as a more durable point of reference.

In practice, the conceptual realm of “South Asia” is a multilayered construct. Any attempt to define it precisely is ultimately doomed to fall short. Rational, categorical frameworks fail to capture the region’s complexity; as such, South Asia cannot meaningfully be approached as a unified strategic entity or block³⁴.

This ambiguity also affects India, the region’s dominant actor, which struggles to define its strategic posture in such a heterogeneous environment. The following reflections offer snapshots of a region at the centre of geopolitical flux, seeking to redefine itself. A dominant India operating in a perpetual rivalry with Pakistan, and navigating historically intricate relationships with Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh, forms the core political reality. Added to this, South Asia must increasingly be viewed against the backdrop of China’s rising ambitions. It is therefore no coincidence that the United States, several Western countries, and the European Union are expressing strategic interest in the region, aware that

competition over trade routes, access to resources, and narrative influence will shape South Asia’s future.

The focus of this analysis is on South Asia’s regional and intergovernmental organisations, and India’s strategic behaviour within them. New Delhi’s grand strategy documents and white papers may project diplomatic ambition³⁵, but India’s actions and positioning within the *South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation* (SAARC), the *Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation* (BIMSTEC), or the *Indian Ocean Rim Association* (IORA) provide a more revealing window into India’s strategic culture.

India’s Regional Policy

With roughly 73% of the region’s landmass, 80% of its GDP, 77% of its population, and the world’s fourth-largest military, India is unequivocally South Asia’s regional hegemon. In recent years, this dominance has become increasingly visible in New Delhi’s regional diplomacy. Under Prime Minister Narendra Modi, the *Neighbourhood First Policy* has placed renewed emphasis on cultivating relations with neighbouring states, focusing on infrastructure cooperation, trade, cultural diplomacy, and development assistance. The aim is to foster regional stability, build mutual trust, and – implicitly – affirm India’s natural leadership role.

This recalibration is in part a response to the intensification of geopolitical competition. From India’s perspective, China has, since 2013, been systematically constructing a network to reshape the Global South, with Beijing as its strategic centre. Through the *Belt and Road Initiative* (BRI) and the

³⁴ It emerged from a region “characterised by political disharmony and strategic schism”, unlike other regionalism projects where “...politico-strategic harmony [forms] a vital factor in stimulating and facilitating close and extensive cooperative linkages, including

those in security and strategic areas” (K. Yome and T.S. Maini (2017): *India’s Evolving Approach to Regionalism: SAARC and Beyond*, Vol 2, Issue 3, 147-165).

³⁵ Vgl. *Neighbourhood First Policy* (NFP), *Look East Policy* (LEP), *Act East Policy* (AEP), *Look North Policy* (LNP), *Connect Central Asia Policy* (CCAP) sowie *Indo-Pacific Vision* (IPV)

String of Pearls Strategy, China has expanded its influence in South Asia and the Indian Ocean region via infrastructure, trade routes, and military access – Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, and Myanmar being illustrative cases. India's Neighbourhood First Policy and the *Necklace of Diamonds Strategy* can in part be read as countermeasures.

Overlaying these dynamics is a civilizational aspiration promoted by segments of India's political leadership: the idea of *Akhand Bharat* – a vision of an undivided India encompassing not only today's India, but also Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, the Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Tibet. This notion, rooted in Hindu civilisational nationalism and espoused by proponents of *Hindutva*, represents an ideological undertone within India's contemporary foreign policy discourse.

Historically, India pursued a different course. Following independence and amid the Cold War, New Delhi sought a non-aligned position, positioning itself under Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru as a voice for Asia and the Global South, including aspirations for a permanent seat on the UN Security Council. Today, that ideational approach has given way to a strategic pragmatism – refined rhetorically and symbolically by External Affairs Minister S. Jaishankar and national security strategist Ajit Doval. In this framework, India is able to maintain situational relationships where mutual interests dictate – simultaneously cooperating with archrival China, engaging Vladimir Putin's Russia, and enjoying courtship from both the EU and the United States. India is thus far more than a "swing state"; it cultivates stable partnerships and strategic alliances across competing blocs.

Given its favourable geopolitical position and regional pre-eminence, India sees little incentive to engage in bilateral or minilateral arrangements that might constrain its autonomy. Efforts toward regionalism, security cooperation, or economic

integration yield limited returns for New Delhi. Heterogeneity in South Asia prevents the emergence of a region built around India as its nucleus. In essence, there is no "South Asia with India at its centre".

India's ongoing rivalry with Pakistan since the 1947 Partition, its complicated role in Sri Lanka's civil war, and its complex ties with Myanmar all present security concerns. These tensions limit India's ability to fully assert its dominance. The India-Pakistan rivalry is the core of South Asia's security complex; shifts in their relationship reverberate across the region. The nuclear dimension further impedes stable regional cooperation, contributing to persistent strategic volatility. Proxy conflicts and contested borders reinforce this dynamic.

Regional and intergovernmental organisations – intended to foster sovereignty, exchange, and trust – struggle to gain traction in this environment. Instead of strategic regionalism, South Asia often manifests what scholars describe as "pseudo-regionalism", where formal structures exist but substantive integration remains minimal³⁶. Economic interactions alone are insufficient to create a coherent geopolitical space.

Regional Organisations in South Asia

South Asia hosts several intergovernmental bodies aimed at fostering cooperation, inclusion, development, military diplomacy, and cultural exchange. These institutions aspire to strengthen economic stability, identity-building, and national sovereignty. India participates in all major organisations, demonstrating at least a formal commitment.

Below is a chronological overview of the most established sub-regional and regional organizations, including their respective purposes, objectives, and member states.

³⁶ K. Yome and T.S. Maini (2017): India's Evolving Approach to Regionalism: SAARC and Beyond, Vol 2, Issue 3, 147-165.

Organisation Group	Year	Members	Nature / Purpose
SAARC (South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation)	1985	Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka	Promote economic, social, cultural cooperation; South Asian regional integration.
BIMSTEC (Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation)	1997	Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Thailand	Connect South & Southeast Asia; cooperation in trade, transport, disaster management, tech.
IORA (Indian Ocean Rim Association)	1997	23 Indian Ocean littoral states (incl. India, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Australia, Indonesia, South Africa, etc.)	Maritime cooperation, blue economy, disaster response, trade facilitation.
BCIM (Bangladesh-China-India-Myanmar Forum / Economic Corridor)	1999	Bangladesh, China, India, Myanmar	Promote trade, connectivity, economic corridor linking South Asia and China.
MGC (Mekong-Ganga Cooperation)	2000	India, Thailand, Myanmar, Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam	Cultural cooperation, tourism, education, connectivity along Ganga-Mekong civilisation links.
BBIN (Bangladesh-Bhutan-India-Nepal Initiative)	2015	Bangladesh, Bhutan*, India, Nepal>(*Bhutan hasn't ratified MVA but stays in discussion.)	Sub-regional connectivity; Motor Vehicles Agreement for transport and trade facilitation.

Table 1: India's Membership in South Asian Regional Organizations

In general, regional organizations in the Global South tend to be characterised as inclusive, non-hierarchical, and committed to upholding state sovereignty. In South Asia, however, India's overwhelming size complicates this narrative. Fears of hegemonic expansion persist, despite India's capacity to play an integrative or mediating role. New Delhi, on the other hand, is also cautious: deeper integration would require concessions that might bolster neighbouring states – or embolden Pakistan. India's present approach marks a departure from the *Gujral Doctrine* and *Manmohan Singh Doctrine*'s more accommodating regional policies of the 1990s,

which favoured reconciliation and trust-building. China's assertiveness shifted India away from that strategy.

Economic integration remains the central objective of South Asia's regional organisations. While such cooperation is expected to produce spillover effects in political stability and security, India's economic rise –founded partly on weak neighbours – creates disincentives for deeper integration. India's market liberalization in the 1990s and the resulting economic rise were based on weak neighbors. For this reason, New Delhi has a strategic interest in keeping the region unstable. A stable and content region could also benefit the other states and, from India's perspective, does not seem desirable³⁷. Hence, New Delhi benefits from a region that remains strategically unbalanced.

None of these regional organizations discuss the political role or strategic orientation of their members. SAARC exists not because of shared strategic interests, but out of the understanding that the member states somehow form a geographic region³⁸. India mainly participates to symbolically demonstrate internationally that it has a position in South Asia and to network and actively advance the region. From a security perspective, however, India relies on platforms such as the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (QUAD), the bilateral naval security agreement with Singapore, partnerships with ASEAN countries (2012), and engagement in BRICS and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). These platforms enable India to project the image of a globally engaged, rising power.

The table below provides an overview of the transregional organizations in which India is also engaged, and through which it increasingly advances its political and strategic interests at both the regional and international levels.

³⁷ Menon, Shivshankar (2007): *Peaceful Periphery is a Prerequisite to Sustainour Growth, speech* at India and International Security, International Institute of Strategic Studies.

³⁸ K. Yome and T.S. Maini (2017): India's Evolving Approach to Regionalism: SAARC and Beyond, Vol 2, Issue 3, 147-165

Organisation	Founded / Established	Nature / Purpose
Commonwealth of Nations	Modern form since 1926 (formalised 1949)	Voluntary association of sovereign states promoting cooperation, democracy, development, and shared values among mostly former British Empire countries.
Asia–Europe Meeting (ASEM)	1996	Inter-regional forum for political dialogue, economic cooperation, and socio-cultural exchange between Asia and Europe.
Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO)	2001 (roots in 1996 "Shanghai Five")	Eurasian inter-governmental organisation focusing on regional security, counter-terrorism, political coordination, and economic cooperation.
Asia Cooperation Dialogue (ACD)	2002	Pan-Asian platform aimed at integrating Asian countries through dialogue and cooperation across multiple sectors.
Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad)	2007	Informal strategic grouping of India, Japan, Australia, and the U.S.; focuses on Indo-Pacific security, maritime cooperation, technology, climate, and regional stability.
BRICS	2009 (BRIC 2009, BRICS 2010 onward)	Grouping of major emerging economies aimed at strengthening economic cooperation, South–South partnership, and reform of global governance institutions.

Table 2: India's Membership in Transnational Organizations

India's participation in regional organisations therefore serves a partially symbolic purpose: demonstrating that it has South Asia "under control". In practice, India pursues realpolitik through regional and transregional organisations when these serve its national interests, including strategic autonomy, leadership in the Indian Ocean, its claim as a voice of the Global South, and selective regional integration.

Map 1: Venn Diagram of the Indian Ocean Rim and Its Organizations

SAARC, IORA and BIMSTEC in India's Political-Strategic Context

SAARC, IORA and BIMSTEC, as regional organizations, hold the potential to shape South Asian as well as broader transregional pathways for the future. In the case of SAARC in particular, India's geopolitical aspirations stand in sharp contrast to the politically tense realities of South Asia. The organization, known as pan-South Asian, is widely regarded as unproductive. With Modi's *Neighbourhood First Policy, Act East Policy*, and the foundational SAGAR (Security and Growth for All in the Region) vision, there is hope that SAARC will gain greater significance and assume a more active role in India's diplomatic engagements.

Comprising Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, the Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka, SAARC was established in 1985 with the aim of creating a socio-economic platform for regional integration. Due to the massive asymmetries within the region, smaller states often do not feel in a leading position – lacking resources, capabilities, and political leverage, they tend to be at a disadvantage in negotiations. Beyond India's difficult relations with Pakistan, Sri Lanka and Bangladesh currently fear political interference by New Delhi. India's external intelligence service, the Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW), has interfered not only in Sri Lanka but also in Nepal during the Maoist insurgency. These insecurities and mutual distrust hinder the formation of a joint agenda and limit

meaningful regional cooperation (intra-regional economic exchange among SAARC members accounts for merely five percent). India is reluctant to “play the SAARC card” and strengthen the organization, as this would primarily benefit Pakistan and could constrain India’s geopolitical ambitions. Consequently, New Delhi refrains from fully enabling the emergence of a regional identity, deeper economic integration, or a stable regional foreign policy. Both direct and indirect interference in neighbouring states further undermines SAARC’s objectives.

India faces a strategic dilemma with SAARC: if New Delhi leverages its political and economic weight to strengthen the organization, its rival Pakistan will benefit; if it does not push SAARC forward, this could be portrayed internationally as a failure of Indian leadership.

In contrast, IORA serves as a platform through which India can help shape the evolving international architecture. Its agenda focuses on (1) economic development, (2) maritime security, and (3) inclusive diplomacy –objectives common to many regional organizations. What makes IORA particularly appealing for India is that it broadens South Asia’s subregional perspective. Suddenly, new actors and new issue areas enter the foreground. The organization is strongly India-centric, and New Delhi sees itself as the natural representative and leader in the Indian Ocean. Beyond the typical SAARC topics, issues such as piracy, international smuggling, maritime affairs (e.g., the blue economy and maritime security) come into play. The regional security architecture – traditionally shaped by the Indo-Pakistan rivalry – can now be discussed under different conditions and with 23 member states. The focus shifts toward Indo-Pacific dynamics, and Pakistan is not part of the grouping. This “playing field” allows India to counterbalance the strategic dilemma posed by SAARC on an international stage.

India’s engagement with BIMSTEC is even more credible and operationally focused. The states

bordering the Bay of Bengal are represented in BIMSTEC. As with IORA, this expands the geographic scope of South Asia and centres attention on a region vital for international trade (e.g., Sea Lines of Communication). Cooperation in diplomacy, economic affairs, and security creates opportunities for all involved in this geopolitically sensitive region – especially for India. BIMSTEC acts as a regional platform designed to curb China’s growing influence. The United States supports this direction, creating thematic and diplomatic convergences. Consequently, BIMSTEC is regarded by the political West as a strategic platform with India in the driver’s seat. This includes India’s involvement in infrastructure projects in these regions – an engagement that has not always been viewed favourably, given New Delhi’s previous neglect of its own northeastern areas.

BIMSTEC demonstrates how India instrumentalizes regional organizations and the strategic calculus that underpins this approach:

1. **Strengthening ties with Southeast Asia** to circumvent the Pakistan dilemma and expand India’s strategic manoeuvring space.
2. **Promoting transregional platforms** (IORA and BIMSTEC) that allow India to diplomatically integrate strategically important regions (e.g., BIMSTEC members were invited to the 2016 BRICS Summit in India; also reflected in the Act East Policy).
3. **Shaping regional agendas**, enabling India to operationally maximize its influence.

It is noteworthy that BIMSTEC members who also belong to SAARC show greater alignment and support for India within the BIMSTEC context. This is partly because the thematic agenda matters significantly to India (e.g., climate change, maritime research), the hierarchy is less pronounced (not least because Pakistan is absent), and the multi-sectoral

focus is more inclusive. Moreover, the Bay of Bengal is believed to contain significant gas and oil reserves.

Through BIMSTEC, India brings the following issues to the forefront:

1. **Blue Economy Development**
2. **Maritime Security**
3. **Maritime Connectivity**
4. **Disaster Management**

Interestingly, the United States' *Indian Ocean Region Strategic Review Act of 2024* emphasizes the same priorities for the Indian Ocean as BIMSTEC. This suggests that BIMSTEC is not only a strategic instrument for New Delhi but may also reflect – directly or indirectly – strategic alignment with the United States. India's strategic autonomy appears to have a certain tilt, indicating that India's aspiration for regional pre-eminence in Asia is increasingly tied to U.S. support. This limits New Delhi's diplomatic manoeuvrability. The degree to which India can emancipate itself from Washington, D.C. remains to be seen. However, by shifting from a "land strategy" to an "ocean strategy," India has at least rhetorically and discursively staked out its strategic territory.

Strategic Outlook

This insight into India's engagement in regional and transregional institutions shows that India does not hold a secure position in South Asia. Its dominance creates a critical distance between the smaller South Asian states and India, while the security complex between Pakistan and India effectively neutralizes the region. In this complex situation, India struggles to position itself as a true geopolitical player.

By shifting its strategic focus away from South Asia and toward the Indian Ocean as a region of interest – obviously driven by competition with China – India has found a clever exit strategy. On one hand, it sidesteps the dilemma posed by Pakistan; on the other, it advances its geopolitical ambitions and foreign policy interests through forums such as IORA and BIMSTEC. This is "maritime regionalism" that

capitalizes on geopolitical opportunities. Here, New Delhi addresses vital interests it shares with the United States. Wrapped in maritime themes such as the Blue Economy, Sea Lines of Communication, and commitments to sustainability and climate protection, India's geopolitical agenda is packaged in a way that is narratively palatable, even if the underlying interests are hard-nosed.

South Asia as a geographic region is of little real importance in this strategy. For India, it's about India—also in the sense of the greater Indian vision of *Akhand Bharat*.

**Dr. Remo Reginokd is President of SIGA. His research focuses on the geopolitics of knowledge and the international politics of South Asia*

The Kashmir Issue

The Kashmir conflict is a territorial, political, and historical dispute that began with the partition of India in 1947 and remains unresolved to this day. India, Pakistan, and also China in the northeastern part of Kashmir face each other as parties to the conflict. In this contribution, from a social anthropological perspective, Sana Asghar from the Pakistani side and Jasmeen Kaur from the Indian side examine everyday social life and the conflict in this region. This description helps to outline geopolitical dynamics from the ground.

5. Hardships of the People of Azad Jammu & Kashmir: From the Beginning to Today

*Sana Asghar**

The Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK) story is a tale of both beauty and misery, mixed in a manner that not many other territories in the world have seen happen. Sandwiched between the giant Himalayas and Karakoram ranges, this region has been dubbed heaven on earth due to its fertile valleys, river basins, snow-white mountains, and cultural heritage. But, behind its spectacular scenery, there is a history of suffering, doubt, and conflict. The sufferings of people of Azad Kashmir are not limited to poverty or underdevelopment as such. The war between two strong countries, frequent natural catastrophes, weak infrastructure, and social issues that concern all families in one way or another have determined their lives.

This essay aims to look into the sufferings of Azad Kashmir since the onset of its modern history to date. It is not attempting to take a position in the India-Pakistan political conflict, nor to resolve the thorny issue of sovereignty. The idea, rather, is to have the people themselves speak, who are the ones who live in the valleys and mountains, who are the ones who bring up children in uncertain circumstances, and

those who attempt to make a life for themselves even where there is instability. The tribulations of these people are pushed into the backdrop of the political arguments, and behind the headlines is a farmer unable to plough his land due to shelling, a child unable to attend school due to a broken bridge, a mother concerned about the next quake or flood, and a family that can only sleep in peace.

It might be a tiny region that is small compared to other territories, but its tale has universal lessons of resilience, survival, and the human price of war. The people of this area do not desire to possess power or dominance, they simply desire to be able to live a normal life, to till their farms, to take their children to school, to conduct weddings without being afraid, to construct houses which will never be demolished again. The message of Azad Kashmir is easy to hear peace and dignity are not luxuries, but rights, and the people who live in heaven on earth deserve nothing less.

Historical background, partition, and wars

The historical challenges experienced by the peoples of Kashmir today cannot be attributed to the events that occurred during the partition of British India in the year 1947 and the subsequent fighting that ensued over the Jammu and Kashmir region. At the time of the partitioning of British India into two new nations, India and Pakistan, the king of the state of Jammu and Kashmir was required to decide which nation to affiliate with. This brought about confusion, and shortly thereafter, the first war between India and Pakistan in 1948.

The result of that initial war was the division of the territory between the two nations by a temporary border, which is currently referred to as the Line of Control (LoC). This division was not established to be permanent, but it is the ground reality. More to the point, it became a model of recurring tension and conflict between the two countries. To the common men who lived along this line, it only implied that their lives were going to be punctuated by permanent

uncertainty as to when the next volleying or battle would commence.

The area, in the next few years, remained a battle and war between Pakistan and India. Two other significant wars in 1965 and 1971 were fought by them whereby Kashmir was a source of dispute. The smaller military conflicts and the high tension periods were also numerous. Since the late 1980s and the 1990s, the situation became even more complex with the armed resistance movement in Kashmir gaining substantial power and facing an enormous military response.

Everyday Hardships

Life is determined by the geography and geopolitics of Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK). The Line of Control (LoC) does not happen to be merely a line on the map; this is a fact that has been lived through to establish one continuous misfortune after another to the generations of the Kashmiri people. This is contrary to most other conflict zones where the LoC is at the center of villages, farmland, schools, and even family circles and makes ordinary individuals vulnerable and in an uncertain sphere.

To the people of villages like Chakothei, Neelum Valley, and Kotli, the firing of guns or mortar shells is not considered something new. The families are in constant fear, and it is usual to see them sleeping in the basement or improvised bunkhouses as the firing continues to escalate. Farmers relate how they schedule their visits to fields either in the early morning hours or during the late evening hours, and wish to avoid the active hours of cross-border shooting. Parents often mention the apprehension about taking their children to school in open places.

In 2018, cross-border shelling in the Neelum Valley resulted in the killing of five civilians, including two children, when a strike hit their home. Victims narrated how the family had been thinking of emigrating, but they were unable to leave their lands and cattle. This is how the tragedy of the so-called

double bind is depicted: to stay here one will be on fire, and to go there is to be ruined economically.

The uncertainty caused by violence causes constant anxiety even in the absence of any firing. Mental health practitioners observe the following symptoms in children and adults in border communities: nightmares, hypervigilance, and depression. At least the results of a local health survey conducted in 2019 reveal that approximately one-third of children who lived within five kilometres of the LoC displayed symptoms of trauma related stress. However, there are almost no mental health facilities in rural AJK, and families must deal without professional assistance.

Agriculture, which supports most rural AJK households, is very susceptible. Shelling destroys irrigation channels, causes the killing and loss of livestock during displacements, and makes access to markets dangerous. When roads are unsafe, small businesses are shut down. One of the local shopkeepers in Muzaffarabad said, "Each time we think that life is normal, some more firing occurs, and people remain inside, and days go by with no customers".

The LoC and the adjacent territories are still full of landmines left behind by the previous wars and tense situations. The goat herding children, or in field games, may walk on these bombs beneath the ground and suffer serious injury or death. Humanitarian groups indicate that Pakistan has long been one of the nations with the highest number of landmine casualties annually across the world, with most of this being in the border areas, such as AJK.

The shelling insecurity is not a single case the displacement trauma, economic catastrophe of ruined crops, threat of landmines, interrupted education, and health care are just an addition to the daily sufferings AJK people must endure. The result of these circumstances is a feeling of vulnerability that is widespread and leads to further spread of poverty and social development setbacks. Such sufferings are not just the by-products of geographical character, but the result of the political

decisions taken by the people, the failure to protect the civilian population in the conflicts.

The 2005 Earthquake and Recurring Shocks

The natural disasters have provided one more agonising topic to the existence of the Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK) people. Although the armed conflict takes the stage in the news pages, nature has many times proved its extreme potential to destroy communities in this mountainous area. AJK is highly susceptible to earthquakes, landslides, and floods due to the steep terrain, the vulnerable soil, and seismic activity in the region. The most traumatic disaster in recent history is the 2005 earthquake that made its mark in this area.

A 7.6 magnitude earthquake hit the AJK capital of Muzaffarabad on 8 October 2005. It killed over 73,000 individuals, wounded over 100,000 others, and displaced almost 3.5 million people in Pakistan controlled Kashmir and northern Pakistan. Whole villages were levelled down and towns such as Muzaffarabad and Bagh were brought down to ruins.

The fact that the earthquake occurred at a time when the schools were in the process of teaching, i.e., right after 8:50 a.m., implied that thousands of children were killed in collapsing classrooms. Whole generations were wiped out in the shortest time possible, as families who had sent children away to school in the morning were wiped out. This created permanent scars in the psyche of the Kashmiri people. One of the survivors at Muzaffarabad was quoted as saying, "I lost my three children that morning. School bags in their hands, they went. They never returned."

Later, the Earthquake Relief and Rehabilitation Authority (ERRA) was formed to oversee reconstruction. The 2005 quake was one of the most funded disaster recoveries in South Asia, with billions of dollars in aid coming in as a result of the efforts of the international donors. But the reconstruction was slowly achieved, especially in the high altitude

villages where snow in winter further postponed rebuilding.

Aftermath of the Earthquake

The earthquake brought down or destroyed almost 6,000 schools in AJK. Temporary learning facilities could not meet the needs, and thousands of children lost years of education. Some girls did not go back to school, and the reasons were either fear, household chores, or marrying early due to family disruptions.

The quake caused invisible injuries. Described feelings of intense fear of enclosed spaces, nightmares, and grief by the survivors. There were not many mental health facilities, and a lot of people had to cope in silence. High incidences of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) were recorded in children in Muzaffarabad and Bagh by psychologists later.

Although the 2005 earthquake was the most fatal incident, floods and landslides can be considered the frequent risks in AJK:

- 2010 Pakistan Floods: Flash floods and landslides hit all parts of AJK due to heavy monsoon rains that damaged houses, bridges, and agricultural lands. Families that had just started to salvage out of the 2005 earthquake were washed away again.
- 2014 Neelum Valley Landslides: Ongoing rain in Neelum Valley caused massive landslides that covered villages and riverways. The landslides cut off food and medicine supply by isolating communities' weeks.
- 2022 Flood Season: Flooding and slope collapses due to torrential rains once again destroyed houses in Muzaffarabad and Rawalakot districts.

Even the moderate rains can cause landslides as the terrain is mountainous, and the available roads are extremely limited. Not only is this life-threatening, but it slows the economy, as crops are unable to get to

markets, patients are unable to get to hospitals, and schools close down for days.

The natural disasters have caused devastating effects in AJK, particularly the 2005 earthquake that hit the region. They destroyed property, education and lives and put people in poverty forever, and contributed to the suffering which political struggle already caused. However, with these, the power of the Kashmiri community also came to the light and how the community needs to invest in disaster preparedness, sturdy infrastructure and psychological assistance.

Natural disasters are uncontrollable, and their effects could be minimized by means of improved planning and improved infrastructure, as well as the international support that should be extended over time. The dream of AJK residents does not simply mean the end of the war but also the end of the wrath of nature.

Infrastructure, Services, and Economic Issues

Even though the news of Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK) is dominated by war and calamities, the secondary crisis of weak infrastructure and poor social services is also catastrophic to the lives of residents. The communities cannot realise their potential due to poor roads, poor electricity, poor water and sanitation, overstretched schools and hospitals. Such problems not only slow down the economic growth but expose Kashmiri families to poverty, calamities, and violence.

Road's construction in AJK is expensive and roads are hard to maintain because of steep mountains, narrow valleys, and slopes predisposed to landslides. However, to the people in the village's roads are lifeblood: they help to connect farmers to markets, students to schools, and patients to hospitals. Unfortunately, not all regions of the area have asphalted roads with a single lane, which can no longer be driven when it rains or snows. Landslides tend to block highways taking up days or even across entire valleys.

The supply of electricity in AJK is paradoxical. It contains some of the biggest hydropower stations, including Mangla Dam, one of the biggest in Pakistan, yet most of the Kashmiri villages must endure daily load-shedding. The power supply is more reliable in cities like Muzaffarabad and rural areas are also facing prolonged power cuts, especially during the winter seasons. Household firewood brings about deforestation. Say the little businessmen, electrical interruptions kill production, be it dairy stores, carpentry shops.

Remote villages lack much sanitation infrastructure. Local streams are polluted by open defecation and improperly built latrines. Some community water schemes had been established by the aid agencies after the 2005 earthquake; however, most of them were never maintained because of the insufficiency of financial aid.

AJK experiences a lack of specialists, nurses, and doctors. Most of the medical practitioners like to work in the larger cities of Pakistan, as it has better facilities and increased wages. The outcome is overworked district hospital staff and patient wait times. In 2019, during the Pulwama crisis, hospitals in Muzaffarabad said they struggled to handle the number of civilian casualties caused by shelling on the LoC. Mental health is an issue that is neglected. Victims of shelling, displacement, and disasters rarely get counselling.

Although AJK is blessed with natural beauty and resources, it is faced with poor economic opportunities. Agriculture is mainly subsistence-based, which is subject to weather and war. There is a tourism potential, especially in Neelum Valley, but insecurity and poor infrastructure discourage investors. A large number of youths travel to the cities of Pakistan or to other countries (particularly to the Gulf and the UK) to seek employment and leave a remittance economy. Although remittances are an important source of income, dependency due to the reliance on migration also leaves the local economies underdeveloped.

Impact of Infrastructure, Services, and Economic Issues

The drawbacks of infrastructure and services are directly converted into suffering. A mother who walks for hours to gather water from a spring. A student who misses classes due to the destruction of her school or the school's closure due to the shell. A dying patient is being transported to a hospital due to a roadblock due by a landslide. Closing down of a shopkeeper because of a power cut. These are the struggles that hardly feature on the international agenda and yet form the reality in the lives of the majority of Kashmiris.

The infrastructure is not all about the cement and steel; it is also about dignity and opportunity. To the Azad Kashmiris, safer travelling, healthier families, educated children, and new employment could be better services. In the absence of long-term investment, though, the economy will continue to stagnate and suffer, further increasing the feeling of marginalization already brought about by conflict.

Political and Human Rights

The politics is not a far-off affair of parliaments and treaties; it is a daily fact of life in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, it is how movement, opportunities, and dignity are created. Although AJK has its own elected government and institutions, the level of their autonomy is limited, and the administration tends to falter under the pressure of bigger geopolitical conflicts. Meanwhile, the common citizens are restricted, have a problem with their rights, and are not represented in the process when the decisions made directly influence their lives.

How Partition Effected AJK

At the time of partitioning of British India in 1947, the princely states such as Jammu & Kashmir were left to make decisions whether to be a part of India or Pakistan. The later invasion of the region by the tribal groups, the controversial accession of the Maharaja to India, and the first Indo-Pak war resulted in the

split of the region along the Line of Control (LoC). In 1947, the area that is now Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK) fell under the control of Pakistani administration, and only a larger part of Jammu and Kashmir became part of India. Since AJK has lived in a grey area, neither a state of Pakistan nor completely self-sufficient.

AJK has its Legislative Assembly, Prime Minister, and President, but under the constitution, the federal government of Pakistan has so much power, especially with the AJK Council in Islamabad. This duality brings about the conflict between the ambitions of self-rule and the fact of external management.

The critics maintain that institutions in AJK tend to move on Islamabad guidance. This has increased a feeling of political reliance and reduced the capacity of the local leadership to focus on Kashmiri-specific needs like infrastructure, education, and the protection of human rights. Corruption, patronage politics, and slowness in the bureaucracy are also issues that weaken local governance. The rural population is usually disengaged from the decision-making process and is not very convinced that they are being listened to.

Although AJK permits some form of political action, the Kashmir policy of Pakistan is usually censored. There are legal and practical difficulties in parties that promote total independence (independent of both India and Pakistan). Self-censorship is reported by journalists because of pressure from authorities. Activists are either threatened with harassment or detention when they cross political red lines.

Although AJK has its elected institutions, it is not uncommon to notice that Kashmiris do not have any say in decision-making processes regarding their future. There are international negotiations between India and Pakistan without direct Kashmiri involvement, which only strengthens a feeling of being marginalized. This lack of agency is not psychologically neutral, and many feel like passive subjects in making decisions about their own land.

Pulwama Attack and Its Impact on Azad Jammu & Kashmir

A suicide bombing occurred on 14 February 2019 in the Pulwama district, in Indian-controlled Kashmir. An Indian paramilitary force (CRPF) convoy was also targeted, resulting in the death of more than 40 soldiers. The assault horrified the entire region. It was plotted by the Pakistan based militant group Jaish-e-Mohammed (JeM) against India. Pakistan was unwilling to be implicated. This was not just a local tragedy in Pulwama as it soon turned into one of the most hazardous conflicts between India and Pakistan in the recent years.

India's reaction and Pakistan's Reply

India reacted to the attack by air bombing Balakot (Pakistan) allegedly to target militant camps. Pakistan retaliated as well by airstriking across the Line of Control (LoC). Fighter jets were downed and there were fears that war was breaking off. This was a military and diplomatic crisis to the world. To the Azad Jammu and Kashmir people, it was even nearer, it was a struggle to survive.

Along the border, the border, which is called the Line of Control (LoC), also turned extremely tense and perilous because of the Pulwama incident. The fighting was now much more intense with each side firing heavy arms like mortars and shells at the other. This especially was a challenge to the villages bordering the border. The individuals who suffered the most were those who lived in Neelum Valley, Kottli, Bhimber, and Poonch since they were in the centre of the violence.

Aftermath of the Attack

To the people and government of India, it was initially a horrifying and embarrassing tragedy that led to the loss of their security personnel on a large scale. It was a time of national sorrow and fury. To the Pakistani government and their people, the immediate aftermath was a period of deep

defensiveness and intense international pressure as the Pakistani nation was put under the scrutiny of the world and held to blame. To the rest of the world that was observing the crisis, the biggest concern was the possibility of a bigger war, and many leaders were very worried that the war could even escalate to the point where nuclear weapons would be used.

But to the common citizens residing in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, it was not international politics; it was a time of immediate and personal pain, intense fear, and massive uncertainty concerning the future. This crisis has been struggling with them, which should not be reduced to political slogans in the course of their daily hardship. In fact, this was regarding the very actual and painful loss of their family homes, the sabotaging of the education of their children as the schools were closed down, the eroding of their inner peace of mind, and the devastating setback to their very basic human dignity.

The 2019 Pulwama attack has been reported to be a military and political crisis between nations. The incident was however more personal and painful to the common man of Azad Jammu & Kashmir. It also marked the beginning of a long painful period of total terror, personal destruction of a great degree and severe money panic.

Social and Psychological Impact of Life in Azad Jammu & Kashmir

It is difficult living in Azad Jammu and Kashmir in concrete terms, such as crumbling-down roads, inadequately manned clinics, and burnt houses. But living in Azad Jammu and Kashmir is also difficult in intangible terms, those are the little internal hurts that people face in their minds and hearts each day. Those internal hurts are often the most painful because they impact the way that people feel about themselves, the way that mothers and children interact, and the way that young people see their futures. Chronic conflict, tragedies such as earthquakes, being extremely poor, and never quite knowing what the road is down tend to leave emotional scarring. Those internal hurts stick with

people long beyond the impact of hearing an explosion or earth-shaking event.

The Role of Women in Azad Kashmir's Struggle

Looking at the history of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, we discover that women have always been the core of this land. Their struggles are not loud, but are concealed within houses and in villages, but their weight is huge. During tranquility, they are the ones who give birth to families, they transmit traditions, and they unite the community. During a crisis – whether war, political, or natural disaster – women are burdened even more. Not only do they become caregivers, but also leaders, and hope symbols.

Women roles in the Region

Women are the natural caregivers in any Kashmiri house. They are the ones who take care of the ill, pacify the old, and provide the children with strength amidst stress. In remote villages, with hospitals distant and with lack of healthcare, women usually rely on traditional herbs and home remedies. This position is even more significant in the case of disasters or in curfews when access to doctors is disconnected. They serve without saying a word and hold families together.

One of the worst problems facing women in Azad Kashmir is education. A lot of families would like to send their daughters to school, which is very often distant or not properly furnished. Girls even walk uphill and across rivers, which is unsafe. Schools are the first to be shut down when there is conflict or natural disasters, and it is girls who suffer most. Girls also find it difficult to carry on with their education after a particular age due to cultural barriers. Nevertheless, some young women are still persistent despite all these challenges. Accounts of girls studying by candlelight or of girls who have gone to school, teaching younger brothers and sisters at home, demonstrate their attachment to education. Women teachers, particularly in rural communities,

are considered role models. Even in small, damaged schools, they keep the dream of education alive.

Youth of Azad Jammu & Kashmir

The learning process in Azad Jammu and Kashmir has never been restricted to lessons within a classroom. To children and young people growing up in this part of the world, education is considered to be the only way of breaking the yoke of poverty, earning a dignified name, and creating a new life without violence. Students who come to school with their bags in their hands walk to school every morning through steep hills or rivers, or conflict-torn villages, with the sole aim of studying and building a better tomorrow. Even with low incomes, parents tend to make massive sacrifices to enroll their children in school. Most fathers work for daily wages, and most mothers sew clothes or peddle little domestic products simply to buy books and uniforms. This demonstrates the degree of importance that people of Azad Kashmir attach to education despite the instability in the surrounding environment.

Hope of the Youth

Education for most of the youths is highly associated with their future aspirations. Their desire is not to have jobs to live; they need to establish peace, development, and honor for their region. Others hope to become doctors to be able to provide services to remote villages where they have no hospitals. Some others desire to become teachers who can give hope to the new generation, or engineers who can reconstruct the decaying infrastructure of their localities. Several young people also desire to work in technology, business, or international organizations, which proves that ambition is not dead even in conflict zones. But due to the scarcity of universities and the scarcity of opportunities locally, many educated youth of Kashmir have to emigrate out of the area to find employment or further education. This poses a painful brain drain, with the people who might have created Azad Kashmir

instead remaining in the places where they are utilized.

Ultimately, youth in Azad Kashmir's education is not just another matter concerning learning facts and figures; it is a matter of survival and hope. All schools that remain open in a challenging situation are turned into a beacon of hope. Each student finishing his or her studies leaves behind him a torchbearer to a bright future. The young generation of this region hopes for a day when they will be able to learn without any fear, when schools will not be destroyed by war or calamities, and when their education will be utilized in building their own area instead of migrating. It is a shame that in the course of losing thousands of young people, generations will be needed to recover, but the hopes of the young people who managed to survive manifest that there is light at the end of the tunnel, and the fire of hope will never be put out. Their best weapon against poverty, fear, and conflict is education, and their best hope is that they can be free and peaceful.

Kashmir as a Pawn Between Pakistan and India

The Kashmir tragedy is not merely the mountains, rivers, and valleys that were mutilated by the conflict, but also how its people have been put on the chessboard as chess pieces. The people of Kashmir are now more than seventyfive years being utilized by both Pakistan and India as an instrument of their own national interest. Instead of addressing the lives, dreams, and rights of the common Kashmiri people, both states have frequently made Kashmir a symbol, a weapon that is to be wielded in speeches, propaganda, and political battles. To the residents of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, it has simply meant that their voice is not heard, their needs are not addressed, and that their suffering is being extended.

Indian Side

The political manipulation of Kashmir on the Indian side is mostly expressed in the form of legislation and

amendments that are aimed at controlling rather than benefiting Kashmiris. One of the key instances of this is the removal of Article 370 in August 2019, depriving Jammu & Kashmir of the special status that it had enjoyed for decades. That was done via a Presidential Order and with the enactment of the Jammu Reorganisation Act, 2019, and the Jammu & Kashmir Reorganisation Act, 2019, dividing the territory into two Union Territories. Due to that shift, numerous laws enacted by Parliament now directly apply to Jammu & Kashmir, alterations occurred without significant consultation at the local level, and the central government gained more influence in making decisions directly impacting everyday life.

In 2024, another amendment was made through the Transaction of Business Rules, which was issued by the Government of India through an executive notification. This amendment gave greater authority to the Lieutenant Governor of Jammu and Kashmir, granting the unelected Lieutenant Governor greater control over the major administrative roles such as transfers and postings of officers, and in certain instances even legal prosecutions. This implied that a lot of authority that was being wielded by elected local officials was transferred to central appointees. This amendment was heavily criticized by the Kashmiri political leaders and opposition parties, who termed it as an effort to reduce the democratic interests of the people.

Pakistan's Side

So has Pakistan, politics in which Kashmir has been utilized. Kashmir is frequently mentioned in political speech, on national holidays, in the press, as evidence of national identity and determination. Leaders attract the masses to their cause, talking about human rights violations in Indian-controlled Kashmir, which they use to rally their own populations. Most Kashmiris are happy to see international attention and support, but have criticized the fact that Pakistan, at times, is more about symbolic action than about providing sustainable improvements to the Kashmiris on the

Pakistan side, such as in infrastructure, education, or health services.

India and Pakistan have at one point or another promoted or permitted the spread of narratives that exaggerate or inflate threats or incidents. These are the stories to legitimize war, limit civil rights, or to consolidate political power. Ordinary Kashmiris listen to these words when politicians talk about the problem of terrorism, national security, or sovereignty, but they experience the effects: loss of life, interference with normal routines, fear, and in most cases, loss of money.

India and Pakistan should begin to cease their political exploitation of Kashmir as a means of achieving political objectives, first and foremost, if they genuinely desire to restore peace to the region. They should stop regarding the region as a pride and power battlefield and be able to listen to the people who have been suffering for decades. The real improvement can only be realized at a time when the voices of the Kashmiri people are the focus of the discourse rather than being silenced by propaganda. The manipulation will go on until then, and the common people of Kashmir will be the ones who will continue to suffer the consequences of wars they had no say in.

From Hardship to Inspire Change – Sardar Muhammad Ibrahim Khan

Sardar Muhammad Ibrahim Khan was also one of the most admired leaders of AJK, and he is commonly referred to as one of the earliest and most influential in the history of AJK. Being born in 1915 in Poonch, he belonged to a simple family, though he did everything to have an education. He came back after his law degree in London with the hope of bringing about change in his people. During the disorder of the Partition in 1947, he was instrumental in the declaration of the formation of the Azad Government of Jammu and Kashmir. To common people in Kashmir, he turned into an icon of heroism as a man who demonstrated that the way of one man could spark up a whole movement. Even during

political instability, service-based leadership can add hope to people, as seen in his life.

Kashmiri literature and Famous Writers

Kashmiri literature and poetry have proved to be very powerful tools of expression. Writers used words to keep alive the spirit of Kashmir when political liberties were suppressed and the war was a subject of taboo. One such poetry was that written by Habib Jalib Kashmiri, whereby he talked about pain, injustice and hope. His poems made people remember that their sufferings were not in vain and the dream of liberty was not to be oppressed by barbed fences and boundaries.

Shaukat Ali Kashmiri was another significant personality who was a political activist and writer. He had been arrested and prevented numerous times, but kept on fighting, campaigning on human rights, both in Kashmir and beyond. He was able to provide a voice to so many common people who could not speak on their behalf through his writings. His examples demonstrate that resistance does not always have to be waged with guns; sometimes it can be waged with bravery, speech, and refusal to be silent.

Sports in AJK

Sport has also been inspirational. AJK athletes, albeit in small numbers because of facilities, have represented Pakistan in martial arts, football, and cricket. Their success teaches the young generation that talent and hard work can open a door even when resources are limited. Likewise, AJK musicians and artists are beginning to use social media they share their songs and paintings to maintain Kashmiri culture as well as share the message of peace.

These renowned personalities and ordinary heroes indicate a universal fact that the greatest strength of AJK is its people. Sardar Ibrahim was a leader of a movement, a poet composing verses under

ensorship, a teacher who had classes in a tent, or a young athlete who had no proper equipment; all of them made adversity their stepping stone. Not only do their stories inspire Kashmiris, but they also inspire anyone who struggles with a conflict, poverty, or even being neglected.

Suggestions and Solutions for a Better Future

The history of Azad Jammu and Kashmir is replete with immensely miserable and marvellous energy. The people have had many ills especially that they are very poor, conflict, forced displacement and Earthquakes and floods have been tormenting the people many years over. However, the fact that they are courageous and do not want to surrender has brought their people together. The problems are serious and have been in existence long enough, yet they can be solved. This will be through collective efforts of the government, the international assistance organizations as well as the locals. In this case we shall address several practical and reality-based ideas that can transform the daily living of the Kashmir people and provide them with hope. They are not certain magic solutions since it needs to be done in good faith and with a great deal of effort, but these can make the suffering go away and then they can start to have a more peaceful and successful future.

The most significant and immediate thing to do is to strive to achieve peace at the Line of Control (LoC). The Kashmiri citizens in their day-to-day lives have no opportunity to make any political decisions, yet when fighting erupts, it is the family that bears the greatest consequences. A stable and sustained ceasefire between India and Pakistan would transform lives immediately. The farmers were able to labor on their farms without fear. Children were able to attend school without risk. There was no worry that families would be rebuilt as their homes could be ruined once more. A ceasefire would not solve all political questions of Kashmir; however, it would provide common people with an opportunity to lead a normal life, which many of them have never

experienced. Minor gestures might also play a role, such as having families on one side of the border visit one another or even having trade resume. The bus service, which used to move between Srinagar and Muzaffarabad, demonstrated that even such small steps might mean everything to the families that were separated years ago.

Another extremely important need is the fixing of the basic infrastructures and services in the region. In Azad Kashmir, roads, bridges, hospitals, and schools are usually poorly constructed or destroyed, and natural calamities aggravate the situation. The government, with the assistance of international partners, should strive to construct earthquake-resistant schools, hospitals, repair broken mountain roads, and construct safe river crossings. Improved infrastructure would make life easier and also enable the remote villages to access towns to sell products and seek assistance. An example is that a farmer in the Leepa Valley can make more money by taking his apples to the market of a city where he can access it safely and in a short time. As well, having improved clinics and ambulances, ill or injured individuals would stand a better chance of survival. Good infrastructure is not simply about construction, but it is also about providing people with safety, respect, and a fair chance to succeed.

The physical and mental health of people should also be given top priority. As we have observed, individuals in Azad Kashmir have visible wounds and an invisible emotional suffering. Establishing counseling facilities, training local physicians on how to assist individuals with traumas, and informing people on mental wellness can assist individuals in dealing with fear, depression, and stress. Mobile health staff would be able to travel to remote villages that are far away hospitals. Collaboration with nonprofit organizations may offer inexpensive medication and health camps in the regions where few services are available. A healthy society is built on healthy persons, and the people of Kashmir are just like anyone else in society.

More attention should be paid to generating jobs and supporting local businesses to enable people to thrive. At this time, a large number of young men are forced to abandon their homes and families in search of employment in foreign countries. Azad Kashmir can generate good jobs near home by promoting small industries such as the traditional crafts, including food processing, tourism, and clean energy. As an illustration, the beautiful Neelum Valley and Rawalakot could receive thousands of visitors in case conditions were safe and infrastructure were enhanced. Tourism projects that are nature-friendly might benefit thousands of families who make a living. In addition, the sale of well known Kashmir handmade items such as shawls, rugs, and wooden carvings in Pakistan and other nations would introduce more revenue to the region. The youthful population can also be equipped through job training programs to work in new varieties of jobs; therefore, they do not need to leave home in an attempt to sustain their families.

Another solution is preparedness for disasters and environmental protection. Due to the frequent occurrence of earthquakes, floods, and landslides in the region, the government and local citizens must be in a better position. Construction of houses that do not collapse during catastrophes, planting of trees to avoid land erosion, and installation of alarms to alert individuals about danger will save numerous lives. Even the dreadful earthquake that struck in the year 2005 taught us bitter lessons of lack of preparedness. Provided that those lessons are applied prudently, it will be possible to make the region safer in the future. It is also important to take care of the environment- activities such as cutting down excess trees and poor use of land have aggravated flooding and erosion. It is not only about ensuring that the scenery is beautiful, but also about ensuring that people can survive and live.

In conclusion, Azad Jammu and Kashmir have been bearing excessive loss, but all can be improved. Our focus on peace, infrastructure, health, education, jobs, women rights, disaster preparedness, and local voice can help us to build a brighter future. The world

must play its part in ensuring the people of Kashmir enjoy dignified and opportunity filled lives instead of struggling to keep alive. Their inner strength has brought them this far but it is time to not only be resilient but also be really better. When these solutions are actually pursued, the beautiful valleys of Azad Kashmir will have the sounds of playing children and melodies of a community in hope.

Conclusion

Azad Jammu and Kashmir is not only the story of beautiful valleys, snow-white mountain or green meadows that flow with rivers. It is beyond that a tale of men, ordinary men, women and children who have been pushed to the extreme in their lives. The population has been bearing the burden of the past in the background of the spectacular landscape. In this case, the families have undergone wars, migration, earthquakes, floods, poverty and political instability. Their experiences have never been shaped by their will since the very first days of partition in 1947 to the present time but rather by the forces which are much greater than their own. But even in the face of all this they have never lost hope. They have exhibited this superhuman courage to such an extent that houses have been raised after earthquakes, schools have been shell shut and life has been continued, even when tomorrow was not sure.

One such example that demonstrated how vulnerable the lives of Kashmiris are is the Pulwama attack of 2019 and its subsequent consequences. Although the attack was carried out on the Indian side, it was the people of Azad Jammu and Kashmir who felt the impact of this attack instantly. Villages along the border were again shell-shocked. Families were forced to leave their houses and seek refuge in bunkhouses. The schools were shut down, trade across the LoC was halted, and ordinary life was grounded. By doing that, they brought even those who were already in poverty further into insecurity. Similar to most of the previous events, this one revealed a bitter reality that, whenever there are

political tensions between India and Pakistan, the greatest losers are the innocent Kashmiris, despite their lack of a voice in such decisions.

The above solutions imply that change is possible. A permanent ceasefire in the LoC would offer the families the basic gift of safety, of being able to sleep without being scared by explosions. Better roads, bridges and schools would connect communities with hospitals, markets and opportunities. Improved healthcare, and specifically mental healthcare, would offer a channel of healing both physical and invisible wounds of trauma. Children would have non-conflict dreams and opportunities would be opened to them through good education. The painful state of the youth migration would be avoided since the local economic opportunities would allow them to build their future in their homeland. By empowering women and equipping them with skills and education and resources, you would empower not only families but also communities.

Finally, environmental protection and disaster preparedness would ensure that less damage is caused by floods and earthquakes that would claim the lives of thousands of people. What matters the most of all is that the Kashmiris must be heard in the decisions they must make about their own future and this would elevate the dignity of the people and make them feel that they are not merely a victim of politics.

The history cannot be unwritten, but the future can be rewritten. The nation of Azad Kashmir should not just survive, but they need to be happy, flourish, and peaceful. They should not hear the sound of guns in their valleys but the voices of children studying, farmers toiling, women as leaders, and families rejoicing. However, the moment the world really believes in justice and humanity, it needs to act in support of them, not as a chess piece, but as individuals who desire that the right to live with dignity is universal.

* Sana Asghar is a Senior Fellow at SIGA and graduate student at the University of Basel, Switzerland.

References

- [1] A. Bose, *Kashmir at the Crossroads: Inside a 21st-Century Conflict*. New Delhi, India: HarperCollins, 2020.
- [2] A. Snedden, *Kashmir: The Unwritten History*. London, UK: Hurst & Co., 2012.
- [3] S. Schofield, *Kashmir in Conflict: India, Pakistan and the Unending War*. London, UK: I.B. Tauris, 2021.
- [4] M. Bose, *Kashmir: Roots of Conflict, Paths to Peace*. Cambridge, MA, USA: Harvard Univ. Press, 2009.
- [5] "India–Pakistan Wars," *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/event/India-Pakistan-wars> (accessed Sept. 12, 2025).
- [6] United Nations Security Council, "Resolution 47 (1948) on the India-Pakistan Question," Apr. 21, 1948.
- [7] Asian Development Bank (ADB), "Pakistan: Earthquake Emergency Assistance," ADB Evaluation Report, 2006.
- [8] World Bank, "Pakistan Earthquake 2005: Damage and Needs Assessment," Report No. 31774, Nov. 2005.
- [9] Amnesty International, "Denied: Failures in Addressing the Needs of Victims of the 2005 Earthquake in Pakistan," AI Index: ASA 33/023/2006.
- [10] Human Rights Watch, *With Friends Like These: Human Rights Violations in Azad Kashmir*, HRW Report, Sept. 2006.
- [11] "Pulwama attack: Timeline of events," *BBC News*, Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-47302467>
- [12] "After Pulwama, Cross-Border Tensions Rise," *Al Jazeera*, Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2019/2/>

[13] S. Z. Qureshi, "The Psychological Impact of Conflict on Kashmiri Youth," *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 45–60, 2017.

[14] Save the Children, "Children in Conflict Zones: A Case Study of Kashmir," NGO Report, 2018.

[15] A. Malik, "The Role of Kashmiri Women During the 2005 Earthquake," *Journal of Gender Studies*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 88–103, 2008.

[16] S. Nazir, "Women in Azad Kashmir: Agents of Change Amid Conflict," *Asian Journal of Peacebuilding*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 223–240, 2019.

[17] "Voices of Kashmiri Women," UN Women Report, 2017.

6. Kashmir: Between Fear, Hope and The Politics of Suppression

*Jasmeen Kaur**

The Kashmir region, long known for its natural beauty and strategic importance, remains a deeply contested area primarily between India and Pakistan. While it is rich in culture and resources, the region particularly Jammu and Kashmir (J&K), administered by India has faced increasing human rights violations. Since India revoked J&K's autonomous status in 2019, residents have reported widespread surveillance, restrictions on free speech, arbitrary arrests, and suppression of dissent. The story of Javid Ahmad Dar, whose passport renewal was denied due to his brother's journalism, highlights how everyday citizens suffer under these repressive policies. International human rights organizations, including Amnesty International, have called for greater accountability and global awareness of the situation.

This essay seeks to examine the multifaceted struggles of ordinary Kashmiris — their disrupted livelihoods, the militarized atmosphere they live in, their educational and economic challenges, and the psychological impact of constant surveillance and fear. It also evaluates the role of India-Pakistan tensions, the influence of external actors like China, and the broader implications for democracy and minority rights in India. By focusing on the lived experiences of the people, the essay reveals how political agendas and international rivalries have consistently sidelined the voices and aspirations of Kashmir's own residents.

Militarization and the Collapse of Trust

The daily presence of the Indian Army, Central Reserve Police Force (CRPF), and other paramilitary forces is an inescapable reality for Kashmiris. Checkpoints, frisking zones, and random inspections

are embedded into everyday movement. Reports of arbitrary detentions, extrajudicial killings, and enforced disappearances have been documented by international human rights organizations. The people often feel caught between militants who threaten them for cooperating with the Indian state and security forces who suspect them of aiding terrorism.

Militarization is not limited to the Valley. Many Kashmiris who migrate to other parts of India for education or employment also face racial profiling, public harassment, and allegations of disloyalty. A 2019 *BBC* report highlighted how Kashmiri students across Indian cities were labelled "terrorists" and attacked physically or socially after the Pulwama bombing ([BBC News, 2019](#)).

Such a militarized environment erodes the foundational trust between the people and the state. It also imposes long-term psychological effects — particularly on the youth, who grow up under surveillance, curfews, and fear.

The Shadow of Conflict on Daily Life

The brutal attack in April 2025 in Pahalgam's Baisaran Valley, where militants specifically targeted Hindu tourists and separated victims by religion before killing them, is a grim reminder of how communal tensions continue to disrupt life in Kashmir. Such attacks not only take lives but erode the fragile trust between communities, deepen fear, and cripple the economy.

For many Kashmiris, tourism is a vital source of income. Families who depend on the arrival of tourists — especially from other parts of India — saw their hopes dashed when attacks caused a sharp decline in visitors. Local shopkeepers, guides, and hotel staff suddenly found their livelihoods threatened. One shopkeeper in Pahalgam told me, "When violence erupts, our lives stop. We lose tourists, our income, our access to the world."

The attack also led to immediate cuts in electricity and internet services in the region, worsening the hardships. The internet, which was already restricted for long periods in recent years, was completely shut

off in some places, disrupting education, communication, and business.

Political Suppression and Identity Crisis

The abrogation of Article 370 in 2019, which revoked Jammu and Kashmir's special constitutional status, was seen by many locals as a political betrayal and a move to dilute their distinct identity. It marked a shift toward tighter central control from New Delhi but also fueled a sense of alienation among Kashmiri Muslims, who form the majority in the Kashmir Valley.

Politically, Jammu and Kashmir has seen its elected government sidelined, replaced by administrators appointed by the central government. The local Assembly has remained dissolved for long periods, and recent delimitation exercises have increased political representation from Jammu, which is Hindu-majority, at the perceived expense of Muslim-majority Kashmir. This has deepened fears of marginalization.

Economic promises have fallen short. Despite New Delhi's pledges of investment and development, unemployment remains high, and land laws have been changed to allow non-locals to buy property, stoking anxiety among Kashmiris worried about losing their homeland's ownership.

Civilians are regularly subjected to security checks and random arrests, adding to a pervasive atmosphere of distrust. The constant presence of the Indian army, curfews, and laws like the Public Safety Act have severely restricted freedoms and civil rights. These policies have been criticized by human rights organizations and have fuelled accusations of state-sponsored suppression.

Education and Youth Aspirations: A Generation in Limbo

Perhaps no group in Kashmir feels the burden of conflict more acutely than the youth. With internet access a crucial part of modern education, the internet blackout from 2019 to 2021 was

catastrophic. This shutdown was the longest internet shutdown in any democracy in the world. It brought online classes to a halt, made start-ups collapse, and cut off young people from information and opportunities. Start-ups described the blackout as a "death blow," since "internet is the oxygen for start-ups." One girl from rural Kashmir recounted traveling many kilometres daily just to find a place with internet coverage to attend her online classes.

Unemployment among youth in Kashmir is deeply concerning. As of 2025, the youth unemployment rate is around 17.4%, significantly higher than the national average of 10.2%. Urban women face even steeper challenges, with unemployment nearing 28.6%. Despite government programs like "Mission YUVA," which claims to have created thousands of jobs, many trained youths remain jobless because of lack of access to credit and markets.

Moreover, many young Kashmiris migrate outside the region in search of education and jobs, only to face discrimination and suspicion elsewhere in India. Some are unfairly stereotyped as potential security threats, further alienating them and limiting their integration.

References:

- Internet blackout impact: [Wikipedia](#)
- Youth unemployment: [Tribune India](#)
- Mission YUVA challenges: [JKPI](#)

Healthcare and Mental Health: A System in Crisis

Healthcare infrastructure in Kashmir remains critically inadequate. Many rural health centres suffer from a shortage of doctors and essential specialists. For example, out of 1,677 sanctioned doctor posts in Primary Health Centres, 647 remain vacant. Specialized medical equipment is scarce; the All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS) Kashmir is still incomplete, and there is only one PET scan machine serving the entire region.

Accessing healthcare in harsh winter months becomes an ordeal. Patients sometimes have to walk several kilometres on snowbound paths to reach clinics, as ambulances are unavailable due to blocked roads or power cuts.

Mental health is a growing concern. Studies show that nearly 45% of adults in the Kashmir Valley suffer from mental distress such as depression, anxiety, and PTSD. Yet, there are only about 41 psychiatrists for a population of over 12 million. This massive gap in mental health services leaves many suffering in silence.

References:

- Healthcare shortages: [Rising Kashmir](#)
- Mental health crisis: [AP News](#)
- Healthcare infrastructure: [Greater Kashmir](#)

Women's Struggles: Between Patriarchy and Conflict

Women in Kashmir face a double burden: the societal restrictions of patriarchy compounded by the trauma and instability of conflict. Female literacy in Jammu and Kashmir is about 58%, lagging behind the overall literacy rate of 68.74%. In conservative rural areas, daughters are often undervalued and denied equal access to education and opportunities.

Women's mental health is particularly vulnerable, with many linked suicides over the last two decades tied to conflict trauma, stigma, and lack of support. Sexual violence and abuse are grim realities for many, with an estimated 11.6% of women reporting sexual abuse.

Women who pursue sports, education, or professional careers often face harassment and social backlash, making it difficult for them to break traditional roles.

Reference:

- Women's rights and challenges: [Wikipedia](#)

Substance Abuse: A Silent Epidemic

The lack of opportunities, mental health care, and stability has driven a surge in substance abuse, particularly heroin addiction. Estimates suggest that by 2024, around 1.3 million people in Jammu and Kashmir were drug users, with 95% addicted to heroin. This has created a parallel black economy where drug trade thrives.

Disturbingly, even children as young as ten have become addicted to inhalants, opioids, and hallucinogens. The public health crisis extends beyond addiction; over 70% of injecting drug users test positive for Hepatitis C, posing severe challenges for healthcare providers.

References:

- Drug addiction stats: [Wikipedia](#)
- Youth addiction report: [Reddit](#)

Geopolitical Interests: The Tripolar Struggle for Kashmir

India: Sovereignty and Security

India's approach to Kashmir is shaped by concerns over sovereignty, national security, and territorial integrity. The revocation of Article 370 was an assertion of India's legal claim over the territory but came with consequences that many Kashmiris perceive as suppressive. The heavy military presence – estimated at hundreds of thousands of troops – reflects India's desire to prevent separatism and terrorism but also contributes to everyday hardship and mistrust.

The Indian government's strategy relies on a combination of political integration, economic incentives, and security crackdowns. However, the absence of elected local governments and the use of laws like the Public Safety Act have made governance seem remote and authoritarian.

Pakistan: The Proxy Front

Pakistan has long positioned Kashmir as a core issue of its national identity and foreign policy. It supports militant groups like Lashkar-e-Taiba and Jaish-e-Mohammed, which operate under various names to circumvent bans and international pressure.

The Pakistani Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) has reportedly provided training, funding, and logistical support to these groups, aiming to destabilize Indian-administered Kashmir and internationalize the Kashmir dispute. This proxy war has perpetuated violence, hampering development and peace.

Pakistan also uses diplomatic forums, including the United Nations Security Council, to raise Kashmir as a dispute demanding resolution.

China: Strategic Opportunism

China's stake in Kashmir primarily concerns its border claims and broader geopolitical ambitions. China controls Aksai Chin, a region that India claims as part of Ladakh. After India reorganized Jammu and Kashmir into two Union Territories in 2019, including Ladakh, China protested, asserting this move challenged its sovereignty.

China supports Pakistan's stance on Kashmir, complicating the regional dynamic. Additionally, China's ambitious China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) – a flagship project under its Belt and Road Initiative – runs through Pakistan-administered Kashmir, adding an economic dimension to its geopolitical interests.

China balances its desire to maintain stable ties with India with its support for Pakistan's Kashmir position, making the region a tripolar contest of competing interests.

The Human Cost of a Geopolitical Chessboard

While states and governments manoeuvre for power and territory, the people of Kashmir bear the brunt. Political suppression, violence, unemployment, disrupted education, mental health crises, and social inequalities have created an environment where hope is fragile.

Yet, despite these immense challenges, Kashmiris continue to hold onto their aspirations for dignity, peace, and progress. The resilience of the youth, the persistence of cultural traditions, and the calls for inclusive democracy offer a glimmer of hope in a land weighed down by conflict. Kashmir's story is one of enduring struggle – caught between the fierce geopolitical interests of India, Pakistan, and China, and the simple human desires for safety, prosperity, and identity. The region's development remains hampered by military conflict and political suppression, forcing its people into cycles of fear and frustration. True peace and progress in Jammu and Kashmir can only emerge through genuine dialogue that respects the rights of all communities, political inclusion, and investment in human development – education, healthcare, and employment. For Kashmir to thrive, the world must see beyond the headlines of violence and politics, and listen to the voices of those who live between fear and hope every day. While India presents itself as the world's largest democracy, the experiences of many within its minority communities – particularly Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, Dalits, and tribals – paint a more complex and concerning picture. In recent years, governance has increasingly taken on a centralizing, and often authoritarian, tone, where dissent is suppressed and democratic pluralism appears under strain.

In Jammu and Kashmir, this democratic deficit is even more pronounced. Since the abrogation of Article 370 in 2019, the region has seen its political autonomy dismantled, its civil liberties curtailed, and its population subjected to one of the most intensive surveillance and military presences in the democratic world. These shifts have deepened the sense of

exclusion and fostered a perception that the region's people – particularly Kashmiri Muslims are not equal participants in the national narrative, but rather subjects of suspicion and control. Across India, similar concerns are echoed by other marginalized groups. Muslims face increasing discrimination through legislative changes such as the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA), as well as rising incidents of hate speech, mob lynching, and targeted harassment. Sikhs, still grappling with the historical trauma of the 1984 riots, are often portrayed as extremists when asserting their political or economic rights – such as during the Farmers' Protest, where many were unfairly labelled “anti-national.” Christians, meanwhile, report growing attacks on churches and fear the tightening grip of anti-conversion laws. Dalit and tribal communities continue to experience systemic violence, forced displacement, and limited access to justice, particularly in rural and forested areas.

These patterns suggest a troubling erosion of the secular and inclusive foundations upon which India was built. In Jammu and Kashmir, the effects of these national shifts are amplified by decades of unresolved conflict and mistrust. Governance through force, legal suppression, or demographic engineering cannot bring peace to a region that has long demanded dignity, representation, and dialogue. And yet, despite these profound challenges, there remains a quiet resilience among the people of Kashmir. Their strength lies not in violent resistance but in endurance—students walking miles for internet access, women leading households amid loss, and communities that continue to celebrate their cultural heritage even in the shadow of occupation. These stories are not just of survival, but of a deep yearning for justice and equality.

If Kashmir is to have a future beyond conflict, it must begin with an honest reckoning—with its history, with its people, and with the promises of the Indian Constitution. Restoring democratic institutions, protecting human rights, and investing in development that reflects the will of the local

population are not acts of generosity, but of justice. The path to peace lies not in the further militarization of the region or the silencing of dissent, but in genuine, inclusive dialogue that prioritizes humanity over territory. Only then can Kashmir move from a landscape of fear and repression to one of hope, dignity, and shared progress.

** Jasmeen Kaur is a Senior Fellow at SIGA and graduate student at the University of Basel, Switzerland.*

7. Strategic Outlook on Indian Defence and Security

Establishment

*Rajganna Kannanathan and Dr. Remo Reginold**

India's emergence as a global power is constrained by a complex security environment shaped by historical and geopolitical factors. The primary obstacle is the strategic alliance between China and Pakistan, which has forced India to reallocate resources from development to defence. Energy security and maritime dominance have become crucial elements of India's defence strategy as its economy grows increasingly dependent on external resources. China's expanding naval presence in the Indian Ocean endangers India's control over key shipping routes. India's security approach involves balancing continental defence with naval modernisation amidst regional rivalries and global energy competition.

India's defence and national security framework has undergone a major transformation over the past twenty years, reflecting the nation's emergence as a key Indo-Pacific power and its exposure to increasingly complex security threats. Traditionally centred on the Ministry of Defence and the individual service headquarters, India's security system has evolved into a more integrated, politically guided, and multi-domain structure. This change has been driven by recognising that India faces a highly dense threat landscape – ranging from ongoing border clashes with nuclear-armed adversaries to internal insurgencies, cyber intrusions, maritime vulnerabilities, and the rapid militarisation of emerging technologies. As a result, New Delhi has sought to develop a framework capable of coordinating political leadership, military planning, intelligence integration, and inter-ministerial cooperation in ways that older, ministry-centric models could not.

The establishment and subsequent strengthening of the National Security Council (NSC) and its Secretariat mark a pivotal moment in this institutional development. Situated within the Prime Minister's Office and led by the National Security Advisor (NSA), this organizational shift has become the key centre where strategic assessments, operational planning, and intelligence gathering converge. Reforms such as appointing specialised Deputy NSAs, expanding the NSCS, and creating new coordinating roles – like the National Cybersecurity Coordinator and the National Maritime Security Coordinator – reflect a deliberate move towards a more unified, vertically integrated security decision-making process. Parallel progress in defence, particularly the creation of the Chief of Defence Staff (CDS) and the ongoing development of Integrated Theatre Commands, showcase India's goal to achieve genuine jointness across land, maritime, air, cyber, and space domains.

These institutional shifts reveal a deeper strategic logic: India is working to transition from a reactive, fragmented security approach to a proactive, unified national security system capable of addressing multiple threats across different domains simultaneously. This reflects and can be read as a response to China's Active Defence strategy.

This paper examines India's evolving defence and national security framework, considering its strategic priorities, organisational reforms, and the centralisation of authority under the NSC and the NSA. By analysing key structural changes – from intelligence integration to theatre command reforms – it assesses how India aims to align its political, military, and technological capabilities with the demands of a complex strategic environment and geopolitical volatility.

Evolution of Indian Defence and Security Architecture

India's post-independence security system initially relied on inherited British structures, with the Joint

Intelligence Committee (JIC) under the Chiefs of Staff Committee serving as the main body synthesising intelligence for political leaders. Although its remit gradually expanded to cover internal and external threats, decision-making remained reactive and fragmented, driven mostly by short-term law-and-order concerns rather than long-term strategic planning. Earlier experiments—such as ad hoc multidisciplinary groups in the late 1980s and the first National Security Council (NSC) convened in 1990 – proved short-lived³⁹. This led to the more permanent 1999 reconstitution, which established the NSC, the Strategic Policy Group (SPG), the National Security Advisory Board (NSAB), and the NSC Secretariat (NSCS) to systematically integrate intelligence, military and policy inputs⁴⁰.

The 1999 Kargil conflict exposed significant weaknesses in intelligence coordination, civil–military integration, and technological preparedness, prompting the Kargil Review Committee (KRC) and a subsequent Group of Ministers (GoM) to recommend wide-ranging reforms. These suggestions led to the creation of several new bodies: the Intelligence Coordination Group (ICG), the Technology Coordination Group (TCG), and the National Technical Research Organisation (NTRO), alongside improved multi-agency intelligence sharing via the MAC/SMAC network and data-driven tools like the Financial Intelligence Unit (FIU) and NATGRID⁴¹. Collectively, these reforms marked India's first comprehensive, whole-of-government approach to national security, replacing fragmented institutional responses with a more integrated system.

Reform momentum continued into the early 2000s with progress in higher defence management and nuclear command-and-control. Although the GoM's key recommendation – the creation of a Chief of Defence Staff (CDS) – was not achieved at that time, other structural changes were implemented: the

Defence Intelligence Agency (DIA) was established, service headquarters were progressively integrated with the Ministry of Defence, and the Strategic Forces Command (SFC) and Nuclear Command Authority (NCA) were formalised, clarifying both political control and operational responsibilities⁴². Efforts to improve economic intelligence and enable real-time intelligence sharing with law enforcement agencies also moved forward, though ongoing civil–military tensions and incomplete inter-service coordination limited the full impact of these reforms. A subsequent wave of restructuring in 2017–18 responded to technological disruptions and evolving security threats, expanding the NSCS into specialised sectors, placing the SPG formally under the National Security Advisor (NSA), and setting up the Defence Planning Committee (DPC) to coordinate strategy, capability development, and defence industrial policy⁴³. Despite these efforts, challenges related to talent, interagency turf boundaries, and unresolved higher defence reforms persisted.

We can summarise major institutional developments as follows:

- Early post-independence structures
- 1999 NSC reforms
- Post-Kargil reforms (GoM / KRC)
- Early-2000s higher-defence reforms
- 2017–18 NSCS expansion and DPC creation

³⁹ P. S. Raghavan, "The Evolution of India's National Security Architecture," *Journal of Defence Studies* 13, no. 3 (2019): 34–35.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 35.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, 36–38.

⁴² *Ibid.*, 39–41.

⁴³ *Ibid.*, 40.

Figure 1: Institutional Evolution of India's Defence and Security Architecture from 1948 until 2018 (AI-generated)

Institutional Implications of Operation Sindoor

Recent counter-terror operations exemplify this integrated approach in practice. Following the April 22, 2025, Pahalgam attack, India launched Operation Sindoor, a series of precision strikes deep within Pakistani territory that dismantled vital terror infrastructure. The operation showcased Ajit Doval's "Defensive Offence" doctrine – preemptive targeting and decisive retaliation below nuclear thresholds – supported by meticulous intelligence gathering⁴⁴.

Institutionally, Operation Sindoor demonstrated the NSCS's enhanced ability to unite groups and highlighted the NSA's role in inter-agency

⁴⁴ Aritra Banerjee, "NSA Ajit Doval: Architect of India's Decisive Anti-Terror Mechanism," *Awaz-The Voice*, May 16, 2025, <https://www.awazthevoice.in/india-news/nsa-ajit-doval-architect-of-india-s-decisive-anti-terror-mechanism-37668.html>.

⁴⁵ Pallab Bhattacharyya, "Ajit Doval: The architecture of India's modern security doctrine" *Awaz-The Voice*, May 13, 2025.

coordination. Post-strike developments indicate a maturing system that combines operational precision with multi-domain situational awareness across the kinetic, cyber, space, and information domains, along with rapid policy alignment. The operation also emphasised India's trajectory towards Atmanirbhar Bharat (cf. self-reliant India, a campaign under Modi's leadership) in defence. Indigenous systems like Akash and BrahMos were used alongside imported platforms such as the Russian S-400 and French smart bombs, including Hammer, SCALP, and Storm Shadow, produced by the European Consortium MBDA, showcasing a practical mix of capabilities while signalling increasing self-reliance⁴⁵. These results align with the broader programme of reforms aimed at synchronising industrial policy, capability development, and strategic autonomy.

In the wake of Pahalgam, the government revamped the National Security Advisory Board (NSAB), appointing former R&AW chief Alok Joshi as chairman and inducting a multidisciplinary slate of 14 experts from the military, police, diplomacy, and technology domains⁴⁶. The reconstitution highlights a renewed focus on long-term assessment, intelligence coordination, and breaking agency silos—areas Joshi has publicly identified as vital to outcomes, given his previous leadership of Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW) and National Technical Research Organisation (NTRO). Located within the NSC system, the strengthened NSAB aims to provide strategic analysis and options to the political leadership, complementing the NSCS/DPC framework and the operational lessons from Sindoor.

India's revamped national security architecture

India's revamped national security structure revolves around a powerful, centralised National Security Council Secretariat (NSCS) led by National Security Adviser Ajit Doval, bringing together intelligence,

<https://www.awazthevoice.in/opinion-news/ajit-doval-the-architect-of-india-s-modern-security-doctrine-37608.html>.

⁴⁶ Bharti Jain, "Former R&AW Chief to Head Revamped National Security Advisory Board," *Times of India*, May 1, 2025. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/former-raw-chief-to-head-revamped-national-security-advisory-board/articleshow/120776092.cms>.

diplomacy, and strategic planning under one umbrella.

The NSCS has transformed from a modest advisory body into a vital operational centre for India's security strategy. Under its leadership, Ajit Doval has redefined the NSA's role into a proactive position of leadership, coordinating efforts across ministries and agencies. The structure now includes several Deputy NSAs from the Indian Foreign Service, Intelligence Bureau, and Indian Police Service, each overseeing specific areas such as foreign affairs, internal security, and intelligence. Additionally, Rajinder Khanna, the former R&AW chief, serves as Additional NSA, concentrating on external intelligence and counter-terrorism⁴⁷. This layered leadership ensures that India's security decisions are guided by diverse expertise and real-time intelligence.

A major change in the architecture is the "securitisation" of economic and technological sectors. India's National Security Council (NSC) serves as the principal strategic advisory body, integrating political, military, intelligence, and technological dimensions into a single platform. Chaired by the Prime Minister, the NSC includes the Defence, Home, External Affairs, and Finance Ministers, reflecting its cross-cutting importance in national decision-making. Its structure is tripartite, composed of the Strategic Policy Group (SPG), the National Security Advisory Board (NSAB), and the National Security Council Secretariat (NSCS). The NSC's design is explicitly intended to facilitate coordination across ministries and agencies while enabling coherent formulation of a long-term national security strategy⁴⁸.

India is developing a formal national security strategy that formalises this integrated approach. The framework is distinctly Indian – shaped by the personalities of its leaders and the geopolitical realities of South Asia. Under Doval, the system has

become more anticipatory and centralised, shifting from reactive crisis management towards strategic foresight. This change positions India to handle complex global challenges with agility and coherence, ensuring its security apparatus is both resilient and prepared for the future.

Operationally, the NSCS – headed by the National Security Advisor (NSA) – manages multiple "verticals" to respond to diverse threat domains. These verticals typically include Strategic Planning, Internal Affairs, Technology & Intelligence, and Military Affairs. The NSA oversees this structure and is supported by several Deputy NSAs, a Military Adviser, and a National Maritime Security Coordinator. Meanwhile, the SPG provides an interagency forum for key officials: its members include the Chief of Defence Staff (CDS), the three Service Chiefs, the Directors of IB (Intelligence Bureau) and R&AW (Research & Analysis Wing), and senior secretaries such as Home, Defence, Foreign Affairs, and Finance⁵. In parallel, the NSAB draws on experts from outside the government – retired officials, academics, strategists – to provide independent, long-term recommendations on national security issues.

India's Revamped National Security Architecture, which captures the full hierarchy and key roles across the Cabinet Committee on Security, National Security Council, and specialised coordinators and advisers.

- **Prime Minister Narendra Modi** at the top
- **Cabinet Committee on Security (CCS)** with the ministries of Home, Defence, Finance, and External Affairs
- **National Security Council** feeding into the **National Security Adviser (Ajit Doval)**
- Under Doval:

⁴⁷ India's NSCS. "From Small Beginnings to Shaping National Security." 19:45, 5.07.2024, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2v3N8OsRoHc&t=108s>

⁴⁸ Nitin A. Gokhale, "Major Revamp of India's National Security Architecture," *Bharat Shakti*, October 9, 2018, <https://bharatshakti.in/major-revamp-of-indias-national-security-architecture/>.

- **National Security Advisory Board (NSAB)**
- **National Intelligence Board (NIB)**
- **Threat Coordination Group (TCG)**
- **Deputy NSAs:**
 - **Pankaj Kumar Singh** – Policy Planning, Counter Terrorism, Border Infrastructure, J&K, Northeast, Chinese military assessment
 - **Vikram Misri** – International Affairs, Maritime Issues
 - **Rajinder Khanna** – Cyber Security, ISRO, Future Technology (Civil)
- **Military Adviser** – Strategy, Net Assessment, Neighbourhood, Future Technology (Military)
- **National Maritime Security Coordinator** – VADM G Ashok Kumar (Retd)
- **Strategic Policy Group**, chaired by the Cabinet Secretary, includes CDS, Service Chiefs, Secretaries of Defence, Home, Foreign Affairs, and others.

Flow of Decision Making

1. Intelligence Collection

- Agencies like the **Intelligence Bureau (IB)** and **Research & Analysis Wing (RAW)** gather information on internal and external threats.

- Military intelligence and specialised units contribute battlefield and strategic inputs.

2. Assessment & Coordination

- Reports are funnelled into the **National Security Council Secretariat (NSCS)**.
- The **National Security Adviser (NSA)** synthesises intelligence, defence, and diplomatic perspectives.
- Inter-ministerial groups (Defence, Home, and External Affairs) provide policy inputs.

3. Strategic Advisory Layer

- The **National Security Advisory Board (NSAB)**, composed of experts and former officials, offers independent analysis and long-term recommendations.
- Specialised task forces within NSCS address emerging domains like cybersecurity, maritime security, and energy security.

4. Decision-Making

- The NSA presents consolidated assessments directly to the **Prime Minister** and the Cabinet Committee on Security (CCS).
- The CCS, chaired by the Prime Minister, makes final decisions on defence, foreign policy, and crisis management.

5. Implementation & External Engagement

- Ministries and armed forces execute decisions.
- The NSA represents India in **international forums** (e.g.,

SCO, Colombo Security Conclave), ensuring external diplomacy aligns with internal security priorities.

Figure 4: Strategic Policy Group (SPG) guided by NSA

Figure 2: Current Security Architecture (Nitin A.Gokhale, Strategic News International)

Figure 5: Intelligence Architecture guided by NSA

Figure 6: Chief of Defence Staff Architecture

Breakdown of the Hierarchical view of Indian National Security Architecture as of 2024 August

Figure 3: Hierarchical View of India's Security Architecture

The Role of Indian National Security Advisor Ajit Doval

Ajit Doval's recent engagements with China and Russia underscore the evolving role of India's National Security Advisor (NSA) as a central figure in shaping foreign and security policy. His meetings in Beijing with Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi and Russian Security Council officials highlight how the NSA position has moved beyond intelligence coordination into high-level diplomacy⁴⁹.

The role of the NSA, as evidenced in Doval's career, has grown from its initial focus on intelligence and internal security to becoming a key architect of India's foreign policy. His background in covert operations, Kashmir policy, and his connections to institutions such as the Vivekananda Foundation influenced his ideological perspective⁵⁰. These experiences have positioned him to manage security sensitive issues, including the Doklam standoff, surgical strikes, and India's broader strategic stance in South Asia. His recent dialogues with China reflect efforts to stabilise strained relations after the Galwan clash. At the same time, his visit to Russia signals

⁴⁹ "Ajit Doval Meets Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi in Beijing," *The Hindu*, July 2024.

⁵⁰ Praveen Donthi, "Ajit Doval in Theory and Practice," *The Caravan*, 2017, <https://caravanmagazine.in/reportage/ajit-doval-theory-practice>

India's balancing act amid the Ukraine conflict and shifting global alignments⁵¹.

Border tensions with China, terrorism concerns, and the need to retain strategic autonomy while engaging with Russia, despite Western pressures, constitute a strategic complexity for India's defence and security policy. Doval's meetings within the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) framework and the Colombo Security Conclave illustrate how the NSA now functions as India's primary representative in multilateral security forums⁵². This shift reflects both the personalisation of national security under Prime Minister Modi and the institutional strengthening of the NSA's office. In practice, Doval exemplifies the fusion of intelligence, diplomacy, and ideology—making the NSA not merely a security adviser but a key strategist in India's foreign policy planning.

- **National Security Council Secretariat (NSCS):** Expanded with three Deputy NSAs:
 - External & Technical Intelligence
 - Diplomatic Affairs
 - Internal Security
- **Strategic Policy Group (SPG):** Includes service chiefs, intelligence heads, and senior secretaries.
- **Defence Planning Committee (DPC):** Focused on long-term defence strategy.
- **Centre for Contemporary China Studies (CCCS):** Specialised think tank for China-related analysis.
- **Tri-Service Agencies:** Joint structures for Cyber, Space, and Special Operations.

Key Role of NSA in India's Security and Defence Architecture

Figure 7: NSA Actor-Network

Key Components in the Diagram

- **National Security Adviser (NSA):** Central authority overseeing all major security bodies.

Evolving India's National Security Strategy

India's evolving national security doctrine emphasises decisive deterrence, strategic autonomy, and integrated power projection across military, economic, and technological domains. Its approach has significantly transformed in recent years, shifting from strategic restraint to assertive deterrence. This change is exemplified by the 3-Pillar Doctrine unveiled in 2025, which includes: (1) Decisive Retaliation, (2) Zero Tolerance for Nuclear Blackmail, and (3) Strategic Autonomy⁵³. The doctrine affirms India's right to respond to threats – particularly cross-border terrorism – at a time and place of its choosing, as demonstrated in operations like the 2016 surgical strikes, the 2019 Balakot airstrike, and Operation Sindoor in 2025. It also rejects nuclear threats as a shield for proxy warfare,

⁵¹ "NSA Ajit Doval Holds Talks with Russian Security Council Secretary," *Indian Express*, August 2024.

⁵² "SCO Summit in China: Ajit Doval Urges Nations to 'Shun Double Standards Against Terrorism'; Pitches for 'Joint Information Operation,'" *Times of India*, June 24, 2025, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/sco-summit-in-china->

<ajit-doval-urges-nations-to-shun-double-standards-against-terrorism-pitches-for-joint-information-operation/articleshow/122047846>.

⁵³ "India's 3-Pillar National Security Doctrine: Decisive Retaliation and Zero Tolerance," *Insights on India*, May 16, 2025, <https://www.insightsonindia.com/2025/05/16/indias-3-pillar-doctrine/>.

maintaining a No First Use policy while introducing calibrated ambiguity to deter adversaries.

The doctrine combines military readiness with economic resilience and technological progress. Chief of Defence Staff General Anil Chauhan's three-tier structure describes concentric circles of strategic engagement: the outer layer concentrates on securing missions through diplomacy and economic strength; the middle layer focuses on defending the mission with military readiness and intelligence coordination; and the innermost layer guarantees operational preparedness through joint command structures and rapid response capabilities⁵⁴. This model shows India's understanding that national security now extends beyond traditional warfare to include cyber threats, supply chain issues, and energy security.

India's strategic autonomy remains a key part of its doctrine, especially given the increasing global polarisation. The doctrine also covers India's Middle East strategy, where initiatives like the India-Middle East-Europe Corridor (IMEC) seek to counter China's Belt and Road Initiative and secure maritime routes essential for energy and trade⁵⁵. Overall, these elements combine to form a doctrine that is proactive, multi-faceted, and suited to India's geopolitical realities.

Dr. Anil Kumar Lal, who was the Commanding General in the Ladakh/Siachen Conflict area and an expert on Himalayan security architecture, space security, military transformation, and strategic deterrence, asserts that India is approaching a critical strategic turning point characterised by what he describes as a G2 duopoly⁵⁶: a world increasingly dominated by the United States and China. He warns that in such an environment, India's traditional hedging strategy is becoming unsustainable as major powers seek clearer alliances. Lal argues that

China's expanding technological coercion, forward military deployments, and strategic infiltration into India's neighbourhood – combined with economic leverage and debt diplomacy – have limited India's strategic options⁵⁷. His analysis emphasises that India can no longer afford reactive policies; instead, it must adopt a proactive, power-balancing stance centred on deterrence, self-reliance, and diverse partnerships.

To operationalise this shift, Lal advocates for the adoption of a formal National Security Strategy (NSS) — a structured, long-term blueprint to coordinate India's strategic outlook⁵⁸. He criticises India's current approach as fragmented and short-sighted, noting that despite its global significance, India lacks a codified doctrine to steer its rising power trajectory. According to Lal, an NSS would anchor India's diplomacy, capability development, and deterrence policy around a coherent vision. By integrating its 10-year defence framework with partners like the U.S. and Russia into a broader strategic architecture, the NSS would enable India to pursue balanced power projection without compromising its sovereignty or strategic autonomy.

Network and Theatre Centric Warfare

India's modern military transformation is increasingly influenced by the shift towards network-centric warfare, where real-time data integration, surveillance systems, and digital connectivity aim to establish a shared operational picture across services. As contemporary conflicts require the fusion of sensors, shooters, and decision-makers into a unified information grid, enabling forces to operate more quickly, accurately, and independently has become crucial for the armed forces⁵⁹. This

⁵⁴ "CDS Outlines Three-Tier National Security Architecture Through 'Ops Sindoor'," *Indian Defence News*, November 17, 2025. <https://www.indiandefensenews.in/2025/11/cds-outlines-three-tier-national.html>

⁵⁵ Talmiz Ahmad and John Calabrese, "IMEC and India's Middle East Doctrine," *The Diplomat*, November 19, 2025. <https://thediplomat.com/2025/11/imec-and-indias-middle-east-doctrine/>

⁵⁶ Anil Kumar Lal, "India's Strategic Autonomy in a G2 Era: The Urgent Need for a National Security Strategy," *The Times of India*, November 12, 2025. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/rakshakindia/indias-strategic-autonomy-in-a-g2-era-the-urgent-need-for-a-national-security-strategy/>

⁵⁷ Lal, "India's Strategic Autonomy in a G2 Era."

⁵⁸ Lal, "India's Strategic Autonomy in a G2 Era."

⁵⁹ Ayesha Ray, "The Indian Army," in *Institutional Roots of India's Security Policy*, ed. Milan Vaishnav (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024), 48-49.

development supports India's move towards theatre warfare, where integrated theatre commands would replace service-specific silos and facilitate unified planning, logistics, and operations across land, maritime, air, cyber, and space domains⁶⁰. These changes are grounded in India's evolving doctrinal emphasis on jointness, multi-domain operations, and information dominance, representing a clear shift from platform-focused strategies to a comprehensive, technology-driven warfighting model tailored for future high-intensity, information-centric conflicts.

Network-centric and information-centric warfare have become central to India's evolving military doctrine as the armed forces shift towards integrated, multi-domain operations. The Indian Navy's transformation – driven strongly by U.S. influence since the 1990s – reflects a broader national move towards **network-enabled battlespaces**, where interoperable doctrines, data-driven situational awareness, and real-time intelligence sharing form the foundation of warfighting. Bhardwaj notes that Indo-U.S. cooperation has focused explicitly on “developing interoperable doctrines and technology-driven networks,” including systems that link maritime domain awareness platforms and fusion centres across services⁶¹. This emphasis dovetails with India's growing investment in information warfare, where space-based assets like the Rukmani satellite, naval fusion centres, and cyber capabilities allow India to achieve “battle space transparency” and enhance distributed operations⁶². Parallel to these shifts, India's move towards theatre warfare – seen in the creation of joint theatre commands – aims to break down service silos and unify operations under integrated commands capable of synchronising land, air, maritime, cyber, and space assets. The Indian Navy's future maritime theatre command at Karwar exemplifies this doctrinal shift, placing naval, air, and amphibious forces under unified operational control⁶³. Doctrinally, India continues to debate the balance between **sea**

control and **sea denial**, as well as the utility of a “balanced fleet,” but all of these debates are increasingly shaped by network-centric concepts and information-dominant operations that underpin modern joint and theatre warfare⁶⁴.

India's defence and security architecture has developed from a fragmented, reactive system into a centralised, multi-domain framework designed to meet the demands of a complex strategic environment. By institutionalising reforms such as the National Security Council Secretariat, Integrated Theatre Commands, and the Chief of Defence Staff, India has demonstrated a clear shift towards jointness, technological integration, and anticipatory planning. Coupled with doctrines like decisive deterrence and strategic autonomy, these changes position India to safeguard its sovereignty while projecting power across continental and maritime domains. However, sustaining this trajectory will require codifying a formal National Security Strategy, deepening indigenous capability development, and maintaining agility in the face of emerging threats – from cyber warfare to geopolitical realignments. In essence, India stands at a critical juncture where proactive, coherent, and future-ready security policies will define its role as a leading Indo-Pacific power.

** Rajanna Kannanathan is Head of the SIGA South Asia Desk and a graduate student at King's College, London*

Dr. Remo Reginold is President of SIGA. His research focuses on the geopolitics of knowledge and the international politics of South Asia

⁶⁰ Ibid., 49.

⁶¹ Atul Bhardwaj, “The Indian Navy,” in *Institutional Roots of India's Security Policy*, ed. Milan Vaishnav (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024), 57.

⁶² Ibid., 63-64

⁶³ Ibid., 61.

⁶⁴ Ibid., 59-60.

8. Indian Intelligence Culture: A Strategic Outlook

Rajganna Kannanthan

An analysis of Intelligence culture examines the historically rooted norms, institutional practices, strategic culture, and political attitudes that shape how a state perceives, organises, and utilises intelligence⁶⁵. It is not just the structure of agencies or the threats they face, but the deep-seated worldview that influences how intelligence is gathered, analysed, shared, and acted upon. As scholars note, intelligence culture reflects the “patterns of assumptions” that guide a nation’s security bureaucracy and political leadership, impacting expectations around secrecy, civilian oversight, risk tolerance, and the moral boundaries of espionage⁶⁶. Recognising this cultural aspect is essential because intelligence systems are not universal; they are socially constructed products of national history, trauma, and political motivation⁶⁷. Intelligence systems are not just bureaucratic tools; they are embedded within broader social and political cultures that shape risk appetite, secrecy norms, civil–military relations, oversight mechanisms, and the perceived legitimacy of intelligence activities⁶⁸. In this perspective, intelligence culture acts as an interpretive lens – helping to understand why states facing similar threats often develop markedly different intelligence institutions and methods. It encompasses three interconnected dimensions: historical heritage, institutional structures and bureaucratic norms, and political–strategic expectations of the elites who guide intelligence agencies⁶⁹. In the Indian context, this paper examines the Indian intelligence culture in the backdrop of its historical evolution, socio-political culture, strategic threat perception, and current

transformation from a circumspect position to a strategically proactive operational position.

Indian intelligence culture is best understood as a product of layered historical sedimentation. The bureaucratic and operational heritage of British colonial rule significantly influenced India’s post-independence intelligence culture. First, the colonial state established a culture of internal surveillance, political policing, and secrecy, prioritising regime stability over strategic intelligence – a pattern that continued after 1947⁷⁰. This colonial legacy created an intelligence system that excelled at surveillance but lacked strategic analysis, with a strong focus on monitoring internal dissent rather than external threats. Second, post-independence nation-building reinforced a culture centred on the executive, in which intelligence agencies, especially the Intelligence Bureau (IB), served as tools of political authority rather than independent analytical bodies⁷¹. The absence of a legislative framework and weak parliamentary oversight further normalised informal practices, personal access, and limited accountability⁷². Third, India’s geopolitical landscape, marked by ongoing internal insurgencies, hostile intelligence agencies in neighbouring countries, and episodic wars with China and Pakistan, fostered an operational, security-driven culture that often compromised long-term analytical capacity. As scholars contend, these three threads established an “internal security–first” intelligence culture that emphasises collection over analysis, secrecy over institutional learning, and executive trust over independent assessment⁷³. Recognising these cultural patterns is crucial for understanding India’s current intelligence challenges and designing reforms suited to its political and strategic environment.

⁶⁵ Peter Gill, “Theories of Intelligence,” in *The Oxford Handbook of National Security Intelligence*, ed. Loch K. Johnson (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 47–48.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, 43–58.

⁶⁷ Christopher Andrew, *Secret World: A History of Intelligence* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2018), 5–7.

⁶⁸ Gill Peter, Theories of Intelligence, 47–49

⁶⁹ Michael Herman, *Intelligence Power in Peace and War* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996), 30–35.

⁷⁰ Praveen Swami, *India, Pakistan and the Secret Jihad* (London: Routledge, 2009), 22–26.

⁷¹ *Ibid.*

⁷² C. A. Bayly, *Empire and Information: Intelligence Gathering and Social Communication in India, 1780–1870* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996), 112–18.

⁷³ N. N. Vohra, *Safeguarding India* (New Delhi: HarperCollins, 2016), 55–61.

Post-independence, India's intelligence culture evolved through crises that both revealed institutional weaknesses and reinforced existing traits. India's most significant intelligence failure occurred in the 1962 war with China, when the IB lacked both the collection and analytical skills necessary to challenge flawed political assumptions about Chinese intentions, leading to India's strategic shock⁷⁴. This setback prompted the government to establish the Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW) in 1968, marking India's first major structural reform in intelligence. In the following decades, a culture of political intelligence gathering and executive dependence took root, especially during the 1975–77 Emergency, when the IB became a tool for internal political surveillance, reinforcing an executive-centric intelligence culture⁷⁵. Although the IB achieved considerable operational successes in counterinsurgency and counterterrorism, persistent understaffing, limited training, and the lack of analytical capacity hindered the development of a modern intelligence culture focused on long-term assessment⁷⁶.

Since its inception, the Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW) has relied on a system in which personal trust, executive control, and institutional secrecy have traditionally taken precedence over formal bureaucratic structures. R&AW was established in 1968 through an executive order and deliberately placed directly under the Prime Minister's Office, fostering a culture where individual relationships with political leaders were more critical than procedural norms or legislative oversight⁷⁷. The agency was intentionally designed to bypass standard bureaucratic constraints, reinforcing a tradition of secrecy and limited external accountability⁷⁸. This arrangement cultivated an intelligence culture characterised by personalised authority, minimal transparency, and a predominantly executive-

focused ethos. It also led to a lack of consistent accountability mechanisms, resulting in limited institutional learning and allowing silo mentalities and bureaucratic turf wars to persist.

For decades, mistrust and rivalry between R&AW and the Intelligence Bureau (IB) have hampered information sharing, a problem that dates back to R&AW's founding and endures in subsequent reviews⁷⁹. The Kargil Review Committee and later reports identified weak Human Intelligence (HUMINT) capabilities, poor inter-agency coordination, and limited technological capacity as key structural flaws⁸⁰. These issues persist because India's intelligence reforms have mainly been crisis-driven – reacting to failures rather than grounded in long-term strategic analysis⁸¹.

Despite institutional opacity, R&AW achieved several key milestones that demonstrated the adaptive and operational strengths of India's intelligence system. R&AW's early leadership built a "multi-disciplinary" organisation that separated analysis from operations, drawing lessons from Western agencies and enhancing India's external intelligence capabilities⁸². Significant achievements included R&AW's involvement in India's major foreign policy actions, especially its role in regional operations spanning Bangladesh (1971) to Afghanistan and Pakistan during the 1980s and 1990s. The introduction of specialised desks, such as Counter Intelligence Teams X and J, marked an expansion of operational sophistication aimed at shaping Pakistan's cost calculus⁸³. Later milestones, particularly the creation of the National Security Council Secretariat in 1998 and the post-Kargil restructuring, formalised coordination channels and introduced new layers of political and strategic oversight⁸⁴. These developments show how India's

⁷⁴ Praveen Swami, "The Intelligence Bureau," in *Institutional Roots of India's Security Policy*, ed. Milan Vaishnav (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024), 139.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*, 140.

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*, 145–147.

⁷⁷ Shreyas Shende and Rudra Chaudhuri, "The Research and Analysis Wing," in *Institutional Roots of India's Security Policy*, ed. Milan Vaishnav (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024), 112–13.

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*, 114.

⁷⁹ *Ibid.*, 127–128.

⁸⁰ *Ibid.*, 121.

⁸¹ *Ibid.*, 127.

⁸² *Ibid.*, 113.

⁸³ *Ibid.*, 118.

⁸⁴ *Ibid.*, 120.

intelligence apparatus periodically modernised in response to geopolitical shocks.

After 1947, independent India largely kept the institutional framework and internal security mindset of the British Intelligence Bureau (IB). This led to what scholars describe as an intelligence culture “shaped by fear and anxiety,” focused on sedition, communist subversion, and communal unrest⁸⁵. Instead of overhauling personnel or reforming mission priorities, India’s political leadership continued to see the IB mainly as a domestic political safety valve. This continuity also influenced the creation of R&AW in 1968. Despite ambitions for a foreign intelligence agency, its bureaucratic ethos was formed by the same elite continuities and colonial logics that previously limited the IB. P. N. Haksar, one of R&AW’s architects, lamented that independence had “continued elite domination” without dismantling colonial intelligence systems⁸⁶. Nehru himself was concerned that India’s intelligence services had become overly reliant on British reporting, functioning almost as an “annexure” of London’s services⁸⁷.

A potent blend of geopolitical suspicion and strategic independence shaped India’s intelligence culture during the early Cold War. U.S. deep mistrust, ideological differences, and misaligned strategic priorities marked India’s intelligence cooperation during that period. American and British covert efforts in the developing world, such as interventions in Iran, Guatemala, and Chile, fostered lasting Indian fears of Western neo-colonialism, enabling political actors to weaponise the CIA as a symbol of external interference⁸⁸. The Indian press and political culture heightened these anxieties, often reinforcing narratives of a “foreign hand” manipulating domestic politics⁸⁹. Simultaneously, the United States viewed India as a difficult intelligence partner. Despite moments of close cooperation, particularly in the 1960s, U.S. officials repeatedly misunderstood

India’s sensitivity to sovereignty and its non-aligned stance. Attempts to influence domestic opinion or to use covert actions in India’s favour almost always proved counterproductive, undermining trust and adding to long-term strategic friction⁹⁰.

During the Cold War, India became an unexpected global hub for defections and asylum politics, placing New Delhi at the crossroads of superpower rivalry. Dozens of Soviet citizens, ranging from sailors to engineers, used India as a “jumping-off point” to seek refuge in the West, including high-profile defectors such as Yuri Bezemenov (1970) and Stalin’s daughter Svetlana Alliluyeva (1967)⁹¹. These incidents strained India’s diplomacy; each defection risked upsetting the fragile balance between American goodwill and India’s increasingly close ties with Moscow⁹². Indian officials tried to limit the granting of asylum to avoid diplomatic fallout. By the early 1960s, India had become a significant centre for Soviet intelligence activities. Key KGB leaders, including Shelepin, Semichastny, and Andropov, viewed India as vital to Moscow’s efforts to promote wars of national liberation and to oppose Western influence in the Global South⁹³. India capitalised on Soviet concerns to strengthen its own strategic independence, balancing Moscow, Washington, and London while pursuing its national interests. Nonetheless, the extent of Soviet intelligence presence also heightened Indian sensitivity to CIA operations, fostering a political culture where foreign intelligence was perceived as an ever-present threat. The Indian government found itself caught between its commitments to liberal asylum norms and the needs of nonalignment, ultimately recognising that Cold War defections were a geopolitical issue without a straightforward solution.

Newly declassified Kennedy assassination files provide unprecedented insights into the scope and nature of CIA activities in India during the Cold War, exposing extensive covert operations from election

⁸⁵ Paul M. McGarr, *Spying in South Asia: Britain, the United States, and India’s Secret Cold War* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2024), 30.

⁸⁶ *Ibid.*, 30.

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*, 4.

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*, 11.

⁸⁹ *Ibid.*, 260.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*, 262.

⁹¹ *Ibid.*, 179-180.

⁹² *Ibid.*, 154.

⁹³ *Ibid.*, 106.

interference and political manipulation to intelligence collection through diplomatic, commercial, and consular networks. It reveals that American diplomats frequently regarded the CIA's presence in India as excessive and counterproductive. Simultaneously, the CIA aimed to conceal its footprint due to India's sensitivity over sovereignty. The documents also illuminate CIA–MI6 cooperation, paramilitary aid to India after the 1962 war, and U-2 overflight negotiations, demonstrating how South Asia became a vital arena for U.S. intelligence efforts beyond the Anglosphere⁹⁴.

India's modern intelligence challenges continue to be connected to the Cold War era. The country has long faced threats from Pakistan, communal and ideological extremism, and China's strategic ambitions; forces that "threatened the integrity of the Indian Union" over many decades⁹⁵. In the 21st century, however, India's intelligence stance has shifted. Under the Modi government, longstanding restrictions on covert action have been relaxed, allowing R&AW and special forces to undertake operations from the 2016 cross-LoC strikes to external counterinsurgency missions in Myanmar.⁵ Yet this heightened activity involves significant strategic risks given India's two nuclear-armed adversaries. The absence of robust oversight mechanisms means intelligence agencies remain vulnerable to "calamitous missteps," much as in earlier periods when intelligence distortions worsened crises rather than resolving them.⁶ India's intelligence culture, rooted in colonial-era internal security, has evolved into a hybrid model that balances sovereignty with pragmatic foreign cooperation. While Cold War interventions by Western agencies often destabilised regional politics, they also accelerated India's modernisation of intelligence capabilities. Today, the ongoing

tension between secrecy, accountability, and strategic needs continues to shape India's approach to intelligence reform and covert operations⁹⁶. The persistent challenge for India is to cultivate an intelligence culture that can effectively balance proactive threat response with geostrategic considerations.

Since independence, India's approach to external threats in intelligence has been characterised by a reactive and cautious stance. However, under Narendra Modi, India's covert doctrine has shifted towards aggression. National Security Advisor Ajit Doval promoted clandestine action as a "low-cost sustainable offensive" to "bleed the enemy to submission⁹⁷." Allegations of R&AW's involvement in the 2023 assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar in Canada and a foiled plot against Gurpatwant Singh Pannun in New York triggered diplomatic crises with Ottawa and Washington⁹⁸. These operations, described as "arguably the biggest debacle" in RAW's history, raise urgent questions about tradecraft, legality, and the erosion of India's traditionally cautious covert ethos.

Ajit Doval's articulation of the "defensive offence" doctrine in his 2014 Nani Palkhivala Memorial Lecture marked a decisive break from India's postcolonial restraint in covert operations⁹⁹. Historically, India adopted a reactive posture toward cross-border terrorism, limiting its intelligence activities to defensive measures. One of the most exemplified cases was when, in 2008, Pakistan's Inter-Services Intelligence Directorate (ISI) planned a suicide bombing in Kabul, at the Indian embassy, where the then Indian National Security Advisor embraced a cautious and diplomatic approach rather than retaliation. Menon instructed the Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW) to "keep your hands in your pockets¹⁰⁰." The episode underscores India's

⁹⁴ Paul McGarr, "The Kennedy Assassination Files, India, and New Insights into Intelligence Beyond the Anglosphere," *KCSI Insights* (King's Centre for the Study of Intelligence, 12 May 2025)

⁹⁵ Paul M. McGarr, *Spying in South Asia: Britain, the United States, and India's Secret Cold War* 12.

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*, 277-278.

⁹⁷ McGarr, Paul. / **India: Secret Wars and the Lure of Localism, Covert Action: National Approaches to Unacknowledged Intervention.** editor / Rory Cormac ; Magda Long ; Genevieve Lester ; Mark Stout ; Damien Van Puyvelde. Washington D.C.: Georgetown University Press, 2025. pp. 173.

⁹⁸ Tribune, "India's Covert Assassination Campaign: RAW Linked to Targeted Killings in Pakistan," January 1, 2025, <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2519427/raw-linked-to-assassinations-in-pakistan-report-exposes-indias-covert-campaign>.

⁹⁹ Scroll Staff, "Watch Ajit Doval Say If Pakistan Does 'One Mumbai' It May Lose Balochistan," *Scroll.in*, January 6, 2016, <https://scroll.in/article/801447>.

¹⁰⁰ Paul, McGarr, / **India: Secret Wars and the Lure of Localism**, 160.

historically cautious, covert stance, favouring diplomatic resolution over punitive measures even in the face of severe provocation. Doval criticised the cautious, muted approach as “weak and misplaced,” arguing that perpetual defence left India vulnerable and ceded the strategic initiative to Pakistan. His proposed shift, “working on the vulnerabilities of Pakistan”, encompassed exposing terrorist networks, destabilising internal security, and undermining Islamabad’s influence in Afghanistan. The statement, “You can do one Mumbai, you may lose Balochistan,” encapsulated a willingness to escalate covert pressure rather than passively absorb repeated attacks¹⁰¹. Operation Sinhoor, in response to the Phalgam terror attack on April 22nd, highlights this transition again. This doctrine, embraced by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, signals India’s shift from a cautious, localised, covert ethos to a more assertive, extraterritorial strategy aimed at imposing costs on adversaries without triggering full-scale war.

India’s approach to covert action has shifted from deep-seated postcolonial suspicion to cautious regional interventions and, more recently, towards assertive global operations. In the early decades after independence, leaders like Jawaharlal Nehru regarded covert action as ethically questionable and strategically risky, limiting intelligence activities to defensive, localised missions. The humiliating defeat in the 1962 Sino-Indian War and subsequent conflicts with Pakistan prompted a change, leading to the establishment of the Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW) in 1968 and successful operations in Bangladesh (1971) and Sikkim (1975), which combined paramilitary support with psychological warfare¹⁰². For much of the late 20th century, India adhered to a doctrine of calibrated, regionally focused covert action, cautious about the diplomatic fallout after failures in Sri Lanka and Punjab. Today, however, this restraint has diminished. This shift raises important questions about accountability, tradecraft, and the strategic risks of abandoning an

“Indian way” of covert action rooted in caution and pragmatism.

Beyond covert operations, India has long regarded its global diaspora as a strategic asset, utilising cultural, economic, and political connections to advance national interests abroad. Historically, the Research and Analysis Wing and other agencies have maintained discreet channels with Indian-origin communities, especially in regions with large populations, such as North America, the UK, and Mauritius¹⁰³. This engagement often serves two purposes: building soft power through cultural diplomacy and monitoring separatist movements like Khalistan that garner support from overseas networks. Recent claims of covert operations targeting Sikh activists in Canada and the United States highlight how diaspora engagement can shift from benign influence to covert actions when national security interests intersect with transnational activism¹⁰⁴. Such actions demonstrate India’s readiness to expand its intelligence operations beyond South Asia, signalling a redefinition of its covert approach towards global ambitions. Switzerland hosts an expanding Indian diaspora mainly involved in high-value sectors such as pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, and information technology. While India’s interaction with these communities has traditionally emphasised economic diplomacy and talent networks, the example set by operations in Canada and the U.S. prompts questions about future developments.

The development of Indian intelligence culture cannot be fully understood solely through its institutional history or colonial legacies. Instead, it is deeply rooted in India’s civilizational ethos, which influences strategic thought, ethical standards, and perceptions of secrecy and authority. Indian strategic thinking is grounded in a long-standing civilisational tradition that regards intelligence as both a moral and pragmatic tool of statecraft. This continuity extends from Tamil classical poetry on war and epic

¹⁰¹ Scroll Staff, “Watch Ajit Doval Say If Pakistan Does ‘One Mumbai’ It May Lose Baluchistan,” *Scroll.in*, January 6, 2016, <https://scroll.in/article/801447>.
¹⁰² Paul, McGarr, / *India: Secret Wars and the Lure of Localism*, 167-171.

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*, 172.
¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*, 173-174.

narratives such as the *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* to Tamil treatises like the *Tirukkural*, all of which highlight foresight, alliance management, and covert operations as vital for safeguarding sovereignty and dharma¹⁰⁵. Indian traditions nurture an ethical realism that balances secrecy with justice, exemplified in works like Kautilya's *Arthashastra* and South Indian Sangam literature, where espionage is justified as a duty to protect the realm rather than merely a utilitarian act¹⁰⁶. In contemporary policy, leaders such as S. Jaishankar and the Modi government draw on these civilisational principles to distinguish India's worldview from Anglo-American theories of international relations, subtly shaping diplomatic narratives, strategic autonomy, and India's self-image as a "civilizational state"¹⁰⁷. Although not formally codified into doctrine, this influence appears through political culture, elite dialogue, and symbolic acts, such as promoting yoga and conveying Sanskrit terms on global forums such as Visvaguru (world teacher) Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam (humanity as one family), conveying India's unique approach to power and ethics¹⁰⁸.

Indian strategic culture has evolved through the interaction of indigenous statecraft traditions and external influences, beginning with Kautilya's *Arthashastra*, which promoted a knowledge-driven view of governance in which intelligence, foresight, and covert action formed the foundation of state power¹⁰⁹. This proactive approach was disrupted during the colonial period, when British rule established a reactive, fragmented, and internally focused intelligence system, shaped by racial hierarchies and bureaucratic rivalries, that reduced intelligence to an ad hoc security measure rather than a strategic tool¹¹⁰. After independence, India

inherited this colonial framework alongside residual Kautilyan ideals, resulting in a hybrid intelligence culture where leaders like Sardar Patel sought centralised coordination, while Jawaharlal Nehru preferred diplomatic openness over secrecy, reflecting Victorian sensibilities¹¹¹. This enduring duality between ancient pragmatism and colonial inertia continues to influence India's approach to national security, external threats, and its pursuit of strategic autonomy¹¹².

In conclusion, India's intelligence culture must be recognised as an evolving blend of its civilisational heritage, colonial legacies, and post-independence political choices, with each element shaping how the Indian state perceives threats, manages secrecy, and utilises intelligence as a tool of national power. The coexistence of Kautilyan pragmatism, colonial bureaucratic inertia, and modern strategic uncertainties has created a distinctive hybrid ethos that continues to influence India's intelligence practices. As India faces a more contested regional environment and aims for a greater global role, its intelligence culture is gradually but clearly transforming from a historically reactive, fragmented, and politically constrained system into one prioritising anticipatory intelligence, strategic autonomy, and proactive operations. This ongoing transformation underscores the central argument of this paper: that Indian intelligence institutions cannot be fully understood through organisational charts or operational mandates alone, but only by examining the deeper cultural logic that underpins them and their strategic imperatives. Recognising this cultural evolution and strategic imperatives is crucial not only for analysing India's past strategic surprises but also

¹⁰⁵ Chad Baxter, "Statecraft and Intelligence in Ancient India," *Journal of Intelligence History* 7, no. 2 (2007): 85–99; David Shulman, *Tamil: A Biography* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2016); J. L. Brockington, *The Sacred Thread: Hinduism in Its Continuity and Diversity* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 1981).

¹⁰⁶ R. P. Kangle, *The Kautilya Arthashastra, Part III: A Study* (Bombay: University of Bombay, 1965); Roger Boesche, "Kautilya's Arthashastra on War and Diplomacy in Ancient India," *Journal of Military History* 67, no. 1 (2003): 9–37; T. K. Sen, "Espionage in Ancient India," *Indian Historical Review* 9, no. 1–2 (1982): 67–85.

¹⁰⁷ S. Jaishankar, *The India Way: Strategies for an Uncertain World* (New Delhi: HarperCollins, 2020); Ian Hall, *Modi and the Reinvention of Indian Foreign Policy* (Bristol: Bristol University Press, 2019); Sushant Singh, "Civilizational

Foreign Policy: India's Search for Its Strategic Self," *International Affairs* 98, no. 4 (2022): 1325–1343.

¹⁰⁸ David M. Malone and Christian Wagner, "India's Soft Power: Prospects and Limitations," in *Handbook of India's International Relations*, ed. David M. Malone, C. Raja Mohan, and Srinath Raghavan (London: Routledge, 2011), 317–328; Srinath Raghavan, *India's Strategic Culture: The Making of National Security Policy* (New Delhi: ORF–Brookings India, 2018); Kadira Pethiyagoda, *Indian Foreign Policy and Cultural Narratives* (London: Routledge, 2020).

¹⁰⁹ Dheeraj Paramesha Chaya, *India's Intelligence Culture and Strategic Surprises: Spying for South Block* (London: Routledge, 2022), 39–57

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 64–70.

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*, 83–88.

¹¹² *Ibid.*, 88–94.

for assessing its emerging capabilities and future role within the Indo-Pacific security framework.

9. International Solar Alliance (ISA), India and the Geopolitics of Solar Power

*Priyanka Agar Wala**

In recent decades, renewable resources have emerged as a diplomatic tool to shape the global geopolitics of clean energy. In this regard, the International Solar Alliance (ISA) was formed to foster collaboration among solar-abundant nations in decarbonizing energy sectors through transformative cross-border initiatives. India, co-founded ISA with France in 2015, has been playing a leading role in shaping its missions and works to advance international cooperation in the transition to sustainable and clean energy. Furthermore, India's comprehensive experience in developing solar initiatives and regulatory frameworks serves as a replicable model for other member countries, especially those in the Global South. By sharing best practices and technical expertise, India aims to empower other nations in their solar energy journeys. This paper deals with the ISA, not only as a clean energy initiative but also as a geopolitical mechanism reflecting and reshaping the power asymmetries of the global energy order. Placing ISA within the larger context of the geopolitics of renewable energy, the analysis tends to understand India's ambition towards green hegemony by initiating solar projects, particularly in Ethiopia.

Geopolitics of Renewable Energy and India

The twentieth and twenty-first centuries were profoundly shaped by the geopolitics of energy, an idea that can be defined as the way countries influence one another through energy supply and demand. Today, the world is facing significant challenges of reducing the use of fossil fuel and accelerating low-carbon technologies, a shift that is reflected in the growing focus on the geopolitics of renewable energy. Unlike oil and gas extraction and control over supply, the new clean energy geopolitics depends on such aspects as access to technology,

knowledge transfer and collaboration. Thus, the balance of power in energy geopolitics is shifting from oil and gas-rich countries to those investing in low-carbon energy solutions.

The strategic use of solar-based technologies is gaining momentum worldwide to improve energy security, advance Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and strengthen international relations, along with other renewable resources such as water and wind. To reduce carbon emissions and achieve a sustainable future, it comprises cooperative efforts between solar-rich countries to install solar power, exchange technological innovations and create supportive regulatory frameworks. This strategy utilizes solar energy to enhance energy access in developing nations, mitigate climate change, and foster trust. In this context, India has emerged as one of the top five winners in renewable energy, contributing majorly to global sustainability and energy security through its solar expertise.

Currently, solar technology is growing globally, but not at an even pace. Although in recent years India's solar energy industry has been expanding rapidly, China contributed exclusively 329 GW of new solar capacity in 2024 which is approximately 55% of the global total. However, it is now considered one of the vital components of India's energy security and sustainable development while competing with major solar power nations. Compared with last year, the solar power production in the country increased by 32.4% from January to April in 2025. Moreover, it has 70.10 GW of installed capacity as of June 2023 which comprises 2.51 GW from off-grid installations, 10.37 GW from rooftop solar systems and 57.22 GW from extensive ground-mounted projects. The growing capacity allowed power providers in India to produce and sell more electricity while reducing coal consumption and the use of natural gas, the two main sources of electricity production in the country. The accomplishment is aligned well with both India's commitment to a green future and its target of achieving 500 GW of non-fossil fuel energy by 2030.

This rapid expansion shows India's robust solar policy and growing significance in the new global energy order.

India's Solar PV industry

The Indian solar PV (Photovoltaic) industries are mostly characterized by limited innovation, owing to adopt advanced technologies and practices. A constant emphasis on the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and improving air quality, led to the demand for renewable alternatives while creating opportunities for solar power as a green energy source in India. Due to the growing competition, technological advancements and economies of scale, solar power has become a cost-effective green solution in the country. India's National Solar Mission, launched in January 2010, also known as Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission (JNNSM) has been instrumental in promoting solar power adoption in the country, especially in rural India. Moreover, initiatives like the Solar Energy Corporation of India (SECI) have been playing a crucial role in solar power projects and auctions that further facilitate country's innovation in this sector.

However, India's local solar manufacturing is heavily dependent on imports (nearly 80%) for its solar equipment, where China alone is contributing more than 50% of the total imports. Although other nations like Vietnam, Malaysia, and Thailand supply India with solar cells and modules, they rely on Chinese raw materials such as polysilicon and wafers. The country still lacks manufacturing capacity of polysilicon and wafers, two of the main inputs for solar cells. Hence, the government of India is actively incentivizing solar sector and collaborating with some of the leading companies like Tata Power Solar and Adani Solar, aiming to achieve energy security while combating geopolitical tensions through reducing the country's vulnerability to fuel price fluctuations and supply chain risk.

ISA, India and Geopolitics of Solar Power

The International Solar Alliance (ISA) was formed as a collective initiative between India and France to combat climate change by advancing and implementing solar energy. The intergovernmental organization was conceptualized on the sidelines of COP21 held in Paris and aims to unlock US\$1 trillion in solar investments by 2030 through its 'Towards 1000' strategy, focusing on reducing both technology and financing costs. These programs concentrate on three priority areas: Analytics & Advocacy, Capacity Building and Programmatic Support, all aimed at fostering a conducive environment for solar energy investments within its member countries.

By concentrating only on solar energy, India also made a deliberate attempt to set the ISA apart from other organizations in the clean energy space that are in a similar position, especially the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) and the International Energy Agency (IEA). In contrast to IRENA, which has a research-oriented profile and generates yearly statistics on the status of renewable energy globally, the ISA emphasized its action-oriented profile as a key differentiator.

Under the leadership of Prime Minister (PM) Narendra Modi, India's foreign policy agenda underwent a significant change by 2015 as India began to stake its claim among other major powers in international politics and aim for a leadership position in global governance. Hence, both India's commitment to clean energy and quest for green hegemony laid the groundwork for the formation of the International Solar Alliance (ISA). The diplomatic stance of the country in the Paris Agreement represented a radical shift from its previously defensive, pessimistic appearances at multilateral climate negotiations. At the same time, the ISA's launch was a diplomatic triumph for India since it sought to bridge the gap between the G20 and G77 blocs to create a new intergovernmental organization.

Moreover, it demonstrates a significant change in India's foreign policy. The country leverages the

climate issue to further two strategic goals: first, to assert its global dominance through a new treaty-based solar organization (i.e., ISA) and second, to take the lead in the environmentally adjacent sector, reaffirming its commitment to climate action. In this context, ISA offers a new and multilateral platform for mobilizing funds and technologies for the deployment of solar energy in the global South while considering the fragmented nature of international climate negotiations regarding finance.

Indian Solar Power Projects

ISA's vision for "One Sun, One World, One Grid" (OSOWOG), a transnational electrical grid that will supply solar power worldwide, was established by Narendra Modi at the ISA's inaugural assembly in October 2018. Under a draft plan created by the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE), OSOWOG will link 140 nations via a shared grid for solar power transfer. The plan has three stages: at the first stage, it will connect Indian grids with the grids in the Middle East, South-East Asia and South Asia aiming to share solar resources, at the second stage, it will link the first phase's countries with the African renewable resource pool and at the third stage, it will be the global interconnection.

On November 26, 2024, ISA and India signed a Project Implementation Agreement (PIA). It marks a significant step towards the advancement of low-carbon energy in the Indo-Pacific region. Currently, India has allocated USD 2 million for solar projects in Fiji, the Comoros, Madagascar and Seychelles. As part of its Quad Climate Working Group commitments, which are supported by the agreement. The purpose of these projects is to build rooftop solar panels, solar pump installations and solar refrigerators by the middle of 2025. This endeavor further illustrates India's increasing leadership in regional climate action.

On the other hand, India's success in both expansive grid-connected projects and rural mini-grids solar installation is currently viewed as a replicable model

for the global south's clean energy transition. Building on this success, the International Solar Alliance (ISA) and India's National Thermal Power Corporation Limited (NTPC) are preparing to sign tripartite agreements with seven African countries to develop large-scale solar power projects with a combined capacity of over 1,530 MW. These include ground-mounted installations like 800 MW in Guinea, 400 MW in Ethiopia, 100 MW each in Malawi and Zambia and 50 MW each in Mali and Niger. As part of this strategic move to deepen clean energy partnerships with Africa, ISA is actively supporting several solar projects across the African continent. These initiatives include the solarization of schools, hospitals, government facilities and agricultural infrastructure such as cold storage units and solar water pumps, aiming to expand energy access and decrease dependence on fossil fuels.

One of these many projects, India is collaborating in solar pump installation in Ethiopia as part of Ethiopia's goal to install 35,000 solar and/or wind-powered water systems by 2030. It aims to mitigate energy scarcity while promoting clean energy transition under Ethiopia's commitment to the Paris agreement and underlines increasing concern over climate change and disparities in energy access. Ethiopia, one of the member countries of ISA, currently faces severe vulnerabilities due to climate change, which include erratic rainfall, rising temperatures and prolonged droughts. It affects the country's agricultural sector and rural livelihoods by causing water scarcity. In May 2022, ISA signed three significant agreements with the government of Ethiopia to launch a national solarization program, including solar-powered water pumping and the establishment of a Solar Technology Application Centre. Hence, ISA is currently actively working to deploy 2,250 solar pumps for irrigation and 1,400 solar pumps for drinking water in collaboration with Ethiopia's Ministry of Water and Energy.

In collaboration with the International Water Management Institute (IWMI) and the Indian National Thermal Power Corporation (NTPC), a development team has already been sent to Ethiopia in March.

These initiatives are anticipated to strengthen both agricultural productivity and rural development through South-South cooperation. Furthermore, it is expected to serve as a replicable model to other solar-rich countries for integrating solar technology into agriculture and other developmental fields while showcasing the transformative potential of solar energy solutions beyond its environmental benefits.

Geopolitics of Solar Pump Installation in Ethiopia

Ethiopia's commitment towards decarbonization by 2030 has been heavily supported by China, particularly through infrastructure projects and cooperative efforts. In early 2024, Ethiopia became the first country to ban the export of gasoline and diesel vehicles as part of its strategic move to a green transition. Currently, more than 100,000 electric vehicles are being used across the country and a large portion of them are being imported from China. As being second by population in Africa and a major regional power, Ethiopia has projected substantial influence over the Horn of Africa due to its historical independence and strategic location. There are several ongoing development projects in the country. In October 2024, the Green Climate Fund (GCF) approved USD 45 million for solar water pumping in Ethiopia. There is also an ongoing solar pump project named the Lalibela project by the International Committee for the Red Cross, which is expected to be completed in 2025.

The growing partnerships, particularly with China and the establishment of stronger diplomatic ties, high-level exchanges, trade relations and cooperation on capacity building and knowledge transfer, make Ethiopia geopolitically significant. Thus, the increasing solar partnership with Ethiopia demonstrates India's ambition to lead the new geopolitics of renewable energy. By offering practical solutions tied to agriculture and rural development, India uses the ISA as a platform to challenge China's dominance in the green energy transition. By recognizing the strategic importance, India has focused on the installation of solar pumps in Ethiopia

as a dual-purpose initiative that aims to support solar power expansion while boosting the country's agricultural sector. Through the installation of solar pumps, India offers support to Ethiopia in terms of water and irrigation and raises its geopolitical position in an area where global interest is rapidly growing. This solar pump initiative in Ethiopia is supported by NTPC, one of the partner organizations of ISA, and demonstrates India's commitment to providing affordable renewable energy solutions for both rural development and agricultural productivity. This strategy underlines India's development cooperation with Ethiopia, rooted in the Indian Technical and Economic Cooperation (ITEC) program and places India as a major player in the geopolitics of clean energy by offering solar-based solutions as environmentally sustainable and cost-effective alternatives.

However, India's domestic solar cell manufacturing capacity continues under technological limitations. Even with high import duty, Chinese solar cells are still to be competitive in price in both the Indian and global markets. A fair portion of the Indian market itself is still dominated by Chinese modules assembled locally. Although China is well-known as the leading supplier of solar equipment worldwide, India's exports of Photovoltaic (PV) modules are gaining traction. ISA, in this context, advocates for the diversification of sources to combat global supply chain risks. This collaborative effort indicates India's growing leadership in global sustainable energy partnerships while aligning well with ISA's mission to deploy solar-based technology in the Global South.

Conclusion

Increasing inequities in power access and concerns about climate change underline solar technology as a new realm for India to lead the clean energy race. In this regard, the establishment of the International Solar Alliance (ISA) highlights how solar energy has emerged as a geopolitical tool in global energy affairs. India's solar advancement and initiatives in developing nations reflect its aspiration to support

sustainable development while building its influence in the global South. Here, in this case, the solar pump installation in Ethiopia demonstrates its strategic move towards solar cooperation. However, India's heavy reliance on Chinese-manufactured solar instruments poses a challenge to its green leadership. Alternatively, it forces India to strengthen its domestic capacity in solar manufacturing and innovation. ISA, therefore, represents both a cooperative platform in advocating solar energy and an opportunity to expand its influence in the emerging geopolitics of renewable energy.

* Priyanka Agar Wala is a Senior Fellow with the South Asia Desk of SIGA. She is a social scientist and researcher specialising in social pluralism, sustainability transitions, and global affairs, with a focus on solar diplomacy, the geopolitics of outer space, and AI governance.

References

Journal, Articles & Reports:

- Akinwumi, I., & Humphries, S. (2020). *Sustainability*, 12(15), 6223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12156223>
- Arora, S., Vijayabaskar, M., Sharma, D., & Stirling, A. (2019). Sustainable development through diversifying pathways in India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 54(46), 32-37. https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?title=Sustainable+development+through+diversifying+pathways+in+India&author=S+Arora&author=M+Vijayabaskar&author=D+Sharma&publication_year=2019&journal=Economic+and+Political+Weekly&pages=32-37
- Atteridge A, Shrivastava MK, Pahuja N, et al. (2012) Climate policy in India: What shapes international, national and state policy? *Ambio* 41: 68–77. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13280-011-0242-5>
- Bedi HP (2024) India's solar soft power. *Energy Research and Social Science* 109: 103396 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2214629623004565>
- Blondeel, M., et al. (2021). "Rather, this is an age of fossil fuel abundance..." *Geography Compass*, e12580. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12580>
- Chatterjee, E. (2022). New developmentalism and its discontents: State activism in Modi's Gujarat and India. *Development and Change*, 53(1), 58-83. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/dech.12579>
- Dubash, N. K. (2013). The politics of climate change in India: narratives of equity and cobenefits. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 4(3), 191-201. <https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/wcc.210>
- Ghosh, A. (2019). *Making sense on its own terms: India in the HFC and aviation negotiations*. In N. K. Dubash (Ed.), *India in a warming world: Integrating climate change and development* (pp. 230–249). New Delhi, India: Oxford University Press. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338046819_Making_Sense_on_Its_Own_Terms_India_in_the_HFC_and_Aviation_NegotiationsIndia_in_the_HFC_and_Aviation_Negotiations/citations
- Jha, V. (2023).** *The Making of the International Solar Alliance: India's Moment in the Sun*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198884705.001.0001>
- Paltsev, S. (2016). "The geopolitics of energy supply and demand." *Review of International Political Economy*, 23(3), 226–247. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00963402.2016.1240476>
- Smith, J. (2024). "Geopolitical dimensions of renewable energy transitions." *Foreign Policy Analysis*, 20(1), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14765284.2024.2334553>
- Smith, K., & Kumar, R. (2019). "Clean energy transitions and national strategy." *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 21(5), 678–694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrp.2019.07.002>

Tadesse, B. (2023). "Ethiopia's Strategic Influence: Shaping Geopolitical and Economic Dynamics in the Horn of Africa." In *Geo-Retrieved Insights* (pp. 50–67). Publisher. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/390255904_Ethiopia's_Strategic_Influence_Shaping_Geopolitical_and_Economic_Dynamics_in_the_Horn_of_Africa

Policy Papers & Institutional Reports:

Grand View Research, Inc. (2024, June 14). *India solar PV panels market size, share & trends analysis report by technology (thin film, crystalline silicon), by grid (on grid, off grid), by application (residential, commercial, industrial), and segment forecasts, 2024–2030*. Grand View Research. Retrieved August 16, 2025, from <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/india-solar-pv-panels-market-report>

International Solar Alliance. (n.d.-a). *Solar Park*. ISA. <https://isa.int/solar-park#>

International Solar Alliance. (n.d.-b). *Regulatory Training*.

ISA. <https://isa.int/programmes/regulatoryTraining>

International Solar Alliance. (2019). *Towards 1,000: Bridging the Solar Finance & Technology*

Gap (White paper). ISA. Retrieved

from <https://isolaralliance.org/uploads/docs/30626e4a64c0df31281ce3d64c1605.pdf>

Research Institute for Sustainable Transformations. (2018). Anurag Srivastava: "South–South cooperation in renewable energy." *DCR Newsletter*, 1(6). Retrieved from <https://ris.org.in/newsletter/dcr/2018/DCR%20Volume%201%20No%20206%202018/pdf/chapter/Anurag%20Srivastava.pdf>

Solar Energy Corporation of India Ltd. (n.d.). *Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission:*

Towards building Solar India[PDF]. SECI. Retrieved August 16, 2025, from [https://www.seci.co.in/upload/static/files/mission_document_JNNSM\(1\)](https://www.seci.co.in/upload/static/files/mission_document_JNNSM(1)).

News & Online Articles

Africa Energy Portal. (2024, Nov 12). Ethiopia to exploit full potential of solar energy, accelerate energy transition. <https://africa-energy-portal.org/news/ethiopia-exploit-full-potential-solar-energy-accelerate-energy-transition>

Energy-Box. (2023, Dec 3). Ethiopia progresses with solar energy projects for water and agriculture development. <https://www.energy-box.com/post/ethiopia-progresses-with-solar-energy-projects-for-water-and-agriculture-development>

SCTG. (2025, April 12). Solar Momentum: Africa's solar energy push gains traction with ISA and Indian industry backing. *SolarQuarter*. <https://solarquarter.com/2025/04/12/solar-momentum-africas-solar-energy-push-gains-traction-with-isa-and-indian-industry-backing/>

Solar Quarter. (2023, Sep 22). Ethiopia's solar PV market: A bright future ahead. <https://solarquarter.com/2023/09/22/ethiopia-s-solar-pv-market-a-bright-future-ahead/>

The International Committee of the Red Cross. (2024). Ethiopia: Solar power helps bring back water to the population in conflict-affected Lalibela. ICRC. <https://www.icrc.org/en/article/ethiopia-solar-power-helps-bring-back-water-population-conflict-affected-lalibela#:~:text=The%20plan%20is%20to%20install,project%20is%20completed%20by%20now.>

RWR Energy. (n.d.). NTPC – Leading India's transition to renewables. Retrieved from <https://ntpc.co.in>

Press Information Bureau. (2022, Oct 10). Tripartite agreement for deployment of 1,530 MW solar capacity in seven African countries. Government of India. Retrieved from <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1795071>

Press Information Bureau. (2023, Nov 5). ISA partners with Ethiopia for solar pump and technology centre. Government of India. Retrieved from <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2071486>

Tadesse, B. (2023). "Ethiopia's Strategic Influence: Shaping Geopolitical and Economic Dynamics in the Horn of Africa." In *Geo-Retrieved Insights* (pp. 50–67). Publisher. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/390255904_Ethiopia's_Strategic_Influence_Shaping_Geopolitical_and_Economic_Dynamics_in_the_Horn_of_Africa

Belt and Road News Center. (n.d.). Ethiopia–China cooperation news. Retrieved from <https://eng.yidaiyilu.gov.cn/p/07T9IL9V.html>

10. Geopolitics of Outer Space: Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) and Its Strategy

*Priyanka Agar Wala**

Over time, space has evolved into a new frontier of geopolitical rivalry out of the monotonous domain of scientific exploration. During the Cold War, outer space was considered as a critical domain for strategic power that concerns a nation's national security, technological advancement, and global stature. Since then, countries with their space agencies have been trying to acquire control over space infrastructure, gain supremacy in space-based technologies, and proclaim their national sovereignty in this domain. However, the global trend shifted to the privatization of the space sector from fully state-controlled space agencies. Thus, countries today militarize and commercialize their space sector to compete in a few functions that require advancements in place for their respective economic, political, and defense aspirations.

Like other space-faring nations, India has recently opened its outer space sector to private participation and partnership, aiming to achieve technological advancement and global competitiveness. Yet its national space agency, ISRO (Indian Space Research Organization) remains central in this sector and has positioned itself strategically to utilize space for national development, regional influence, and global leadership. ISRO's activities, guided by the Indian space policy, are rooted not only in aspirations for technological advancement but also in the social and economic empowerment of the country while equipping the armed forces with space-based military capabilities. Furthermore, the emergence of space as an arena for scientific advancement and a geopolitical weapon has made the activities of ISRO significant. Its changing strategy in space has also become an articulation of India's ambition to not only stabilize the role of India

in regional leadership but also build the global space environment in a manner that serves its national interests.

Hence, this paper exclusively focuses on ISRO and seeks to understand its strategic shifts in navigating the changing global space dynamics. It examines ISRO's achievements, its current role in the regional and international space race, and how India's space policies reflect larger geopolitical trends. Understanding these dimensions will provide insight into India's aspirations at the global level, in which ISRO will contribute to the country's military and non-military aspirations.

ISRO in the space race

The Indian Space Program, extensively led by the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) has been passed through many phases i.e. initiation (1960 -70 s), experimental (1980s), operational (1990s), and expansion (2000s onward). ISRO, previously the Indian National Committee for Space Research (INCOSPAR) formed in 1962, was expanded in 1969 and brought under the Department of Space (DoS) in 1972 to harness India's space technology for various national needs. It stepped onto the world stage in 1980 as a rising space organization when it launched RS-1, country's first satellite to indigenously developed launch vehicle from the Satish Dhawan Space Center. With its capability to develop satellite space launch vehicles, ISRO has developed a Polar Satellite Launch Vehicle (PSLV)" as well as a Geosynchronous Satellite Launch Vehicle (GSLV)" which can meet both India's national needs and demands of the global market.

Some of ISRO's milestones such as the initial steps towards the development of Anti-Satellite (ASAT) capabilities, the launch of the South Asian Satellite and Indian Regional Navigation Satellite System (NavIC), and the various missions such as "Chandrayaan (Chandrayan-1 in 2008, Chandrayan-2 in 2019 and Chandrayan-3 in 2023)" the moon mission, "Mangalyaan (2013)" the mars mission, and the soon to be launched "Gaganyaan (2025)" ISRO's

first crewed mission underscore the ambition that India has set forth not only to lead in space technology but to achieve itself as one of the major international players in space. The 2023 Indian Space Policy further signifies this ambition towards enhancing the capacity of ISRO by commercialization of space, increased private-sector participation, and improved defense capabilities through programs like "Mission DefSpace". It now casts an evolving space vision for India that is being put in place to reap technological dividends and geopolitical gains that would further enhance its standing in the competitive international space race.

India and its partnership

Since its inception, ISRO has pursued bilateral and multilateral relations either in the form of formal agreements or memorandums with many space agencies to enhance its capacity. In the bipolar Russian American drive to conquer space, India launched "Aryabhata", its first satellite by Soviet Kosmos-3M rocket in 1975. However, the international partnership has changed over time. The country is pursuing various joint projects with Japan, Brazil, France, and Israel. In 2017, ISRO launched around 100 small satellites in collaboration with many private entities in the USA, Switzerland, and Israel. Again ISRO, jointly with NASA develops a flagship project called NISAR that aims to map the entire globe in just 12 days and provide special and temporal data on sea level rise, ground water, natural hazards, ice mass, and vegetation biomass to understand our ecosystem. This observatory is the first dual-frequency radar with both L-band SAR (lower waves and deeper penetration) and S-band SAR (shorter waves and more surface details) contributed by NASA and ISRO respectively. However, the year 2023 marked this strategic shift when India became the signatory of the Artemis Accord with a larger landing capacity. In this year, India advocated peaceful space exploration at the G21 conference. It shows that India's vision has

drastically transformed from being primarily oriented toward socio-economic development to the larger strategic objectives of global competition, defense, and commercialization.

Why India privatizes its space sector?

India's space industry, predominantly led by ISRO, focuses on top-down technology transfers to Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) and limits the private sector's autonomy to develop end-to-end applications. Major allocations are by ISRO, space applications, and autonomous bodies such as IIST and the Northeast Satellite Applications Center. This is complemented by reduced contributions to space sciences and INSAT satellites. NewSpace, supported by initiatives like 'Make in India' and 'Digital India', however, nurtures entrepreneurship, with companies developing innovative low-cost technologies for global markets holding considerable growth potential within this pretty much nascent industry. Moreover, the budget of the Department of Space in 2024-2025 has increased from \$133 million over the previous financial year to \$156 million, marking an increase of 18 percent. It highlights aspects like capacity building in space technology and commercializes space activities to compete in the new space race. However, India's private sector has a limited contribution to space exploration and mostly works as a supplier and vendor for ISRO, it is changing quickly.

As per India's Space Policy 2023, India's Space program will focus on the development of its commercial sector so that ISRO can work on research. India now has almost 200 space start-ups with 200 million USD in private investment. Skyroot, founded in 2018 by a former ISRO scientist, is a start-up that collaborates with ISRO to use its expertise and expand India's vision of dominating the space race through economically affordable and sustainable launch vehicles. The success of the Vikram series further accelerates India's quest to compete with prominent global entities such as SpaceX (USA), Energy (China), and MDA (Canada).

Perhaps it aims to offer dedicated launches for 20,000 USD per kilogram, which is yet more expensive than SpaceX. Unlike other private entities that offer "rideshare", the goal of Skyroot is to take satellites to customized locations. It will allow companies, academic institutions, and governments as well to send small payloads to diverse orbits for further commercial, educational, or scientific exploration in space and will accelerate India's soft power.

India towards space militarization

India, being a signatory of the Outer Space Treaty 1967 and in favor of peaceful exploration of space, has no formal national space policy that explicitly outlines the military uses of outer space. However, while encouraging private participation in the entire space economy, the Space Policy of India 2023 emphasizes the need to develop space capabilities for the socio-economic development and security of the nation. It supports various non-governmental entities in carrying out end-to-end activities in satellite-based remote sensing and space situational awareness. However, their applications could serve both civilian and military purposes due to the dual nature of the technology. Historically, India has emphasized national security and conflict prevention as key elements of its interest in space for defense; however, this interest began changing from the mid 2000s onward, with the Indian Air Force advocating the establishment of a "space command". The focus has been states due to severe, ongoing tensions with Pakistan and China, and growing ties with the United States. The Kargil War between India and Pakistan in 1999 primarily highlighted the need of satellites in the provision of situational awareness and intelligence relay, thereafter, leading to the making of India's 'Defence Space Vision 2020.' This has brought the defense and space sectors closely together. Since then, ISRO has launched numerous defense and security satellites tailored for reconnaissance, surveillance, and communication purposes.

India's strategic position in outer space

Outer space is no longer a tool to measure weather or prevent catastrophes; it has become a strategic domain of establishing influence beyond the border, national security, and financial prosperity. With the continuous development by ISRO in its capacity building from geostationary and LEO satellites to the successful test of Anti-satellite, India has entered the militarization of space. ISRO's landmark achievements in building navigation systems and upcoming human flight in space mark India as a major space-faring nation, this indicates the three main strategic goals of India: 1. Capacity building to dominate China and Pakistan militarily, 2. Regional dominance and 3. Global influence.

Indo-China space race

The successful soft landing of Chandrayaan-3 on the south pole of the Moon was historic for India, as it became the fourth nation to possess such capability and the first to reach out to the South Pole. This achievement demonstrates the scientific capability of India and establishes it as an emerging power in the competitive global race to the Moon. A wonderful quote by the Soviet engineer Boris Chertok "If there hadn't been a Gagarin, there wouldn't have been an Armstrong" could demonstrate the Indo-China space race. If China had not gone to the Moon, India wouldn't have gone to the Moon. Thus, India's ambition in space is largely driven by competition with China. It was ignited after the war of 1962 and was epitomized by milestones like the launch of Chandrayaan-1 in 2008 and Chandrayaan-3 in 2023 by ISRO. Until 2019, as India displayed capability in ASAT by destroying one of its satellites, it showed readiness to defend space assets. Surely, the setting up of a Space Situational Awareness (SSA) program will easily enhance such capability in monitoring and countering threats to space security. ISRO's ASAT test was primarily intended to counter China's advancements in space militarization which is

considered as a milestone for India in land, sea, air, and space defense.

China launched its sounding rocket into the upper atmosphere in 1960, Pakistan in 1962, and India in 1963. These three space-faring nations have shaped the South Asian security architecture where China and Pakistan both have shared a disputed border with India. China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has led to significant infrastructure development with strategic implications in the Indo-Pacific region which fuels the long historical and geopolitical rivalry between India and China. For example, China has built the Hambantota port in Sri Lanka, a deepwater seaport at Gwadar in Pakistan, and has been actively involved in infrastructure development in Afghanistan and Bangladesh. This Chinese expansion in South Asian countries and security concerns in the realms of land and maritime boundaries has strategically shaped India's policy of outer space. Although the new space policy has limited indication towards militarization of space, the ambiguity of the policy indicates that ISRO is secretly developing its space power to establish its hegemony in South Asia to lead future military races.

ISRO is forging space security partnerships with space agencies of the Quad (U.S., Japan, and Australia), France, and others to counter China's growing influence in outer space. This shift marks a departure from India's traditional alignment with nonaligned G21 countries. While the Indo-US partnership prevents the U.S. from collaborating with China or dual-use technologies through the Wolf Amendment, restricted Pakistan-U.S. relations limit even access to advanced space technology, making Pakistan more dependent on China. Thus, in 2018 Pakistan adopted China's BeiDou Navigation System (BDS) instead of the GPS navigation system and in May 2024, Paksat-MM1 was launched from a launch site in China's northwest Sichuan province. It is the second satellite launched by China after iCube-Q, the lunar joint project. Paksat-MM1 is a communication satellite that aims to enhance e-commerce, e-governance, internet, and broadband connection. This strategic competition between

China and the USA and the strategic shift of Pakistan from the USA to China has further accelerated India's quest for being a space power.

India's space policy to regional dominance

India's regional diplomacy is mostly marked by geopolitical rivalry with its neighboring countries. However, none of the SAARC countries excluding India and Pakistan (to some extent) has made significant development in their space sectors. Among these nations, only Bangladesh and Sri Lanka have satellites while Afghanistan, Bhutan, Nepal and the Maldives do not have any domestically owned satellites. As a result, the launch of the South Asian Satellite (GSAT-9) in 2017, formally known as the SAARC satellite by ISRO, has reaffirmed India's scientific prowess. This Geostationary Communication Satellite aims to provide various communication applications in Ku-band with coverage over South Asian countries. However, it is more geopolitical than geospatial. It is one of the steps of Prime Minister Narendra Modi's regional diplomacy to connect with its neighboring South Asian nations in space and counter Chinese influence. While Pakistan opted out of the initiative and joined the Chinese BeiDou navigation system, the remaining South Asian countries along with Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Nepal, the Maldives, and Sri Lanka were rather optimistic regarding the project.

However, the ongoing tension over historical conflicts, border contention, and religious and ethnic tensions with neighbors like Bangladesh, the Maldives, Nepal, and Sri Lanka, raises doubts about the satellite's ability to serve as a unifying force. These challenges raise questions on the success of not just the South Asian Satellite but also an early indication of shifting India's focus from aspiring to regional to global leadership. Thus, the installation of NavIC 2.0 aims to position India from a regional navigation system to a global navigation system along with the USA, Europe, Russia, and China. It traced back to the Kargil war that highlighted the

need for self-reliance and the PNT system (positioning, navigation, and timing). It will be launched in 2028 (estimated) and will be helpful for civilian and military purposes.

India to lead the future space race

While ISRO's successful missions, like Chandrayaan and Mangalyaan, have put India on a cutting-edge map towards achieving excellence in interplanetary exploration, further development in reusable space technologies and advancement in docking of spacecraft bring India more than one step closer to aspiring innovative and ambitious future in space exploration. SpaDex, India's first Space docking mission, is launched at the beginning of 2025, in which two satellites will dock and undock in space. With the success of the mission, India will join the US, China, and Russia as a member of the elite group with space docking capability and establish the Bharatiya Antariksha Station (BAS) as a fully operational space station by 2035. Furthermore, Gaganyaan, ISRO's ongoing project on a manned mission to space showcases India's ambition to lead the global space race. The success of the mission puts the country into the group of countries with the USA, Russia, and China who have the capacity for human flight in space. In the long run, Gaganyaan will open doors for diplomatic collaborations with other space faring nations and will have many tangible and intangible Implications that support India's quest for global leadership.

However, with the emergence of space tourism, there is an increasing demand for sustainable space technologies. By launching 104 Nano satellites with one single rocket, India has recorded the greatest number of satellites in space by a single rocket from a country, surpassed only by Russia, and has established its presence in the growing privatization of space markets. It makes India a serious competitor in the race of the world and a significant player in the burgeoning economic space for commercial space-based surveillance and communication. It not only competes with countries

but also competes with private companies like SpaceX and Blue Origin. It has the world's most reusable launch vehicle, whereas ISRO has simply announced its entry into this. Another important launch is that of the GSLV Mk III, which boasts an indigenously developed cryogenic engine and has been determined to carry heavy payloads. In a low-cost innovation and effective use of indigenous resources, India is marching steadily toward becoming one of the elite groups of space faring nations. It signifies not merely the achievement of a new space mission in terms of technological success but also draws much worldwide attention, enhancing the nation's leverage over others in terms of strategic and scientific reach.

Conclusion

India's space exploration predominantly led by ISRO marks the strategic shift from addressing socio-economic challenges to establishing itself as a strategic global space power. Some of ISRO's significant advancements, such as a successful soft landing on the moon, the development of indigenously developed technologies and increasing militarization of space underscore India's strategic aim toward regional domination and countering countries such as China and Pakistan. With these diverse ambitions of commercializing space services, reusable rocket technology, and establishing the Bharatiya Antariksha Station, India has placed itself as an economically and environmentally sustainable space-faring nation in the global space race.

However, India as a regional space power has been contested by geopolitical complexities and competing interests. China's strategic partnerships with South Asian nations and infrastructure developments in the region through the Belt and Road Initiative have countered India's hegemony. Compared to the United States, China, and the European Union, the Indian space program operates under a rather small budget, thereby restricting its competition with high-cost ventures like

deep-space exploration. But India's strategic move towards commercialization, global partnerships, and growing investment in the sector mark India's trajectory to lead the future race scientifically, economically, and geopolitically.

* Priyanka Agar Wala is a Senior Fellow with the South Asia Desk of SIGA. She is a social scientist and researcher specialising in social pluralism, sustainability transitions, and global affairs, with a focus on solar diplomacy, the geopolitics of outer space, and AI governance.

Literature

- Achakzai, N. U. (2023, September 4). *Pakistan's space program – OpEd*.
- Ahmed, R. Q., Shoaib, M., & Ashraf, R. (2023). India's space pursuit and the changing matrix of South Asian security. *Space Policy*, 65, 101564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2023.101564>
- Aliberti, M. (2018). *India in space: Between utility and geopolitics*. Springer.
- Aryabhata. (n.d.). Retrieved December 27, 2024, from https://www.isro.gov.in/aryabhata_1.html#
- "Budget 2024: India's space sector eyes strategic allocations and incentives." (2024, July 11). *Business Standard*. https://www.business-standard.com/budget/news/budget-2024-india-space-sector-eyes-strategic-allocations-and-incentives-124071100385_1.html
- Desai, F. S., & Yug. (2023, December 13). Barriers to space cooperation in South Asia: Africa as an inspiration. *TDHJ.org*. <https://tdhj.org/blog/post/barriers-space-cooperation-south-asia/>
- Editorial Desk. (2022, December 27). Make SPARSO self-sufficient. *Prothomalo*. <https://en.prothomalo.com/opinion/editorial/z1utm6i8bl>
- Gaganyaan. (n.d.). Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://www.isro.gov.in/Gaganyaan.html>
- Giri, C. (2021). *India in the second space age of interplanetary connectivity*. Taylor & Francis.
- Gunia, A. (2024, April 24). "Cabs to get into space": How this Indian startup wants to revolutionize satellite space travel. *CNN Business*. <https://www.cnn.com/2024/04/23/business/india-space-startups-skyroot-aerospace-hnk-intl/index.html>
- Hussain, S., & Shahzad, K. (2023). India's quest for "global space and influence" through the "outer space" domain. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 10(3), 351–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2023.05.004>
- ISRO Delegation Visits ESA Mission Control. (n.d.). Retrieved August 12, 2024, from https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Operations/ISRO_delegation_visits_ESA_mission_control
- Jalil, G. Y. (2023, December 29). Issue brief on Pakistan's space policy: Tapping into the space potential. *Institute of Strategic Studies Islamabad*. <https://issi.org.pk/issue-brief-on-pakistans-space-policy-tapping-into-the-space-potential/>
- Mukunth, V. (2024, July 23). Budget 2024: 18% hike for Department of Space, lion's share for development of space tech. *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/sci-tech/science/18-hike-for-department-of-space-union-budget-lions-share-for-development-of-space-technologies/article68436318.ece>
- Nadarajah, H. (2024). The emergence of new actors in space. *Asia Pacific Foundation of Canada*. Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://www.asiapacific.ca/publication/space-intro-emergence-new-actors>
- NASA-ISRO SAR (NISAR) Satellite. (n.d.). Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://www.isro.gov.in/NISARSatellite.html>

Nody, N. I., & Ashraf, S. B. (2023, August 28). Let's stake our claim to outer space. *The Daily Star*. <https://www.thedailystar.net/opinion/views/news/lets-stake-our-claim-outer-space-3405026>

Overview of the Indian space sector. *Embassy of India, France & Principality of Monaco*. Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://www.eoiparis.gov.in/page/overview-of-the-indian-space-sector/>

Pakistan launches communication satellite with Chinese assistance. (2024, May 31). *Voice of America*. <https://www.voanews.com/a/pakistan-launches-communication-satellite-with-chinese-assistance-/7637155.html>

"Pakistan's new space policy: Overcoming historical challenges and embracing a new era." (n.d.). *The Diplomat*. Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://thediplomat.com/2023/12/pakistans-new-space-policy-overcoming-historical-challenges-and-embracing-a-new-era/>

"Pakistan's Space and Upper Atmosphere Research Commission: Evolution and prospects." (2024, May 11). *The Nation*. <https://www.nation.com.pk/11-May-2024/pakistan-s-space-and-upper-atmosphere-research-commission-evolution-and-prospects>

Prasad, N. (2017). Traditional space and NewSpace industry in India: Current outlook and perspectives for the future.

PSLV accomplishes zero orbital debris mission. (n.d.). Retrieved August 13, 2024, from https://www.isro.gov.in/PSLVC58_POEM3_acc_omplish_zero_orbital_debris_mission.html

Rajagopalan, R. P., & Stroikos, D. (2024). The transformation of India's space policy: From space for development to the pursuit of security and prestige. *Space Policy*, 69, 101633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2024.101633>

"Space: The next 'frontier' of UK-India cooperation?" (2024). *International Institute for Strategic Studies*. Retrieved August 13, 2024,

from <https://www.iiss.org/online-analysis/online-analysis/2024/07/space-the-next-frontier-of-ukindia-cooperation/>

Stroikos, D. (2024). Why does India want to be a space power? | LSE research. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of International Studies*. <https://www.lse.ac.uk/research/research-for-the-world/politics/india-space-programme>

Syed, F. H. N. (2023). Indo-Israel strategic partnership in Indian Ocean and outer space: A need for regional counter-balancing approach. *NUST Journal of International Peace & Stability*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.37540/njips.v6i2.148>

Zafar, M. A., & Zafar, A. (2022). Devising national space policy in Pakistan. *Æther: A Journal of Strategic Airpower & Spacepower*, 1(4), 49–62. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/487>

11. India's Arctic Ambitions: A Multifaceted Engagement in a Transforming Region

*Dr. Michael Wenger**

India's engagement in the Arctic has evolved from a historical scientific interest into a multifaceted strategy driven by contemporary geopolitical, economic, and environmental imperatives. The nation's 2022 Arctic Policy underscores a commitment to sustainable development, leveraging scientific research – particularly the crucial Arctic-monsoon linkage – as a primary tool of diplomacy. While scientific and environmental goals are explicit, India's ambitions are subtly shaped by the pursuit of energy security, new trade routes like the Northern Sea Route, and the strategic necessity of balancing relationships with Russia, Western nations, and a rising China. This engagement reflects India's aspiration to be a responsible global stakeholder in a rapidly transforming region.

Introduction: India's Growing Arctic Focus in a Changing Geopolitical Landscape

The Arctic, long perceived as a remote and desolate expanse of ice, has rapidly transformed into a region of acute global importance. This shift is driven by a confluence of factors: it stands as a critical barometer of global climate change, with its warming rates significantly exceeding the global average¹; it is believed to hold vast untapped natural resources, including significant hydrocarbon and mineral deposits²; and it is increasingly an arena for geopolitical competition and cooperation among established and emerging powers.¹ The tangible effects of climate change, particularly the receding ice cover, are opening up new maritime transit possibilities, such as the Northern Sea Route (NSR) and the Northwest Passage. These routes have the potential to reshape global trade dynamics and maritime logistics by offering shorter and potentially

more economical pathways between continents.² The Arctic's transition from a peripheral concern to a central stage for global environmental, economic, and strategic interactions provides the crucial context for understanding why a non-Arctic nation like India is progressively deepening its engagement with the region.

India's interest in the Arctic is not a recent phenomenon but has evolved considerably over time. Its historical connection can be traced back to 1920 when, as part of the British Empire, it became a signatory to the Svalbard Treaty, which granted signatories certain rights in the archipelago.¹ However, for much of the 20th century, India's polar focus was predominantly directed towards Antarctica. The 21st century has witnessed a marked shift, with India's Arctic engagement expanding from an initial scientific curiosity to encompass a more comprehensive set of strategic, economic, and environmental dimensions.² Key milestones in this journey include the establishment of its permanent research station, 'Himadri,' in Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard (Norway) in 2008, and its accession to Observer status in the Arctic Council in 2013.¹ This evolving engagement reflects both India's expanding scientific and economic capabilities and its recognition of the Arctic's burgeoning global significance. India's increasing involvement in the Arctic can be interpreted as a manifestation of its broader ambition to assert itself as a significant global actor, moving beyond its traditional focus on South Asia and the Indian Ocean Region. Active participation in the affairs of a distant and complex region like the Arctic signals a willingness to engage in diverse international forums and contribute to debates on global governance.¹ This aligns with India's articulated foreign policy vision of assuming a "leading power" role on the world stage. Therefore, India's Arctic policy is driven not only by the pursuit of specific regional benefits but also by the imperative to project its capabilities and intent as a responsible and influential global stakeholder. Furthermore, while scientific inquiry has been a consistent and foundational driver of India's Arctic

presence, its more recent strategic and economic focus appears to be shaped by a combination of reactive and proactive impulses. Geopolitical shifts, such as China's assertive articulation of itself as a "Near-Arctic State" and its "Polar Silk Road" initiative¹, alongside Russia's strategic pivot towards Asia and its active courting of non-Western partners in the Arctic³, have undoubtedly influenced India's strategic calculations. Concurrently, the tangible opportunities presented by melting ice, including access to potential energy resources and the viability of new trade routes like the NSR, are being proactively explored by New Delhi.² Thus, India's contemporary Arctic posture is a nuanced blend of responding to a dynamic external environment and actively seeking to advance its national interests.

1. Foundations of India's Arctic Engagement: Policy and Scientific Moorings

India's engagement with the Arctic, while gaining prominence in recent years, is rooted in a historical legal standing and has been progressively built upon through sustained scientific endeavors. This foundation provides the legitimacy and context for its current and future ambitions in the region.

1.1. Historical Context: From Svalbard Treaty to Arctic Council Observer

India's formal association with the Arctic dates back to 9 February 1920, when, as part of the British Empire, it became one of the original High Contracting Parties to the Svalbard Treaty.¹ This treaty, signed in Paris, granted signatories, including India, non-discriminatory rights to engage in commercial activities and scientific research in the Svalbard archipelago, subject to Norwegian sovereignty. While this early legal connection remained largely dormant for decades, it established an initial, albeit passive, basis for India's presence in Arctic affairs.

The modern era of India's Arctic engagement commenced with a dedicated focus on scientific

research. The first Indian scientific expedition to the Arctic was launched in 2007, marking a significant step towards understanding the region's unique environment and its global implications.⁴ This was rapidly followed by a landmark achievement in 2008: the establishment of 'Himadri,' India's first permanent Arctic research station, located at the international research base in Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard, Norway.¹

A pivotal moment in India's diplomatic engagement with the Arctic came in May 2013, when it was granted Observer status in the Arctic Council, the preeminent intergovernmental forum for addressing issues faced by the Arctic governments and the indigenous people of the region.¹ This status, which has since been renewed, allows India to attend the meetings of the Council and its subsidiary bodies, contribute to its working groups, and engage in its projects, although it does not grant voting rights.⁵ India's attainment of Observer status signified international recognition of its legitimate interests in the Arctic and provided a formal platform to articulate its perspectives and collaborate with Arctic states and other stakeholders.

Fig. 1 The gavel of the Chair of the Arctic Council. The council is the leading intergovernmental forum promoting cooperation, coordination and interaction among the Arctic States, Arctic Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic and non-Arctic stakeholders. India had been granted Observer Status in the council in 2013. (Image: Linnea Nortström, Arctic Council)

1.2. India's Arctic Policy (2022): "Building a Partnership for Sustainable Development"

After years of active scientific engagement and participation as an Observer in the Arctic Council,

India formalized its approach to the region with the release of its official Arctic Policy in March 2022, titled "India and the Arctic: Building a Partnership for Sustainable Development".¹ The formulation of this policy was reportedly influenced by external factors, including China's 2018 Arctic white paper and an increased geopolitical focus on the Arctic by powers like the United States, suggesting a need for India to clearly articulate its own stance and interests.⁶

The policy is structured around six core pillars, each with specific objectives designed to guide India's multifaceted engagement.

Table 1: Key Pillars and Objectives of India's Arctic Policy (2022)

Pillar	Key Stated Objectives	Primary Sources
1. Science and Research	Strengthen existing research base (Himadri), including year-round presence and potential additional stations; acquire a dedicated ice-class Polar Research Vessel and build indigenous construction capabilities; align Indian research with international initiatives (e.g., SAON, SIOS); foster bilateral and multilateral research projects; increase participation in Arctic Council Working Groups.	5
2. Climate and Environmental Protection	Enhance engagement with UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the Arctic context; improve Earth System modelling for climate predictions; preserve Arctic biodiversity and contribute to environmental management (addressing methane, black carbon, micro-plastics); engage with Arctic Council Working Groups on conservation and emergency preparedness; promote high environmental standards for Indian enterprises.	5

Pillar	Key Stated Objectives	Primary Sources
3. Economic and Human Development	Explore opportunities for responsible exploration of natural resources and minerals; pursue sustainable economic cooperation and investment with Arctic states and other actors; establish digital partnerships for e-commerce; identify infrastructure investment opportunities (offshore exploration, ports, ICT); encourage private sector participation and membership in the Arctic Economic Council; explore renewable energy partnerships; share governance expertise related to indigenous communities.	5
4. Transportation and Connectivity	Participate in environmental monitoring and regulation for Arctic shipping; collaborate in shipbuilding (especially ice-class vessels); promote opportunities for Indian seafarers in Arctic transits; work towards linking the International North-South Transport Corridor (INSTC) with Arctic routes.	5
5. Governance and International Cooperation	Strengthen India's participation in the Arctic Council and other relevant international fora; contribute to the evolution of Arctic governance frameworks consistent with international law (especially UNCLOS); foster partnerships with Arctic states and other stakeholders.	5
6. National Capacity Building	Develop India's internal human, institutional, and financial capabilities to support its Arctic endeavors; advance the study and understanding of the Arctic within India; enhance cooperation across various sectors relevant to the Arctic.	5

The underlying philosophy of India's Arctic Policy is a commitment to "building a partnership for sustainable development".⁴ The stated motivations include the imperative to combat climate change, understand its profound impacts on India (particularly on the monsoons and the Himalayan cryosphere), seek sustainable economic opportunities that benefit both India and the Arctic region, foster international cooperation based on principles of international law, and systematically build national capacity to engage effectively with the Arctic's complexities.²

While science is a prominent driver, it is apparent that India's Arctic Policy and its associated scientific endeavors also function as instruments of diplomatic engagement, allowing India to maintain a constructive presence in a region of growing strategic significance. The policy's emphasis on science, sustainability, and international cooperation can be seen as a form of "scientific diplomacy," projecting India as a responsible stakeholder. However, some analysts suggest that the policy, while comprehensive in its scientific and environmental aspects, could be more assertive in articulating India's geo-economic and geopolitical aspirations, especially when compared to the approaches of other non-Arctic observer states like China, Japan, and South Korea.⁷ The very existence of a polar research vessel, for instance, while primarily for scientific tasks, also serves to highlight a nation's "global reach and interest spheres".¹

1.3. Scientific Infrastructure and Key Research Areas

Scientific research forms the bedrock of India's engagement in the Arctic, providing critical data for national needs, contributing to global scientific understanding, and serving as a platform for international collaboration.

Table 2: Overview of India's Arctic Scientific Infrastructure and Research Priorities

Category	Details	Key Focus Areas	Primary Sources
Research Station	Himadri Station: Ny-Alesund, Svalbard, Norway (est. 2008). Manned initially for ~180 days/year, now extended to >300 days/year with winter expeditions.	Atmospheric studies, glaciology, microbiology, marine ecosystems, climate change impacts, Arctic ecology.	1
Observatory	IndARC Observatory: Kongsfjorden, Svalbard (deployed 2014). First multi-sensor moored underwater observatory.	Long-term oceanographic and atmospheric data collection, climate monitoring, Arctic-Monsoon connections.	2
Laboratory	Gruvebadet Atmospheric Laboratory: Near Himadri, Svalbard (est. 2016). India's northernmost atmospheric lab.	Study of long-range pollutants, cloud formations, precipitation, Arctic atmospheric parameters.	4
Nodal Agency	National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research (NCPOR): Goa, India. Under Ministry of Earth Sciences.	Manages India's polar (Arctic, Antarctic, Himalayas) research programs and logistics.	4

Category	Details	Key Focus Areas	Primary Sources
Planned Assets	Polar Research Vessel: Objective in Arctic Policy to acquire a dedicated ice-class vessel and build indigenous construction capability.	To support multidisciplinary research in polar regions, enhance operational autonomy.	1
Key Research Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Arctic-Monsoon Linkage - Cryosphere Studies (Arctic-Himalaya comparison) - Biodiversity & Ecosystem Studies - Atmospheric Sciences & Pollution - Space Weather - Pathogens in Permafrost 	Understanding climate teleconnections, glacier dynamics, marine life, atmospheric processes, public health risks.	2
Recent Initiatives	<p>Winter Expeditions: Launched Dec 2023 for year-round data collection, especially during polar nights.</p> <p>International Collaboration : Joint projects/cruises with Norway (NPI), Canada</p>	Expanding temporal scope of research; leveraging international expertise and access.	8

Category	Details	Key Focus Areas	Primary Sources
	(POLAR), Russia, South Korea (KOPRI); participation in SAON, SIOS.		

A particularly crucial area of Indian research is the Arctic-Monsoon linkage. Scientists are investigating how rapid Arctic warming and the decline in sea ice extent influence atmospheric circulation patterns that, in turn, affect the Indian monsoon—a lifeline for India's agriculture, water resources, and overall economy.⁴ Studies suggest that melting Arctic ice can trigger Rossby waves in the atmosphere, altering pressure systems and impacting rainfall distribution over India.⁹

Another significant theme is cryosphere studies, with a unique focus on comparing Arctic glaciers with those in the Himalayas, often referred to as the "Third Pole".⁴ This comparative approach allows Indian scientists to leverage their considerable expertise in high-altitude Himalayan research to better understand glacier melt dynamics, freshwater availability, and the broader impacts of climate change in both polar and high-mountain regions. This "Third Pole" narrative provides India with a distinct and compelling justification for its Arctic engagement, differentiating it from many other non-Arctic states by highlighting direct impacts and a unique area of scientific contribution.¹ The "Interpolar Dialogue" initiative, linking the Arctic, Antarctic, and Himalayas, further institutionalizes this connection, fostering cross-regional learning.¹⁰

Fig. 2: Himadri, India's first and only all-year Arctic station in Ny Ålesund on Svalbard. It is operated by the National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research NCPOR since 2008. (Image: NCPOR)

India's commitment to enhancing its scientific capabilities is evident in recent initiatives. The launch of its first winter scientific expedition in December 2023, enabling research during the continuous polar night, marks a significant step towards maintaining a year-round operational presence at Himadri and collecting data previously unavailable. Furthermore, the Arctic Policy's objective to acquire a dedicated ice-class Polar Research Vessel and develop indigenous shipbuilding capabilities for such vessels is a critical long-term goal.¹ This would substantially enhance India's research autonomy and operational reach in the polar regions.

However, the pillar of "National Capacity Building" as outlined in the Arctic Policy faces challenges in its broader application beyond the scientific domain. While scientific capacity is being steadily augmented, the development of commercial and strategic assets, such as a fleet of ice-class commercial vessels or fostering significant private sector investment in

Arctic ventures, remains a considerable hurdle.⁴ This indicates a potential gap between the policy's ambition for comprehensive national capacity and the current state of diversified Arctic operational capabilities.

Fig. 3: First Batch of Indian Arctic Expedition, 2019-2020 in front of Himadri Station. The team (Dr. Dinesh, Dr. Prasanna Kumar, Dr. Anand, Ms. Aswathy, Dr. Jayu, Dr. Jasmine) will undertake microbiology, physical oceanography, zoology and geochemistry related studies in Arctic. (Image: NCPOR via Facebook)

2. Geopolitical and Strategic Dimensions of India's Arctic Ambitions

Beyond its scientific pursuits, India's engagement in the Arctic is increasingly shaped by a complex interplay of geopolitical considerations and strategic interests. As the Arctic transforms into an arena of heightened international attention, India is navigating these dynamics to secure its long-term national interests and enhance its global standing.

2.1. India's Strategic Calculus: Core Interests and Motivations

Several core interests underpin India's strategic calculus in the Arctic:

- **Energy Security:** As the world's third-largest energy consumer, importing approximately 83% of its oil and 50% of its gas, India has a vested interest in diversifying its energy sources.² The Arctic is estimated to hold substantial undiscovered hydrocarbon reserves – around 13-22% of the world's oil and 30% of its natural gas⁸ – making it a potentially significant future source to mitigate

dependency on traditional West Asian suppliers.¹¹

- Resource Access:** Beyond hydrocarbons, the Arctic is rich in various minerals, including copper, phosphorus, niobium, platinum group elements, and strategically important rare earth elements.² Access to these resources is crucial for India's industrial growth and technological advancement.
- New Trade Routes:** The opening of Arctic shipping lanes, particularly the Northern Sea Route (NSR), presents opportunities for shorter transit times and reduced shipping costs between Asia and Europe, offering an alternative to congested traditional chokepoints like the Suez Canal and the Strait of Malacca.¹
- Climate Change Impact Mitigation:** While primarily a scientific concern, understanding and predicting the impacts of Arctic climate change on India's monsoons, water security, and coastal regions is also a profound strategic imperative for national planning and resilience.⁴
- Geopolitical Balancing and Global Standing:** Engaging in Arctic affairs allows India to navigate its relationships with major global powers, project its influence in a new domain, and contribute to shaping the evolving governance architecture of the region. This is intrinsically linked to India's aspiration to be a "global power broker".¹ A significant driver for India's heightened Arctic attention is the growing presence and influence of China in the region. New Delhi is concerned that an unchecked Chinese expansion in the Arctic could divert the strategic focus of powers like the United States away from the Indo-Pacific, where India has more immediate security concerns. Furthermore, the prospect of

China utilizing new Arctic sea routes to bypass the Malacca Strait—a critical maritime chokepoint where India possesses some strategic leverage—is viewed with apprehension, as it could diminish India's ability to influence Chinese maritime movements in a potential conflict scenario (the "Malacca dilemma").¹

While India's 2022 Arctic Policy primarily emphasizes scientific, environmental, and developmental cooperation, these underlying strategic and security considerations are potent, albeit often "subtly embedded," drivers.⁶ The official focus on "softer" aspects might be a deliberate diplomatic choice to maintain a cooperative image, avoid antagonizing Arctic states, or reflect India's current limitations in projecting hard power in such a distant region. Nevertheless, analyses suggest that great power competition, the rise of China, and the imperative to secure national interests are influential factors in India's Arctic calculus.¹

2.2. Navigating Great Power Dynamics in the Arctic

India's Arctic strategy involves a delicate balancing act in its relationships with key global and regional players.

Table 3: India's Engagement with Key Arctic Actors and Fora

Actor/Forum	Nature of Engagement & Cooperation Areas	Strategic Interests for India	Challenges & Complexities	Primary Sources
Russia	Energy investments (OVL in Vankor, Yamal), NSR development	Primary partner for Arctic access, energy security, alternative	Over-reliance risks, Western sanctions impact	1

Actor/Forum	Nature of Engagement & Cooperation Areas	Strategic Interests for India	Challenges & Complexities	Primary Sources
	ment, potential naval port access, joint shipbuilding, scientific collaboration, training.	shipping routes, strategic depth.	(e.g., Arctic LNG 2), navigating Sino-Russian Arctic alignment, ensuring India's interests are prioritized.	
United States	Joint military exercises (Yudh Abhyas in Alaska), shared concerns over China, potential for scientific & technological cooperation.	Balancing China, access to advanced technology, strategic partnership in broader Indo-Pacific context.	US sanctions on Russian projects affecting Indian entities, differing perspectives on Russia's role.	1
Norway	Strong scientific collaboration (Himadri in Svalbard), diplomatic engagement, maritime	Key partner for scientific research, access to Arctic infrastructure and expertise, diplomatic support	Generally positive; ensuring alignment on broader Arctic governance issues.	1

Actor/Forum	Nature of Engagement & Cooperation Areas	Strategic Interests for India	Challenges & Complexities	Primary Sources
	energy sector focus.	within Arctic forums.		
Canada	Scientific collaboration (MoU with POLAR), engagement with Indian diaspora. Fieldwork by Indian scientists in Canadian High Arctic.	Access to diverse Arctic environments for research, potential for resource cooperation.	Maintaining momentum in scientific partnerships.	1
China (as non-Arctic actor)	Competitor and concern. Both are Arctic Council Observers. Limited direct cooperation.	Monitoring China's activities, countering potential strategic disadvantages (Malacca dilemma, Indo-Pacific focus dilution).	China's "Near-Arctic State" claim, "Polar Silk Road," growing Sino-Russian Arctic axis, resource competition.	1
Arctic Council	Active Observer: Attends meetings,	Platform for multilateral diplomacy,	Navigating Russia-West tensions within	1

Actor/Forum	Nature of Engagement & Cooperation Areas	Strategic Interests for India	Challenges & Complexities	Primary Sources
	contributes to Working Groups (e.g., CAFF, PAME, EPPR), engages with Task Forces.	influencing Arctic governance norms, scientific collaboration, showcasing responsible stakeholder image.	the Council, ensuring Observer voice is heard, translating participation into tangible influence.	

Relationship with Russia: Russia is undeniably a cornerstone of India's current Arctic strategy.¹ With the longest Arctic coastline and vast resource potential, Russia offers India critical access for energy exploration, participation in the development of the NSR, and potential for broader strategic cooperation, including discussions around Indian access to Russian naval port facilities in the Arctic.¹ Russia, particularly since the imposition of Western sanctions following its 2022 invasion of Ukraine, has actively courted India as a strategic partner in the Arctic, viewing it as a friendly power that can contribute capital and legitimacy to its Arctic development plans.¹ There are hopes in some Arctic circles that India could play a constructive role in managing relations with a potentially isolated Russia and act as a balancing influence, particularly vis-à-vis China's growing sway over Moscow.¹

However, this close relationship with Russia presents India with a significant "Russia dilemma." Over-reliance on Moscow carries risks, including potential alienation from Western Arctic partners (most of whom are NATO members and have severely curtailed cooperation with Russia), exposure to

secondary sanctions for Indian entities involved in Russian projects (as evidenced by sanctions on Indian shipping firms linked to the Arctic LNG 2 project¹²), and the danger of being drawn into Sino-Russian strategic alignments that may not fully serve India's long-term interests.¹ The growing military and economic cooperation between Russia and China in the Arctic is a particular concern, as it could subordinate India's interests if its engagement is too narrowly focused on Russia.¹

Engagement with Western Arctic States: India maintains important relationships with Western Arctic nations, primarily focused on scientific collaboration and diplomatic engagement. **Norway** stands out due to its hosting of the Himadri station in Svalbard and a burgeoning bilateral relationship with a strong Arctic focus.¹ The

United States is a key strategic partner for India in the broader Indo-Pacific, and this extends to some Arctic engagement, such as joint military exercises like 'Yudh Abhyas' conducted in Alaska.¹ With

Canada, cooperation includes scientific exchanges and fieldwork in the Canadian High Arctic.⁸ These Western partnerships are crucial for scientific advancement, accessing diverse Arctic environments, and potentially diversifying India's Arctic engagement beyond its heavy reliance on Russia. Some analysts suggest that India should more closely align its Arctic strategy with its Indo-Pacific vision, which emphasizes collaboration with democratic allies to uphold a rules-based order.¹³

The China Conundrum: China's expanding footprint and assertive posture in the Arctic are major factors shaping India's strategic approach.¹ Beijing's declaration of itself as a "Near-Arctic State" and its ambitious "Polar Silk Road" initiative (part of the Belt and Road Initiative) are viewed by New Delhi with considerable apprehension.² As previously noted, India fears that China's Arctic activities could provide it with alternative shipping routes that bypass traditional chokepoints like the Malacca Strait, thereby diminishing India's strategic leverage in the Indian Ocean.¹ The increasing strategic alignment

and joint military activities between China and Russia in the Arctic further complicate the geopolitical landscape for India.¹ Consequently, a significant element of India's Arctic strategy involves monitoring and potentially counterbalancing China's influence, often in concert with other concerned powers. The strategic dynamics of the Arctic are, for India, increasingly inseparable from those of the Indo-Pacific, with China's activities in both regions being interconnected. India's response in the Arctic is therefore partly aimed at mitigating potential negative spillover effects and countering China's multi-domain strategic expansion.

2.3. India's Role in Arctic Governance

As an Observer to the Arctic Council since 2013, India actively participates in its meetings and contributes to the work of its six Working Groups, which cover issues such as environmental protection, emergency preparedness, and sustainable development.⁴ India has also engaged with other Arctic-related forums like the Arctic Energy Summit and the Arctic Science Ministerial.¹⁴ Through these engagements, India advocates for the peaceful exploration and utilization of Arctic resources, emphasizing its commitment to international law, particularly the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), as the governing framework for the Arctic Ocean.⁶ India seeks to be perceived as a responsible and constructive stakeholder, contributing to the evolution of Arctic governance norms while ensuring that its legitimate interests are considered and accommodated.

2.4. Pursuit of Strategic Autonomy and a "Balancing" Role

India's Arctic policy is intrinsically linked to its broader foreign policy doctrine of "strategic autonomy," which emphasizes maintaining independence in its foreign policy choices and engaging with multiple power centers based on its national interests.¹⁵ The Arctic provides another arena for India to practice this multi-alignment, positioning itself as "non-West but not anti-West".¹ There is an expectation, both internally

and among some international observers, that India could leverage its unique position and relationships to act as a balancing power or a bridge between Russia and the West, and also to temper China's influence in the region.¹ The Arctic thus serves as a test case for India's ability to navigate complex geopolitical terrains involving deeply entrenched and often conflicting interests of major powers, requiring sophisticated diplomacy and a clear articulation of its own core objectives versus peripheral opportunities.

3. Economic Interests and Connectivity Ventures

India's engagement with the Arctic is increasingly driven by economic considerations, primarily focusing on the region's vast resource potential and the emerging opportunities presented by new Arctic shipping routes. These interests are pursued with a stated commitment to sustainability and international cooperation, though significant challenges remain in translating potential into tangible economic benefits.

3.1. Resource Potential: Hydrocarbons and Minerals

The Arctic region is endowed with significant untapped natural resources. Estimates suggest it may hold as much as 13% of the world's undiscovered oil and 30% of its undiscovered natural gas, according to the US Geological Survey and other assessments.⁸ Beyond hydrocarbons, the region is also rich in various minerals, including copper, phosphorus, niobium, platinum group elements, and substantial deposits of rare earth elements, which are critical for modern technologies.² For India, a rapidly growing economy and one of the world's largest energy importers, these resources represent a significant opportunity to diversify its energy portfolio and reduce its heavy dependence on traditional suppliers in West Asia.²

Indian investments in Arctic resources have primarily been channeled through state-owned enterprises (PSUs). ONGC Videsh Ltd (OVL), the overseas arm

of India's national oil company, along with other PSUs like Indian Oil Corporation, Bharat Petroresources, and Oil India Ltd, have been at the forefront of these ventures.¹⁶ OVL has made notable investments in Russian oil and gas projects, including stakes in Sakhalin-1 and Vankorneft (a 15% stake acquired in 2015 significantly enhanced India's presence on the Arctic energy map).¹⁶ India has invested approximately \$15-16 billion in Russia's oil and gas sector overall, with a portion of this directed towards projects in the Arctic and Russia's Far East, including the Yamal LNG project.¹⁶ However, direct Indian participation in newer projects like Russia's Arctic LNG 2 has been constrained by international sanctions, with India officially stating it would not purchase LNG from this sanctioned project.¹²

While some Indian private sector companies, such as Reliance Industries and Deepak Fertilisers, reportedly purchase Arctic-origin crude oil, their direct investment in Arctic exploration and extraction activities remains limited.⁴ India's Arctic Policy (2022) explicitly encourages Indian businesses to explore opportunities and participate in forums like the Arctic Economic Council and its various working groups focusing on areas such as the blue economy, maritime transportation, and responsible resource development.⁴ Despite this encouragement, actual private sector investment has been slow to materialize, reflecting the high costs, long gestation periods, and significant geopolitical risks associated with Arctic ventures.

3.2. Arctic Shipping Routes: Opportunities and Challenges for India

The progressive melting of Arctic Sea ice is opening up new maritime corridors, most notably the Northern Sea Route (NSR), which runs along Russia's northern coastline.

The Northern Sea Route (NSR): The NSR offers the potential for a significantly shorter shipping passage between ports in Europe and Asia compared to traditional routes via the Suez Canal or around the

Cape of Good Hope, potentially reducing transit times by up to 40% and lowering fuel consumption and emissions.² India's Arctic Policy acknowledges the NSR as a vital emerging shipping route that could reshape global maritime trade.¹⁷ The economic feasibility of the NSR for India is, however, a subject of ongoing assessment. While some analyses highlight potential benefits, others suggest that the NSR may not offer significant time or distance advantages for India compared to East Asian nations like China, Japan, and South Korea, which are geographically better positioned to leverage it.² Moreover, the route's viability is currently hampered by a lack of specialized ice-breaking commercial vessels in the global fleet, insufficient port infrastructure along the Russian Arctic coast, the seasonal nature of navigation (though year-round navigation is a Russian goal), and the high costs associated with icebreaker escorts and insurance.¹⁸ Consequently, the NSR is generally considered a long-term prospect rather than an immediate economic boon for India, requiring substantial investment in capacity building and infrastructure development.¹⁸ India has expressed interest in collaborating with Russia on the development of the NSR, including joint shipbuilding initiatives, training for Indian seafarers in polar navigation, and exploring cargo transit possibilities.¹⁹ A key strategic interest for India is linking the NSR with the International North-South Transport Corridor (INSTC), a multi-modal network connecting India with Russia via Iran and Central Asia, to create a more integrated trade network.²

The Chennai-Vladivostok Maritime Corridor (CVMC):

Complementing its interest in the NSR, India is actively developing the Chennai-Vladivostok Maritime Corridor (CVMC). This proposed sea route, spanning approximately 5,600 nautical miles (10,300 km), aims to significantly enhance bilateral trade between India and Russia's Far East. A Memorandum of Intent for the CVMC was signed in September 2019, and the corridor reportedly became operational in November 2024, carrying cargoes such as oil, food, and machinery.²⁰ The CVMC is

projected to reduce cargo transport time between Indian ports and Vladivostok from around 40 days to approximately 24 days.²⁰ This corridor holds strategic importance as it can serve as an eastern gateway for India to Russia, with Vladivostok potentially acting as a trans-shipment hub for goods extending further north via the NSR.²

The development of these Arctic and sub-Arctic shipping routes, while often framed in terms of economic benefits, may currently hold greater strategic value for India. They offer pathways for trade diversification, reduce over-reliance on traditional maritime chokepoints vulnerable to disruption, strengthen strategic ties with Russia (particularly its resource-rich Far East), and signal India's intent to be an active maritime player in new and emerging geographies. The substantial economic returns from these ventures appear to be a longer-term aspiration, contingent upon overcoming numerous infrastructural, financial, and geopolitical hurdles.

Fig. 4: The classic Suez Canal Route (blue) and the INTSC (red) are two of the main Russo-Indian trade routes. (Graphics: Wikicommons, CC BY-SA 3.0)

3.3. Developing National Capacity for Polar Operations

A critical component of realizing India's Arctic economic ambitions is the development of indigenous national capacity for polar operations. India's Arctic Policy includes the key objective of acquiring a dedicated ice-class Polar Research Vessel and, significantly, building indigenous capabilities for the construction of such specialized

vessels.¹ This reflects a long-term vision for self-reliance in polar research and operations. Collaboration in shipbuilding with international partners possessing expertise in constructing ice-class vessels suitable for polar conditions is also envisaged.⁵ Notably, Russia has reportedly selected India over China for the construction of a new class of non-nuclear icebreakers, which could provide a significant boost to India's shipbuilding industry and polar operational capabilities.¹⁵

The policy also aims to promote opportunities for Indian seafarers to crew ships engaged in Arctic transits, thereby building a skilled maritime workforce familiar with polar conditions.⁵ Effective navigation in the Arctic requires specialized hydrographic and oceanographic data, robust maritime safety facilities, and reliable satellite coverage, areas where India aims to participate and contribute.¹⁷ India's national space capabilities, including its RISAT series of radar imaging earth observation satellites and the IRNSS regional navigation satellite system, are seen as valuable assets that can be deployed to support Arctic studies and enhance maritime safety in the region.²¹ Furthermore, India's Maritime India Vision 2030, which aims to elevate the country's global shipbuilding ranking, aligns with the opportunities presented by emerging Arctic routes and the need for specialized vessel construction, supported by budgetary allocations for shipbuilding infrastructure.¹⁷

However, the path to robust national capacity for Arctic economic engagement faces a "chicken and egg" dilemma. Significant upfront investment in specialized infrastructure (ice-class commercial fleets, port upgrades, resilient supply chains) is necessary to make Arctic ventures commercially viable. Yet, such large-scale investment is often hesitant in the absence of proven profitability and stable, predictable geopolitical and environmental conditions. This creates a cycle where the vast potential of the Arctic remains under-realized due to the high initial costs and perceived risks, particularly for the private sector.

3.4. Role of Public and Private Sector Enterprises

Currently, India's economic footprint in the Arctic is predominantly driven by its public sector undertakings (PSUs), particularly in the energy sector through investments in Russian projects.¹⁶ India's Arctic Policy actively encourages greater participation from the private sector, urging Indian companies to explore investment opportunities and to join bodies like the Arctic Economic Council to engage with its working groups on various aspects of Arctic commerce.⁴

Despite this policy push, private sector investment in the Arctic remains notably low.⁴ This reticence can be attributed to several factors, including the high capital expenditure required, the long gestation periods for returns, the harsh operating environment, and, critically, the significant geopolitical risks. The sanctioning of two Indian private shipping firms, Skyhart Management Services and Avison Shipping Services, by the United States in January 2025 for their alleged involvement in transporting LNG from Russia's sanctioned Arctic LNG 2 project serves as a stark illustration of these risks.¹² Such actions create a climate of uncertainty and can deter private capital, even if the activities align with the Indian government's policy of continued economic engagement with Russia. This underscores the challenge of mobilizing private enterprise for Arctic ventures and highlights the need for robust de-risking mechanisms and a more concerted effort by industry bodies, as suggested by calls for Indian chambers of commerce like CII, FICCI, and Assocham to shed their reticence and actively propel an "Arctic outlook" among their members.¹⁶

4. Social, Environmental, and Cultural Aspects

India's engagement with the Arctic extends beyond geopolitics and economics to encompass significant social, environmental, and cultural dimensions. These aspects are deeply intertwined with India's own vulnerabilities to climate change and its

commitment to sustainable development and international cooperation.

4.1. The Arctic-Himalaya ("Third Pole") Connection: Climate Impacts on India

A cornerstone of India's Arctic narrative is the profound and scientifically recognized connection between climate change in the Arctic and its impacts on the Himalayan cryosphere – often termed the "Third Pole" – and, by extension, on India's overall environmental and economic security.¹ The rapid warming of the Arctic and the associated melt of sea ice and glaciers have far-reaching consequences for global weather patterns. For India, this translates into direct impacts on the Indian monsoon, which is the lifeblood for its agriculture (nearly 60% of which is rain-fed), water resources, and the livelihoods of millions.²

Research indicates that changes in Arctic sea ice levels can lead to increased variability in monsoon rainfall, potentially causing both severe droughts and devastating floods in different parts of India.⁹ Rising global sea levels, exacerbated by melting Arctic and Antarctic ice sheets as well as Himalayan glaciers, pose a direct threat to India's extensive coastline and its numerous island territories, impacting vulnerable communities and ecosystems.⁴ The health of Himalayan glaciers, which are critical sources of freshwater for major river systems in North India, is also intricately linked to broader climate patterns influenced by Arctic changes.⁴ These interconnected climatic impacts underscore why Arctic research is not merely an academic pursuit for India but a matter of urgent national concern.

Furthermore, the thawing of Arctic permafrost carries the potential risk of releasing ancient, dormant pathogens (viruses and bacteria) into the environment, which could increase the probability of new pandemics with global reach.⁵ This "Third Pole" linkage provides a compelling scientific and empathetic justification for India's Arctic engagement. However, it may also inadvertently draw attention to India's own vulnerabilities and the

immense resource requirements for addressing climate impacts within its immediate Himalayan region, potentially leading to domestic discussions about resource allocation between national adaptation needs and international Arctic research initiatives. The key will be to continuously demonstrate the tangible benefits of Arctic research for understanding and mitigating impacts on India and the Himalayan ecosystem.

Fig. 5: The Indus-Ganges Plain in Northeast India. Fed by the glaciers of the Himalayan, the two major river systems are the most important water sources in India. (Image: Wikicommons CC BY-SA 3.0)

4.2. Environmental Stewardship: India's Stance

Reflecting global concerns about the fragility of the Arctic ecosystem, India's Arctic Policy prominently features climate and environmental protection and sustainable development as central pillars.¹⁷ India has committed to enhancing its engagement with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within the Arctic context and aims to contribute to the preservation of Arctic biodiversity.⁵ Specific objectives include participating in research on ecosystem values, marine protected areas, and traditional knowledge systems to conserve Arctic flora and fauna, and contributing to environmental management efforts addressing issues such as methane and black carbon emissions, micro-plastics, and marine litter.⁵

India also intends to promote the adoption of high environmental standards by its enterprises when they engage in scientific or economic activities in the Arctic region. Collaboration with various Arctic Council Working Groups, such as the Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF), Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME), and Emergency Prevention, Preparedness and Response (EPPR), is a key mechanism through which India seeks to contribute to regional environmental governance.⁴ This emphasis on environmental stewardship aligns with global norms and serves to enhance India's image as a responsible international actor. Such a stance can also be a subtle geopolitical tool, allowing India to engage constructively in Arctic governance forums and differentiate its approach from actors perceived as primarily resource-driven or geopolitically assertive, thereby fostering trust and cooperation with Arctic states, particularly the Nordic countries.

4.3. Engagement with Indigenous Communities

India's Arctic Policy articulates an intention to engage with the indigenous communities of the Arctic. Stated objectives include sharing India's expertise in the governance and welfare of indigenous and other local communities, and undertaking cultural and educational exchanges between the indigenous peoples of India's Himalayan glacial regions and those of the Arctic.⁴ The policy aims to ensure that any economic development pursued in the Arctic is sustainable and respects the rights, traditions, and livelihoods of Arctic residents, including its diverse indigenous populations.⁴

However, available information suggests that while the policy intent is clear, the specific details and extent of India's actual interaction and collaboration with Arctic indigenous communities are not widely documented.⁴ International best practices in Arctic engagement increasingly emphasize the importance of co-production of knowledge, which involves integrating Indigenous Knowledge systems with

scientific research through equitable partnerships, ensuring Indigenous leadership in research, and respecting Indigenous data sovereignty.²² While the "Interpolar Dialogue" initiative, which connects Arctic and Himalayan communities, aims to honor cultural wisdom and local perspectives¹⁰, there appears to be a gap between the aspirational goals of India's policy regarding indigenous engagement and the current level of demonstrable, impactful programs. This represents an area with significant potential for future development, allowing India to contribute more meaningfully to the social fabric of the Arctic and learn from the rich traditional knowledge of its inhabitants.

4.4. Cultural and Educational Exchanges

Closely linked to engagement with indigenous communities is the broader aim of fostering cultural and educational exchanges. India's Arctic Policy explicitly includes the objective "To undertake cultural and educational exchanges between the indigenous communities of the glacial regions of the Himalayas and the Arctic".⁵ This vision is being advanced through initiatives like the "Interpolar Dialogue" and the concept of a "cryosphere corridor," which seek to build bridges of cooperation and understanding, linking the frozen realms of the Arctic and the Third Pole through shared learning and resilience planning, emphasizing human and cultural dimensions.¹⁰

In terms of educational collaboration, the University of the Arctic, a cooperative network of universities, colleges, and research institutions concerned with education and research in and about the North, welcomed students from India in 2019, providing them with opportunities to participate in Arctic-related courses and research networks.⁴ Even India's research stations, like Himadri, have been framed as "emissaries of the nation's cultural heritage," for instance, by participating in global events like the Ocean Ring of Yoga.¹⁶ These initiatives, while perhaps modest in scale currently, aim to build people-to-people connections and facilitate

knowledge sharing that transcends purely scientific or governmental channels, enriching India's understanding of the Arctic and fostering mutual respect.

5. Challenges, Opportunities, and the Path Forward for India in the Arctic

India's Arctic ambitions, while growing, are set against a backdrop of significant geopolitical, operational, and financial challenges. Successfully navigating this complex environment will require astute diplomacy, sustained investment in capacity building, and a clear-sighted balancing of national interests with global responsibilities.

5.1. Navigating Geopolitical Tensions and Evolving Security Environment

The Arctic is no longer the zone of "exceptionalism" and low tension it was once perceived to be.¹ The deterioration in relations between Russia and Western Arctic states, particularly following Russia's 2022 invasion of Ukraine, has profoundly impacted regional cooperation. The Arctic Council, for instance, saw a temporary suspension of cooperation with Russia by the other seven Arctic states (the A7).¹ For India, this presents a major challenge: how to balance its crucial strategic partnership with Russia – its primary gateway to Arctic resources and routes – against its relationships with Western Arctic nations, many of whom are NATO members and view Russia's Arctic posture with deep suspicion.¹

The growing strategic cooperation between Russia and China in the Arctic is another layer of complexity for India.¹ While India seeks to maintain its own distinct partnership with Russia, it must guard against being subsumed within a broader Sino-Russian agenda that may not align with its interests. Furthermore, there are increasing concerns about the potential militarization of the Arctic, with several Arctic states, including Russia, enhancing their military presence and capabilities in the region.¹

Although military security was explicitly excluded from the Arctic Council's mandate, which many attribute to its past success in fostering cooperation¹, the spill-over of global tensions into the Arctic is undeniable. India, with limited hard power projection capabilities in the region, must rely on diplomatic acumen to navigate these security dynamics. The Arctic, therefore, serves as a demanding test case for India's foreign policy doctrine of "multi-alignment," requiring it to engage with diverse and often rivalrous powers simultaneously while safeguarding its core interests.

5.2. Addressing Operational, Technological, and Financial Challenges

Realizing Arctic ambitions necessitates overcoming significant practical hurdles. Arctic operations are inherently expensive due to the harsh climate, remote locations, and the need for specialized equipment and logistics.¹⁸ India's funding for Arctic research, while dedicated, is modest in comparison to the scale of the region and the costs involved (approximately Rs. 39 Crores, or roughly \$4.7 million, over a recent five-year period).²³

A critical technological challenge is the requirement for specialized infrastructure, particularly icebreakers and ice-class commercial vessels for resource transportation and navigation through Arctic waters.¹⁷ While India's Arctic Policy includes the goal of acquiring a polar research vessel and developing indigenous construction capabilities¹, its commercial fleet currently lacks significant ice-class capacity. This necessitates substantial investment and technology transfer.

Furthermore, private sector investment in Indian Arctic ventures remains limited, constrained by high costs, long return horizons, and geopolitical uncertainties.⁴ Building a robust pool of human resources with expertise in polar operations, Arctic engineering, and specialized maritime skills is another long-term requirement.¹⁹ These operational, technological, and financial challenges underscore the need for a sustained, strategic commitment to

capacity building if India is to move beyond a primarily scientific or symbolic presence.

5.3. Balancing Economic Aspirations with Environmental Sustainability and Indigenous Rights

As India explores economic opportunities in the Arctic, including resource extraction and the use of new shipping routes, it faces the critical challenge of aligning these aspirations with its stated commitments to environmental sustainability and the rights of indigenous communities.⁴ The Arctic ecosystem is exceptionally fragile, and increased economic activity carries inherent risks of pollution, habitat disruption, and other environmental damage. India's credibility as a responsible Arctic stakeholder will heavily depend on its ability to ensure that any commercial activities undertaken by its entities adhere to the highest environmental standards and contribute to the sustainable development of the region.

Meaningfully engaging with and incorporating the perspectives and rights of Arctic indigenous communities is another vital aspect.⁴ While India's policy expresses intent in this regard, translating this into concrete, respectful, and mutually beneficial partnerships requires dedicated effort and a deeper understanding of indigenous knowledge systems and governance structures.²²

5.4. Strengthening International Partnerships and Multilateral Engagement

Given its status as a non-Arctic state, international partnerships are indispensable for India to achieve its Arctic objectives. This involves deepening cooperation with key Arctic states on multiple fronts: with **Russia** for energy, resources, and NSR access¹; with **Norway** for scientific research, particularly in Svalbard, and maritime expertise¹; with **Canada** and the **USA** for scientific collaboration and broader strategic alignment.¹

Enhancing India's participation and influence within the Arctic Council and its working groups remains a priority. Beyond the Council, India should explore opportunities for plurilateral collaborations, potentially with Nordic countries as a bloc, or within frameworks like BRICS, where Russia has indicated an interest in fostering Arctic endeavors.¹ Some analysts also advocate for aligning India's Arctic strategy more closely with its Indo-Pacific partnerships, particularly with democratic allies who share concerns about a rules-based order in contested global commons.¹³

5.5. Outlook and Strategic Considerations

Looking ahead, India's Arctic footprint will likely continue to expand, driven by the enduring factors of climate change research, energy security needs, and geopolitical positioning. The acquisition of a dedicated polar-class research vessel is a probable and significant step, enhancing both research capabilities and symbolic presence.¹ The potential for increased, albeit cautious, military-to-military cooperation, such as access to Russian naval facilities or participation in Arctic-focused exercises (like the Yudh Abhyas in Alaska), may also feature in India's strategic toolkit, primarily for capacity building and diplomatic signaling.¹

A key imperative for India will be to move beyond a primarily scientific or reactive posture to a more clearly defined political and strategic vision for its role in the Arctic.¹ This involves articulating what India wants to achieve politically and how it intends to leverage its unique strengths – such as its "Third Pole" expertise and its position as a major developing nation with a tradition of independent foreign policy – to contribute to regional stability and governance. The call for a more explicit "strategic and geopolitical pillar" in India's Arctic policy reflects this need.²

Ultimately, effective Arctic engagement for India will necessitate a more robust and coordinated interface between government policy, scientific research institutions, and private industry.¹⁶ Bridging the

current disconnects and fostering an "environment of enterprise" in polar affairs will be crucial for translating scientific knowledge and policy goals into tangible commercial ventures and strategic assets. Without a significant ramp-up in tangible national capacities beyond the purely scientific realm—encompassing economic, technological, and operational dimensions—India risks remaining a largely symbolic or niche player in the unfolding Arctic story.

6. Conclusion: Synthesizing India's Arctic Vision

India's journey in the Arctic, from its early association as a signatory to the Svalbard Treaty in 1920 to its current status as an active Arctic Council Observer with a formal, multifaceted policy, reflects a nation increasingly attuned to the region's profound global significance. The Arctic is no longer a distant periphery, but an arena intrinsically linked to India's core national interests and its aspirations on the world stage.

The primary drivers of India's Arctic engagement are threefold: **scientific inquiry**, particularly focused on understanding the critical linkages between Arctic climate change and the Indian monsoon system, as well as the health of the Himalayan cryosphere; **economic opportunities**, centered on the potential for accessing vital energy and mineral resources and leveraging new Arctic shipping routes like the NSR and CVMC to enhance trade connectivity; and **geopolitical considerations**, which involve navigating complex great power dynamics, managing the strategic implications of China's growing regional presence, and asserting India's role as a responsible global actor committed to strategic autonomy.

India's Arctic ambitions are characterized by an endeavor to balance the pursuit of national interests with a commitment to sustainable development, environmental protection, and adherence to international law. The 2022 Arctic Policy, "Building a

Partnership for Sustainable Development," provides the official framework for this engagement, emphasizing a cooperative and science-led approach. However, underlying this formal posture are significant strategic calculations influenced by the evolving security environment in the Arctic and the broader shifts in global power equations.

India's approach to the Arctic serves as a clear microcosm of its overarching foreign policy strategy of multi-alignment. It seeks to build and maintain constructive partnerships with a diverse array of actors, including Russia, the United States, and key European Arctic states, while simultaneously addressing the challenges posed by China's expanding influence. The unique "Third Pole" narrative, linking Arctic changes to the Himalayas, provides a distinctive and compelling justification for its engagement, allowing India to contribute specialized knowledge and highlight its direct stake in the region's future.

Despite the growing discourse and policy articulation, India's Arctic vision appears to be fundamentally about laying a robust foundation for long-term engagement rather than expecting immediate, transformative geopolitical or economic gains. The current emphasis on strengthening scientific research, formulating comprehensive policy, incrementally building national capacity (such as the planned acquisition of a polar research vessel), and engaging in cautious diplomatic maneuvering suggests a patient, strategic, and incremental approach. This is well-suited to a region where India's direct operational leverage is currently limited, but whose future strategic, economic, and environmental importance is undeniable.

The Arctic is more than just a new frontier of interest for India; it is an arena where the nation's scientific capabilities, economic aspirations, diplomatic skills, and its vision of a multipolar, rules-based international order are being actively tested and projected. Success in this complex and rapidly changing region will require sustained political will, significant investment in diverse capacities, and an

adaptive strategy that can effectively navigate the evolving challenges and opportunities of the 21st-century Arctic.

* Dr. Michael Wenger is an independent researcher, a marine biologist, and a former CEO of Polarjournal AG

7. References

1. Arctic Council. (n.d.). *Co-production of knowledge in the Arctic: Bridging Indigenous and scientific perspectives*. Retrieved from <https://arctic-council.org/news/co-production-of-knowledge-in-the-arctic-bridging-indigenous-and-scientific-perspectives/>
2. Arctic Council. (2013, May 15). *Kiruna Declaration*.
3. Armbruster, B. (2023, August 15). How US media builds public support for confrontation with China. *Brave New Europe*. Retrieved from <https://braveneweuropa.com/ben-armbruster-how-us-media-builds-public-support-for-confrontation-with-china>
4. Business Standard. (2025, January 12). Two Indian firms sanctioned by US for 'aiding' Russia's Arctic LNG project. *Business Standard*. Retrieved from https://www.business-standard.com/companies/news/indian-ship-firms-us-sanctions-russia-arctic-ling-project-skyhart-avision-125011200177_1.html
5. Chatterjee, S. (2024, October). *China and the Arctic: An Overview*. Observer Research Foundation.
6. Chattopadhyay, S. (2023, November 5). Time to redraw India's Arctic investments. *The Sunday Guardian Live*. Retrieved from

- <https://sundayguardianlive.com/investigatio/n/time-to-redraw-indias-arctic-investments>
7. Chaudhury, D. R. (2018, July 12). Chennai-Vladivostok sea route: India's effort to counter China's OBOR could soon get a big Russian helping hand. *The Economic Times*. Retrieved from <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/new/s/defence/chennai-vladivostok-sea-route-indias-effort-to-counter-chinas-obor-could-soon-get-a-big-russian-helping-hand/articleshow/64954824.cms>
 8. China, People's Republic of. (2018). *China's Arctic Policy* (White Paper). State Council Information Office.
 9. Daily Pioneer. (2025, May). The northern sea route emerges as a climate-friendly trade corridor. *The Pioneer*. Retrieved from <https://www.dailypioneer.com/2025/columnists/the-northern-sea-route-emerges-as-a-climate-friendly-trade-corridor.html>
 10. Drishti IAS. (n.d.). *India and the Dynamism of Arctic Region*. Retrieved from <https://www.drishtias.com/daily-updates/daily-news-analysis/india-and-the-dynamism-of-arctic-region>
 11. Edvardsen, A. (2023, April 14). Russia Wants to Cooperate With BRICS Countries on Research on Svalbard. *High North News*. Retrieved from <https://www.highnorthnews.com/en/russia-wants-cooperate-brics-countries-research-svalbard>
 12. Ensure IAS. (n.d.). *Arctic Sea Ice Influence on Indian Monsoon Patterns*. Retrieved from <https://www.ensureias.com/blog/current-affairs/arctic-sea-ice-influence-on-indian-monsoon-patterns>
 13. ETV Bharat. (2025, January 2). Explained: Importance of India engagement with Arctic nations. *ETV Bharat*. Retrieved from <https://www.etvbharat.com/en!/opinion/exp/ained-importance-of-india-engagement-with-arctic-nations-enn25010205774>
 14. Ganapathy, N. (2025, February 18). India ramps up scientific engagement in the Arctic as global players jockey for influence. *The Straits Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.straitstimes.com/asia/south-asia/india-ramps-up-scientific-engagement-in-the-arctic-as-global-players-jockey-for-influence>
 15. Government of India, Ministry of Defence. (2023, September). *Exercise Yudh Abhyas-23 Set to Commence in Fort Wainwright, Alaska, USA - Indian Contingent Departs* (Press Release ID: 1960137). Press Information Bureau. Retrieved from (<https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1960137>)
 16. Government of India, Ministry of Earth Sciences. (2022, March 17). *India's Arctic Policy: Building a Partnership for Sustainable Development*. New Delhi. Retrieved from (<https://www.moes.gov.in/sites/default/files/2022-03/compressed-SINGLE-PAGE-ENGLISH.pdf>)
 17. Government of India, Ministry of Earth Sciences. (2023, December 18). *Honourable Union Minister Sh Kiren Rijju launches India's maiden winter scientific Arctic expedition* (Press Release ID: 1987724). Press Information Bureau. Retrieved from (<https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1987724>)
 18. Government of India, Ministry of Earth Sciences. (2025, February 13). *Lok Sabha Unstarred Question No. 2342: Research in Arctic Circle*. Press Information Bureau. Retrieved

- from(<https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2102740>)
19. High North News. (2022, April 6). Op-ed: India's Arctic Policy: Strong foothold on science and business interests. *High North News*. Retrieved from <https://www.highnorthnews.com/en/indias-arctic-policy-strong-foothold-science-and-business-interests>
 20. Indian National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research (NCPOR). (n.d.). *India in Arctic*. Retrieved from <https://ncpor.res.in/arctics/pages/background>
 21. Indian National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research (NCPOR). (n.d.). *National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research*. Retrieved from <https://ncpor.res.in/>
 22. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC). (n.d.). *Arctic Research Plan 2022-2026: Introduction and Background*. Retrieved from <https://www.iarpcollaborations.org/plan/introduction-and-background.html>
 23. Jakobson, L. (2010). China Prepares for an Ice-Free Arctic. *SIPRI Insights on Peace and Security, No. 2010/2*.
 24. Kaur, A. (2024, January). *India's Arctic Policy: A Legal Framework for a Sustainable Approach*. The Arctic Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.thearcticinstitute.org/india-arctic-legal-framework-sustainable-approach/>
 25. Khorrami, N., & Østhagen, A. (2025, April). *India in the Arctic: A Potential Pathway to Strategic Autonomy Beyond Russia*. ORF Occasional Paper No. 474. Observer Research Foundation. Retrieved from <https://www.orfonline.org/research/india-in-the-arctic-a-potential-pathway-to-strategic-autonomy-beyond-russia>
 26. Khorrami, N., & Østhagen, A. (2025, June 5). *India in the Arctic: Advancing a Path for Strategic Autonomy Beyond Russia*. The Arctic Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.thearcticinstitute.org/india-arctic-advancing-path-strategic-autonomy-beyond-russia/>
 27. Kim, M. J. (2025, April 7). *The Arctic and Northern Sea Route: A New Frontier for India-South Korea Cooperation*. Korea Centre, Observer Research Foundation. Retrieved from <https://koreacentre.org/2025/04/07/the-arctic-and-northern-sea-route-a-new-frontier-for-india-south-korea-cooperation/>
 28. Kumar, S. (2025, May 19). *Arctic Circle India Forum Connects Arctic and "Third Pole" Himalayas for Climate Action*. Sasakawa Peace Foundation, Ocean Policy Research Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.spf.org/opri/en/news/20250519.html>
 29. Lackenbauer, P. W., & Manicom, J. (2013). India's Arctic Engagement: Emerging Perspectives. *Arctic Yearbook 2013*. Retrieved from (https://arcticyearbook.com/images/yearbook/2013/Scholarly_Papers/1.LACKENBAUER.pdf)
 30. Mahapatra, A. K. (2022, February 22). *India's Arctic Security Dimension: 'Thought through' or 'a Remedial Process to Address an Insecurity'*. The Arctic Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.thearcticinstitute.org/india-arctic-security-dimension-thought-through-remedial-process-address-insecurity/>
 31. Mohan, C. R. (2024)..

32. Nelson, M. (2022, September 27). Coast Guard Spots Chinese and Russian Military Ships Together in Bering Sea. *Alaska Public Media/KSKA*. Retrieved from <https://alaskapublic.org/news/2022-09-27/coast-guard-spots-chinese-and-russian-military-ships-together-in-bering-sea>
33. Nilsen, T. (2023, April 28). Russia's Coast Guard Cooperation with China Is a Big Step, Arctic Security Expert Says. *The Barents Observer*. Retrieved from <https://thebarentsobserver.com/en/security/2023/04/russias-arctic-coast-guard-cooperation-china-big-step-expert>
34. Observer Research Foundation. (2021, July 12). *Introducing the Arctic as a strategic geopolitical pillar for India*. Retrieved from <https://www.orfonline.org/research/introducing-the-arctic-as-a-strategic-geopolitical-pillar-for-india>
35. Observer Research Foundation. (n.d.). *Understanding the potential of the Northern Sea Route*. Retrieved from <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/understanding-the-potential-of-the-northern-sea-route>
36. Østhagen, A. (2024). Great Power Competition in the Arctic and the Role of India. *Strategic Analysis*, 48(6), 619-633. DOI: 10.1080/09700161.2025.2450998
37. Pant, H. V. (2017, June 22). India Challenges China's Belt-Road Intentions. *YaleGlobal Online*. Retrieved from <https://archive-yaleglobal.yale.edu/content/india-challenges-chinas-belt-road-intentions>
38. Pareek, M. (2022). India's Arctic Policy: The Historical Context. *Arctic and North*, 48, 100-117.
39. Rachmawati, R. N., & Taneja, P. (2025). *The Arctic Region: National Interests and Policies of India and China*. *Journal of Liberty and International Affairs*.
40. Raisina House. (n.d.). *India's Arctic Policy: A Pathway to Sustainable Engagement*. Retrieved from <https://raisinahouse.org/f/indias-arctic-policy-a-pathway-to-sustainable-engagement>
41. Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS). (2023). *India's Arctic Policy: Contours of its Engagements in the Region*. SDR Newsletter. Retrieved from <https://ris.org.in/newsletter/sdr/2023/Article-1.pdf>
42. Roche, E. (2021, February 14). Maritime corridor, trade on Shringla's Russia visit agenda. *Mint*. Retrieved from <https://www.livemint.com/news/india/maritime-corridor-trade-on-shringla-s-russia-visit-agenda-11613238424308.html>
43. Roy, S. (2025, March 7). *China and Russia's Involvement in the Arctic: Geopolitical and Security Implications for the United States and its Allies*. Air University, Air Force Culture and Language Center. Retrieved from (https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/Portals/10/AFCLC/07.%20Media/Arctic%20Research/China%20and%20Russia's%20Involvement%20in%20the%20Arctic%20Report_v08a%20-%207%20March%202025_Final.pdf?ver=NHFCEvkNsmtG-L9o0hjTA%3D%3Dx)
44. Sahu, A. (2020, November 13). *The West should encourage India to become Russia's Arctic alternative to China*. *ArcticToday*. Retrieved from <https://www.arctictoday.com/the-west->

- [should-encourage-india-to-become-russias-arctic-alternative-to-china/](#)
45. Sakhuja, V. (2011)..
 46. Sharma, B. (2021, November 25). High Time for India's First Polar Research Vessel. *IDS Comment*. Retrieved from <https://www.idsa.in/idsacomments/indias-first-polar-research-vessel-bsharma-251121>
 47. Singh, A., & Østhagen, A. (2024, April 16). India's Arctic Imperative. *The Hindu*. Retrieved from <https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/op-ed/indias-arctic-imperative/article68067583.ece>
 48. Stephen, K., & Knecht, S. (Eds.). (2017). *Governing Arctic Change: Global Perspectives*. Palgrave Macmillan.
 49. Srivastava, V. (2023, December 29). Why Indian scientists are on a winter voyage to the Arctic. *Nature India*. DOI: 10.1038/d44151-023-00203-z
 50. Stensrud, C. J., & Østhagen, A. (2024). Hybrid Warfare at Sea? Russia, Svalbard and the Arctic. *Scandinavian Journal of Military Studies*, 7(1), 111-130.
 51. Suri, M. (2024, November). *Dragon on Ice: China's Geostrategic Interests in the Arctic*. Institute for National Security Studies (INSS). Retrieved from <https://www.inss.org.il/publication/north-pole/>
 52. Tripathi, S. S. (2018). *India's Foreign Policy: The "Modi Doctrine"*. SWP Comment 2018/C07. Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik. Retrieved from (https://www.swp-berlin.org/publications/products/comments/2018C07_wgn_Tripathi.pdf)
 53. Tuckfield, H. S., Marshall, W. C., & Tuckfield, H. (2025, March 21). *The Chennai-Vladivostok Maritime Corridor: A Game-Changer for Indo-Russian Relations*. The Indo-Pacific Studies Center. Retrieved from <https://theindopacificstudiescenter.org/the-chennai-vladivostok-maritime-corridor-a-game-changer-for-indo-russian-relations/>
 54. Unacademy. (n.d.). *India's Arctic Policy on Arctic Regions*. Retrieved from <https://unacademy.com/content/upsc/study-material/general-awareness/indias-arctic-policy-on-arctic-regions/>
 55. Universal Institutions. (n.d.). *India's Strategic and Sustainable Engagement in the Arctic*. Retrieved from <https://universalinstitutions.com/indias-strategic-and-sustainable-engagement-in-the-arctic/>
 56. Universal Institutions. (n.d.). *India's Strategic Stakes in the Arctic Region Explained*. Retrieved from <https://universalinstitutions.com/indias-strategic-stakes-in-the-arctic/>
 57. US Department of State. (2019, May 6). *Looking North: Sharpening America's Arctic Focus* (Remarks by Secretary of State Mike Pompeo). Retrieved from <https://www.state.gov/looking-north-sharpening-americas-arctic-focus/>
 58. US Department of State. (2025, January 10). *Sanctions on entities involved in Russia's Arctic LNG 2 project..*
 59. Vajiram & Ravi. (n.d.). *India's Role in the Arctic: A Strategic and Economic Perspective*. Retrieved from <https://vajiramandravi.com/current-affairs/indias-role-in-the-arctic-a-strategic-economic-perspective/>
 60. Vivekananda International Foundation. (2023, November 28). *Norway values India-Norway cooperation on Arctic: Norwegian*

- Ambassador*. Retrieved from <https://www.vifindia.org/print/13405>
61. Wang, J. (2024, August 28). *China's Arctic Strategy Amid Geopolitical Shifts*. Centre for Strategic and Contemporary Research (CSCR). Retrieved from <https://cscr.pk/explore/themes/politics-governance/chinas-arctic-strategy-amid-geopolitical-shifts/>
62. Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Chennai–Vladivostok Maritime Corridor*. Wikipedia. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chennai%E2%80%93Vladivostok_Maritime_Corridor
63. Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Himadri (research station)*. Wikipedia. Retrieved from [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Himadri_\(research_station\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Himadri_(research_station))
64. Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research*. Wikipedia. Retrieved from(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Centre_for_Polar_and_Ocean_Research))
65. Xiao, J. (2024, October 2). China's Coast Guard Joined by Russians on First Patrol in Arctic. *BNN Bloomberg*. Retrieved from <https://www.bnnbloomberg.ca/business/international/2024/10/02/chinas-coast-guard-joined-by-russians-on-first-patrol-in-arctic/>
66. Zaikov, K., & Bhagwat, A. (2024). The Cooperation Between Russia and India in the Arctic zone of the Russian Federation. *Administrative Consulting*. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/a/acf/journal/y2024id2606.html>
67. Zhuang, J. (n.d.). *India's Arctic Engagement*. University at Buffalo. Retrieved from <https://www.eng.buffalo.edu/~jzhuang/arctic/india.html>